

Guidelines to improve new business models at Living Labs

D4.4. Guidelines to improve new Business Models at Living Labs

Summary

Objectives:

The main objectives of deliverable D4.4 is the development of guidelines to create and improve circular business models (CBMs) within the context of the LLs in the B-WaterSmart project. Secondly the guidelines are applied to develop CBM based on the circularities identified (D4.3) in the LLs.

Methodology:

The methodology employed in the creation of this document involved a preliminary literature review, followed by the design and development of guidelines derived from this review. These guidelines were then applied to the LL's circular solution to develop CBM, utilizing information obtained through interviews with the LLs, data requests, external sources, and other project-related documents.

Results and findings:

- Guidelines to improve new business models in LLs.
- Application of guidelines for proposal of CBMs based on circular solutions in the LLs.
- Conclusions are presented on the current state of development of the CBMs and their next steps.

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- PP = Restricted to other programme participants
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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AD	Anaerobic Digestion
AdTA	Águas do Tejo Atlântico
AdP	Águas de Portugal
AMAEM	Aguas Municipalizadas de Alicante, Empresa Mixta
ANBI	Unione Regionale Consorzi Gestione e Tutela del Territorio e Acque Irrigue
APA	Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente
ARERA	Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente
ARH	Administração da Região Hidrográfica
ARPAV	Agenzia Regionale per la Prevenzione e Protezione Ambientale del Veneto
ARS LVT	Administração Regional de Saúde de Lisboa e Vale do Tejo
BM	Business Model
BMI	Business Model Innovation
BWS	B-Water Smart
CBM	Circular Business Model
CBMC	Circular Business Model Canvas
CBMI	Circular Business Model Innovation
CE	Circular Economy
CEW	Circular Economy of Water
CoP	Community on Practice
D	Deliverable
DMK	Deutsches Milchkontor
EF	East Frisia
ENEL	Ente Nazionale per l'Energia Elettrica
EPAL	Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres
EPSAR	Entidad Pública de Saneamiento de Aguas Residuales
ERSAR	Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos

IS	Industrial Network
kWh	Kilowatt hour
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LL	Living Lab
LNEC	Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
OOWV	Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environment
PSKW	Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt
R&DI	Research, Development and Innovation
RO	Reverse Osmosis
SBM	Sustainable Business Model
SCBM	Sustainable Circular Business Model
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
UF	Ultrafiltration
UV	Ultraviolet
VLAQWA	Vlaams Kenniscentrum Water
WP	Work Package
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

Revision history

The table below provides detailed explanations of the integration of the changes requested as part of the final project review.

Feedback received	How the feedback has been integrated in D4.4
<p>The executive summary shall be reviewed as it rather stands as an introduction. The first paragraph in the executive summary should be reviewed as it is unclear, and the executive summary should highlight what the key points are, and what should be communicated to the audience who will read the document. It should include the summaries of each LL, which are currently in the conclusion part</p>	<p>Following the review's request, certain sections of the document have been reorganized. It has been determined that the conclusions section more effectively serves the purpose of an executive summary, as it encompasses all the aspects highlighted in the review. Therefore, it has been adopted as the executive summary in the revised document.</p>
<p>The introduction should be reviewed to make it less complex and rather address the link with T.4.3 of the DoA, provide clear objectives, explain the rationale of this deliverable and briefly describe the sections of the report. There should also be a qualification of the results because the implementation/experimentation phase will be mostly done after the project ends.</p>	<p>The introduction has been restructured to make it simpler and more direct, addressing the requests made in the review.</p> <p>A paragraph has been introduced for the qualification of the results</p>
<p>-The introduction should better outline what the benefits and limitations of the exercise are (in a form of bullet points). It should also better outline what is required (in terms of e.g., financial model, governance, policy and regulation etc) to fully deploy CE in the water sector. There are a lot of interesting and important issues that are raised in relation to CE, in the report. Nonetheless, they are lost in the 160 pages.</p>	<p>This contribution, once evaluated and completed, was deemed more appropriate as part of the conclusions, as it reviews the exercise carried out, and it makes more sense to address the impacts of this exercise in the conclusions. However, if necessary, it could be moved to the introduction. In any case, a reference has been made in the introduction indicating that these analyses can be found in the conclusions.</p>

<p>-The analysis that is included in the introduction should be “merged” with the introduction of Section 2 (see below).</p> <p>The introduction of section 2 should stand as a separate section and be much clearer about the definition of CBMs and outline why it is important to deploy these concepts in the water sector.</p> <p>The definition and objectives of the CBMs should be better highlighted.</p>	<p>A new, more user-friendly section has been created, merging both sections.</p> <p>We have included a better-highlighted definition and objectives of the CBMs to provide more clarity and context for the reader.</p>
<p>Section 2 “Guidelines to improve new business models in LL” should be reviewed.</p> <p>There are a lot of references to other Tasks and WPs. What are the key ideas that relate to D. 4.4? It is unlikely that the future reader will consult all the deliverables.</p>	<p>The references to other tasks and work packages (WPs) were included because, at the time of the delivery of this document (D.4.4), many of those activities were still under development or had not been delivered, such as D1.4 (m48), D7.8 (m44), D4.3 (m42), D4.5 (m48), D2.14 (m48), and D2.15 (m48).</p> <p>Additionally, the guidelines proposed in this document are designed as a set of best practices. Therefore, the references to those tasks and WPs are not intended to delve into their content but rather to indicate that the specific activities mentioned were being implemented or would be implemented within the project.</p> <p>In this sense, the references serve to contextualize and connect the recommendations proposed here with the ongoing work of the project, highlighting how those specific activities inform and complement the development of circular business models (CBMs). This explains why the citations are made in reference to the concrete work carried out in the project, without elaborating on them extensively within this document.</p>
<p>The report should better highlight how the outcomes and analysis of the steps before the detail design, will inform the latter.</p>	<p>To clarify this aspect, we have included a section that briefly explains the influence of the previous phases on the detailed design.</p> <p>3.5.5. Connection of the Previous Phases with the Detailed Design</p>

<p>The report only describes the technological steps (e.g. East Frisia, Venice LLs).</p>	<p>As can be observed, the document proposes a guide of best practices for developing CBMs in a way that facilitates achieving the objectives. This is done by structuring the work through defined phases, analyzing the main errors that are usually made, and even providing a checklist, emphasizing the need to document the work with final reports at each phase. Additionally, a practical exercise was carried out to adapt the existing information to this proposed framework in order to develop preliminary CBMs based on that information, as mentioned in the report.</p> <p>The overall project was defined in phases, which, in some cases, meant that not all the necessary information was available at the time of this exercise. Therefore, the information that was included reflects what was available, as is the case with these LLs. In some LLs, experimental phases were very focused on technological solutions, which did not allow for an adequate flow of information to go beyond what has been presented. As can be seen, the reports for each LL vary in depth, and this is solely due to the information available at the time the report was created.</p>
<p>The report does not describe enough how the design and piloting stages will be informed by the previous steps, even if they are delivered beyond the project end. The report could for instance give 2 examples.</p>	<p>It is not clear what this request is referring to, as the document consistently emphasizes the importance of the previous phases in each of the following ones, even explaining how it is an iterative process. Providing two examples is not considered appropriate, given that the state of the projects at the time of writing the report, and the fact that in many cases the proposed structure in the guidelines was not followed, means that there is a lack of the basic structure needed to concatenate the phases.</p> <p>Furthermore, the document presents sufficient information on the key aspects of the framing, such as the sections on Key Dependencies, Risks, and Opportunities, as well as Barriers and Drivers (Macro level). In the scoping phase, detailed analyses of key actors (in other documents), existing infrastructure, and value chains are carried out, which delineate the CBM that is developed in the following phases.</p>

	<p>In the ideation phase, the preliminary assessments are generally missing, although there are descriptions of the value chains that provide basic information to delimit the detail design, while also showing the CBMC and the SWOT Analysis.</p>
Typos to be corrected on page 35, 61, 64.	Done.

Executive summary

In the deliverable we have presented guidelines for the innovation of CBM that respond to the needs of the water sector, regulated environments, LLs and non-market or hybrid circular solutions. As a result, a methodology for the implementation of good practices has been proposed through guidelines that can be used by users who intend to develop CBMs based on circular solutions in LLs.

During the development of the guidelines, and with the aim of making them specific to the BWS project environment, reference is made to the work carried out in other project documents. This has allowed to make a first approximation work to interrelate different work units of the BWS project under the same framework, and thus to present a roadmap for the development and implementation of CBMs in LLs.

One of the results obtained from these guidelines is that they allow the development from a holistic perspective, which considers both macro and micro aspects of circular solutions, of a coherent narrative for the design of CBMs that can be adapted to the context and needs of both LLs with a strong enabling orientation (municipal bodies) as well as for LLs with a more technical orientation (water treatment plants). This approach has been necessary due to the non-market or hybrid application context that characterises many of the circular solutions identified in the LLs, which makes it particularly important to assess the intangible elements of CBM, and therefore the framing of the solutions in the contexts of action.

Another fundamental aspect of the guidelines is the presentation of common mistakes during the execution of the different stages in the CBM innovation process, so that they can be taken into account in order to avoid possible failures and errors in the implementation of CBMs. Additionally, self-assessment documents (e.g. checklists) have been developed, which can be used to guide users in exercises, analyses, and relevant documents according to good practices in CBM innovation in each of its stages. It has been considered important to stress the need to generate partial stage closure documents, that allow the development of the projects to be evaluated and also facilitate transparency during the execution.

The guidelines have been put into practice for the analysis of some of the circular solutions proposed in each of the LLs, with emphasis on the analysis of one circular solution per LL (selected on D4.3). On the one hand, the aim of their application has been to collect the information developed in the project, so that the innovation process followed by the CBMs can be represented. On the other hand, a preliminary CBMC have been drawn up for each solution that visually reflect the most relevant aspects of the proposed CBMs according to the information available up to the date of preparation of this document. Finally, their application has made it possible to detect the strengths and weaknesses of the proposed CBMs, as well as to determine their current state of development and the actions to be taken for their development. The circularities that have been studied are listed in the following table:

LL circularities examined and CBM developed through guidelines application.

Circularity ID	LL	Description	Baseline Business Model type (linear/circular/new)	Scaled-up Business Model
C1	AL	Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion	CBM	CBM
C7	LI	Urban water reuse for irrigation	LBM	CBM
C9	VE	Increase of industrial water reuse	LBM	CBM
C12	EF	Increase water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate (cow water)	LBM	CBM
C14	FL	Stormwater reuse for irrigation through a subirrigation system	NBM	CBM
C17	BO	Increase of energy production through biogas	LBM	CBM

In general terms, for all the solutions, the innovation processes of the CBMs are still in a preliminary development phase, and detailed analyses are required in order to adjust and define the final CBMs. The most recurrent aspects hindering the development of the CBMs at this stage are detailed financial analyses have not been carried out to define revenue models, the organisational structures of scaled solutions have not been defined or the operating models are still uncertain, financing mechanisms have not been defined, or implementation plans have still not been developed. Another common issue is that most of the solutions studied are directly conditioned by the adaptation of regulatory policies to cope with the uncertainties that affect them. In such a way that either the products they generate are made attractive in the current market by promoting incentives and restrictions to the use of certain conventional products (e.g. fresh water), laws and regulatory policies are adapted to favour their implementation (e.g. use of reused water for certain uses), or financing mechanisms are promoted to incentivize the adoption of these CBMs. These aspects are currently part of the studies being developed in the project.

Another aspect that can be drawn from the CBM analysis and which is particularly necessary to emphasise is the lack of transparency that can be generated due to the lack of follow-up documentation of the projects, and initial stage documentation, which highlights the importance of adequately documenting all the stages of the project.

The summaries of the analysis of the preliminary CBMs for each LL are presented below.

Alicante LL:

The circularity studied is **C1: Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion**. The existing starting business model is a CBM (developed anaerobic digestion), and its innovation is developed in the context of a LL driven by a water utility. The solution increases the level of circularity of the WWTP processes by introducing an organic substrate to the digestion sludge and thus

increasing biogas production. The innovation strategy implemented is a **CBM Transformation** and the innovation purposes are aligned with the development of a **Hybrid model SCBM: Scale-up sufficiency and Scale-up stewardship**. The CBM can be classified as a **Hybrid model: Circular inputs and Resource recovery** and **Industrial Symbiosis** subtype. Following the LL's specific objectives of becoming a biofactory, the development of this CBM will potentially drive the development of an Industrial Symbiosis network, which, in this case, would have a low level of centralisation and coordination, due to an early stage of maturity. At the same time, the solution is conceived from the outset for the self-consumption of the biogas generated and thus to promote the self-sufficiency of the plant. The value proposition offered, in addition to the energy resilience of the plant, is the treatment of waste for waste generators and the opportunity to enhance brand reputation and access to a local circular economy network that can generate other opportunities for the participants in the future.

In the preliminary CBM proposed through the CBMC, the following elements are yet to be defined:

- Key partners: during the project contact has been established with two organic waste suppliers, however, in order to reach the targeted feedstock volumes, agreements will have to be established with these suppliers, in addition to looking for other suppliers. Similarly, it will be necessary to define who will provide transport services for the waste from the collection point to the WWTP.
- The definition of the cost structure will have to be detailed in order to define the expected operational costs once the supplier structure is defined.
- The revenue streams that have been defined to date only by estimating economic savings from energy costs, but other revenue streams are yet to be defined (e.g. tipping fees).

Conclusions drawn from the CBM SWOT analysis:

- Strengths and opportunities: overall the solution proposed in the LL is aligned with the strategic objectives of the driving organisation. The development of the solution boosts the development of an industrial network and increases the capacities and competences to develop a stewardship role at local and regional level that will boost the development of the other circular solutions proposed (e.g. brines valorisation, nutrient recovery). In addition, the WWTP has partial infrastructure for the implementation of the solution, which reduces the necessary investment costs.
- Weaknesses and threats: the main hindrances are the entry into an organic waste market (with demand for "high quality" waste); the management of a complex value chain with multiple stakeholders (technical and organisational) which make it necessary to allocate own resources for its management; and the regulatory restrictions for the generation of income through digestates.

The current state of development of CBM is in a "Detail analysis" phase. More detailed economic and financial feasibility studies are required, as well as the development of operational processes to reduce and minimize the uncertainties and elements that have been identified. One of the measures planned by the lead organisation is to develop, outside the BWS project, a pilot to evaluate operational aspects of the solution.

Lisbon LL:

The circularity studied is **C7: Urban water reuse for irrigation**. The existing starting business model is an LBM (use of fresh water for irrigation of urban green areas). The innovation strategy followed by the BM is **CBM Transformation** and the innovation purposes are aligned with the development of a

Purposeful stewardship type SCBM. The development of CBM is framed in the context of a LL driven by a public organisation. The main objective from a macro context for the LL that the solution aims to achieve is to enable the environment for the extended use of reclaimed water to limit the consumption of fresh water for non-potable uses in the city of Lisbon. The CBM can be classified as a **Hybrid model: Circular inputs and Resource recovery** and **Upcycling** subtype. The main value proposition is the production and distribution of reclaimed water for irrigation of publicly owned urban green areas with the municipality being the main end-user, although it is also foreseen for use in gardens owned by the state, local administrations, and some private owners with public access.

In the preliminary CBM proposed through the CBMC the following elements are still to be defined:

- Key partners: the organisational structure is preliminary but is not definitive.
- Cost structure: the costs of production and distribution of reclaimed water are unknown.
- Revenue Streams: the pricing mechanisms are not defined.

Conclusions drawn from the CBM SWOT analysis:

Strengths and opportunities: Firstly, there's a significant advantage in avoided costs through the reduced need to purchase drinking water for non-potable purposes like irrigation of green areas. Additionally, there's a remarkable alignment in vision among stakeholders and across levels, facilitating the promotion of water reuse. Moreover, the collective competences, capacities, and resources of organizations within the LL create a solid foundation for driving the necessary changes and establishing an enabling environment, which includes regulatory policy changes and heightened social awareness. Furthermore, the strategic plan for Lisbon includes the development of a distribution network for reclaimed water, while the availability of treated wastewater volume and the technical expertise of AdTA, supported by recent legislative developments, contribute to the production of reclaimed water. Lastly, the emphasis on constructing blue and green sustainable infrastructure not only enhances the city's resilience but also opens up a new market for reclaimed water, further reinforcing the potential for sustainable water management practices.

Weaknesses and threats: Urban water reuse is pioneering in Portugal, so an effort in reclaimed water quality monitoring is currently asked to users. The management of the reclaimed water distribution network is not yet defined. Additionally, significant investment in the construction of the reclaimed water distribution network and investment is needed in advanced treatment for Class-A reclaimed water production. The situation currently existing in the Lisbon water distribution service is, among other aspects, affecting the decision on the management of the reclaimed water distribution network. Moreover, external political and economic context not favourable for investments and impacting the goods supply chains.

The current state of development of CBM is in a "Detail analysis" phase. Given the context that affects the development of this CBM, conditioned especially by the existing regulation, the definition of key aspects for its development is still uncertain, requiring the overcoming of these barriers. One of the key aspects that have been identified is that the definition of the scoping of the solution must be clearer and more specific in order to facilitate the delimitation of the actions and develop analyses that are more approachable. In addition, the cost structure should be defined in more detail to be able to develop economic and financial analyses, as well as to define the organisational structures and operational procedures that will be necessary for the correct implementation of CBM.

East Frisia LL:

The circularity studied is **C12: increase water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate (cow water)**. The circular solution is framed in the context of a LL driven by a public water company in partnership with a dairy plant, a technology supplier, and a research institute. From a macro perspective the solution helps improving the sustainable management of the available water resources and guaranteeing water availability for the next generations in East Frisia.

The existing business model, from a water supplier's perspective is linear as it supplies drinking water for the identified cow water application. The business model innovation strategy follows a **CBM diversification**, although this is subject to the final organisational structure (e.g. operator model) of the scaled-up scenario. The innovation purpose is aligned with the development of a **Scaled-up sufficiency SCBM**, since the circular solution encourages reduction of drinking water consumption for industrial processes, and the use of cow water is an opportunity to expand production.

The value proposition for dairy plants is the provision of treated water volumes to save freshwater and maximize recirculation resources, while improving site security and generating beneficial marketing effects.

The preliminary CBM proposed from the developed CBMC identifies the following elements to be defined:

- Key partners: the organizational structure for the scale-up solution is still under evaluation.
- Cost Structure: investments and operational costs are still to be defined.
- Revenue Streams: have not yet been estimated.
- Environmental impacts: to be assessed.

Conclusions drawn from the CBM SWOT analysis:

Strengths and opportunities:

There is an established long-term relationship between the water supplier and dairy company. Moreover, the LL stakeholders are highly skilled in solutions related to the reuse of water. Furthermore, there is a close relationship to the public authorities, provided the public nature of the water supplier and longstanding established production site.

The solution provides the following opportunities: replication of the solution to other dairies in the region, update existent regulation to increase reuse potential of recycled process water, promote positive social and environmental impacts, as well as develop innovative collaborations and partnerships in other sites, and lastly expand the development of a CE market.

Weaknesses and threats:

The weaknesses and threats of the solution relates to the production costs of treatment of industrial water being more expensive than freshwater, thus the dependency in the medium term to public or public/private financing instruments. Also, the process is highly technical and specific, and requires the adoption of the technology for replication to other industries. Moreover, there is limited market expansion apart from the dairy industry (still, one of the most important employers in Germany). Lastly, the current regulations are restrictive for the intended reuse application.

The current state of development of the CBM is under the "Detail design" stage. Key aspects in the development of the CBM at this stage are the determination of the production and operating costs for the envisaged scenario. This is necessary in order to correctly determine the funding requirements, whether public or public/private, to ensure the sustainability of the solution. Similarly, it is necessary to define the organizational structure, as well as to design operational processes, contingency plans, and implementation plans. Additionally, the solution is affected by regulatory constraints as the intended reuse application is restricted under current regulations. It is necessary to adapt and/or create new policies and regulations to enable its implementation. These aspects allow the CBM to be reviewed and adjusted before proceeding to implementation.

Flanders LL:

The circularity studied is **C14: Stormwater reuse for irrigation through a subirrigation system**. There was no initial business model. The innovation strategy developed for its implementation is **CBM Circular Start-up** and its objectives are aligned with the development of a **Purposeful stewardship SCBM**. The circular solution is framed in the context of an LL driven by a set of public organisations combining research institutes, water companies and public authorities. The main objective pursued through circularity is the capture of stormwater for infiltration back into the groundwater aquifer through a synergy with the farming sector. The **CBM** can be classified as **Circular inputs** of the **Biomimicry** subtype. The value proposition offered is increasing water security of farmers during dry months or drought events by recharging the groundwater system with stormwater while increasing the soil moisture of their crops by performing the infiltration of water through a subirrigation system. This improves the stormwater management of the city, improving resilience to climate change and protecting natural ecosystems.

The preliminary CBM proposed from the developed CBMC identifies the following elements to be defined:

- Value proposition: the value proposition that has been defined for the farmers, and for the community, will need to be confirmed according to the final participation they have within the circular solution.
- Key partners: the organisational structure of the solution outside the B-Water Smart project is not confirmed. The operating model to be implemented is under development.
- Cost structure: the operational costs have been estimated, but a detailed cost structure is still pending.
- Revenue streams: revenue models and financing mechanisms to cover operational costs have not been defined and are currently under evaluation with relevant stakeholder groups.
- Customer segments and Targeted solutions: depending on the value proposition, the organisational structure, and the revenue models applied, these elements will need to be reviewed.

Conclusions drawn from the CBM SWOT analysis:

- Strengths and opportunities: It is a project that effectively drives the collective collaboration of different stakeholders with a potential to drive the dissemination of circular practices, raises social awareness, and fosters the development of synergies between sectors. It has an environmental impact that is clearly aligned with natural resource protection and climate resilience. Infrastructure investment costs are partially covered by redevelopment plans that were planned before the BWS.

- **Weaknesses and Threats:** One of the problems identified in the project is the definition of a strong value proposition to the end-users and an absence of ex-ante feasibility studies. Given that the orientation of the solution is very much towards environmental protection of the ecosystem, and the quantification of the impact is difficult to define, the definition of revenue models to cover the application is unclear. At the same time, current regulations on the application of stormwater use in irrigation imply on the one hand high requirements on water quality, and on the other hand are not clear enough on the allocation of responsibilities for stormwater management.

The current state of development of the CBM is in the "Detail Design" phase. However, it is important to note that the stormwater reservoir, adapted for application in the planned circularity, has already been constructed. However, there are still many uncertainties in the development of a sustainable CBM. Some of the reasons identified include the absence of preliminary feasibility studies, as well as a lack of clarity and definition of value propositions in the initial (ex-ante) project planning phases. Efforts are currently being made to identify different alternatives for financing operational costs to clarify some of these uncertainties, as well as to define an organisational structure for the solution beyond the BWS. Regarding the regulatory aspects affecting the solution, work is being developed in the project that aims to overcome these barriers both by adapting policies and regulation, as well as by developing pilots to provide visibility and demonstrate the technical feasibility of the solution.

Venice LL:

The circularity studied is C9: Increase of industrial water reuse. Increase of water reuse for agriculture has not been studied. The initial business model affected by the circular solution is an LBM (discharge of effluent to the ecosystem) and the innovation strategy followed is that of CBM diversification. After analysing the innovation pathway of the business model, a Scale-up stewardship SCBM archetype has been defined. Furthermore, the CBM can be classified as a Resource Recovery model of the Upcycling subtype. The LL under which this solution is developed is driven by a water company.

The main objective pursued through the implementation of this circularity is increasing the reclaimed water reuse for industrial processes. The industries in the area currently receive both freshwater and industrial water (produced from freshwater by a private company) supplies. The value proposition offered is supplying reclaimed water fit for industrial processes produced through a tertiary treatment process using an Ultrafiltration and Reverse Osmosis System. The reclaimed water guarantees a stably high quality for industrial purposes and stable volume availability over time in comparison with the freshwater quality variation and related risk (e.g. drought events). Its implementation will allow the wwtp to, on the one hand, "Create value from waste" and thus improving the circularity of the plant's processes and, on the other hand, improve the climate resilience of the city and the municipality.

The adoption of a role as stewardship by the lead organisation must be examined through the integrative perspective that the LL has in its context of action, taking into account the set of solutions being studied, and that its objectives are aligned with the enablement and widespread use of reclaimed water (and other recovered resources) in the local and regional environment.

In the preliminary CBM proposed from the developed CBMC, following elements are still to be defined:

- **Key partners:** definition of the organisational structure depending on the roles and responsibilities in the distribution of reclaimed water to industries.
- **Customer segments and Targeted solutions:** definition of all customers, and the end-user's final scenario/puzzle.

- **Cost Structure & Revenue Streams:** The cost structure has not yet defined the distribution costs of reclaimed water, nor the investment in additional distribution infrastructure that would be necessary. Consequently, the revenue streams (e.g. water tariffs), which depend on the previous two points, have not been fixed.

The conclusions that can be drawn from the SWOT analysis of the CBM:

- **Strengths and opportunities:** Overall the competences and capacities of the driving organisation favour the implementation of the solution. The technology adopted allows the production of stable reclaimed water of different quality and application for different uses, that allows adjusting the value proposition to different uses. In addition, the infrastructure costs are partially covered. The opportunities detected are the good relationship with the authorities, which favours the possibility of adapting policies, and also that industries are interested in the consumption of reclaimed water.
- **Weaknesses and Threats:** The existence of a private organization that sells industrial water produced from fresh water to local industries could complicate matters. Moreover, one of the threats is the risk of not being able to cover the cost differences between industrial water (from freshwater) and reclaimed water (from WWTP effluent). Additionally, added to this is the risk of uncertain energy prices that may cause an increase in production and distribution costs. Lastly, another weakness is that the current regulation does not specifically incentivize the use of reclaimed water.

The current state of development of the CBM is in the "Detailed Design" phase. Because of the existing uncertainties and the risks presented by the CBM, it is essential during this stage to develop detailed financial analyses to define the cost structures and the costs of production and distribution of reclaimed water for different scenarios so that comparisons can be made with the freshwater tariffs that are being charged to local industries. In the case that costs of production and distribution of the alternative product would be higher than those actually paid for industrial water, it will be necessary to make an assessment to define the necessary financing mechanisms, as well as adaptations of policies and regulations, so that the use of reclaimed water can be incentivised.

Bodø LL:

The circularity studied is **C17: Increase of energy production through biogas**. The initial business model affected by the solution is an **LBM** (linear waste treatment process) and the innovation strategy followed is that of **CBM** diversification and the innovation purposes are aligned with the development of a **Hybrid SCBM: Purposeful sufficiency and Purposeful stewardship**. Furthermore, the **CBM** can be classified as a **Hybrid CBM: Circular Inputs and Resource Recovery** model of the **Industrial Symbiosis** subtype. The LL under which this solution is developed is driven by a public authority and the main partners are a waste management company and municipal water companies operating in the public sector.

The main objective pursued through the implementation of circularity is reducing pollution and increasing the efficiency of resources. The value proposition offered is improving the waste processes at the plant by maximizing resource efficiency by exploiting biogas recovery from sewage sludge and organic waste that can be transformed into electricity for the plant self-sufficiency. The implementation of the solution will allow the waste management company to "Create value from waste" and on the to "Maximize material and energy efficiency".

Unlike the other circular solutions in the project, in Bodø's LL, preliminary feasibility studies are still underway to determine the technology that will enable the circular solution and define the value chain. Thus, information available for the development of the CBM is limited. According to the innovation process, the CBM is still at the **Ideation stage**, and a Preliminary Assessment is being developed. However, a CBMC and a preliminary SWOT analysis have also been presented. Some of the conclusions derived from the SWOT are presented below:

- **Strengths and opportunities:** The competences and capacities of the waste management sector are aligned with the competences required for the management of a biogas production system. Furthermore, the plant has volumes of organic waste from its nuclear business model that can be mixed with sewage sludge received from the wastewater treatment plants. Additionally, there are no competitors in the region, thus presenting an opportunity for market creation. Moreover, biogas generation projects are being promoted at the national level, which could lead to funding opportunities.
- **Weaknesses and Threats:** some of the weaknesses that have been identified is that the transport of sewage sludge involves long transport distances which can affect the impacts and the level of circularity of the solution. Another potential hindrance is the high cost of the infrastructure and that returns on investment are generally low in self-consumption biogas projects. Finally, another weakness is that agreements between multiple municipalities (sewage sludge comes from several municipalities) may be complex due to the existing regional legislation. Other technical threats are the variability in the quality of substrates for biogas production, and on the other hand, the existence of regulatory barriers that limit the valorisation of digestate from sewage sludge.

1 Introduction

This deliverable is the result of the work carried out within Task 4.3 (T4.3) of the B-WaterSmart project. T4.3 aims to develop guidelines that enable the creation and implementation of Circular Business Models (CBMs) in the Living Labs (LLs). These CBMs are essential to promote the circular economy in the water sector, encouraging resource reuse, energy efficiency, and waste minimization. The transition toward circular models in the LLs is seen as a key strategy to overcome the challenges associated with sustainable water management.

The development of this deliverable originates from the need identified in T4.3 to have specific methodologies that assist LLs in adopting circular practices. The water sector faces multiple challenges, including increasing demand, regulatory pressure, and the need to adopt more sustainable practices. CBMs offer a way to address these challenges, transforming traditional linear practices into processes that contribute to closing cycles, optimizing resources, and generating shared value.

Objectives of the Deliverable

The main objectives of this deliverable are:

1. **Provide a clear and structured methodology** for designing and implementing CBMs in LLs. This involves creating a set of guidelines that guide the involved actors in the transition toward more circular business models, either by creating new CBMs or transforming existing ones.
2. **Apply these guidelines** in six European LLs (Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon, and Venice) to evaluate the proposed circular solutions. This analysis allows for identifying the specific challenges and opportunities of each LL, developing business models tailored to their particular context.
3. **Lay the groundwork for the future implementation** of CBMs. The models proposed and the analyses conducted in this document will serve as a starting point to guide the subsequent phases of implementation and experimentation.

Structure of the Document

To address these objectives, the document is structured into the following sections:

- **Section 1:** Provides a general introduction to the project's context, objectives, and the relevance of developing CBMs in the water sector.
- **Section 2:** Presents the proposed guidelines for implementing CBMs in LLs, based on a literature review and existing methodologies for business model innovation. This section describes the stages of CBM development, from the initial definition of concepts to planning and execution.
- **Section 3:** Analyzes the application of these guidelines in the six LLs. For each LL, an analysis of the identified circular solutions, specific opportunities and challenges, and the design of CBMs tailored to its context is presented.
- **Section 4:** Summarizes the results obtained, discusses the learnings, evaluates the benefits provided and the limitations of the exercise, and presents the summaries of the analysis of the preliminary CBMs for each LL.

The implementation of the CE in the LLs of the water sector requires a combination of solid financial models, effective governance structures, adaptive regulatory frameworks, and continuous capacity development. The guidelines and analyses presented in the document provide a practical guide to address these requirements and facilitate the adoption of CBMs in regulated contexts

It is essential to clarify that the results presented in this document are preliminary. The implementation and experimentation phase of the CBMs will primarily occur after the project's conclusion. Therefore, the guidelines and business models proposed here should be understood as an initial framework that will require validation and possible adjustments once applied in a practical environment. The experience gained during future implementation will help refine the CBMs, incorporating the challenges and opportunities encountered in the reality of the Living Labs.

This document, therefore, aims to lay the necessary methodological and conceptual foundations for adopting circular practices in the water sector. Although specific solutions are still under development, the analyses presented here provide guidance for the transition toward more sustainable and circular business models. The ability to adapt these guidelines to different contexts will be key to the long-term success of CBMs.

2 Circular Business Models (CBM) in the Water Sector: Definition, Importance, and Strategic Implementation Guidelines to improve new business models in LLs

2.1 Brief definition of Circular Business Models (CBM)

As a general notion we start from the fact that a Circular Business Models (CBMs) are business strategies aimed at promoting sustainability by closing resource loops and maximizing the value of materials and products throughout their lifecycle. Unlike traditional business models based on linear “take-make-dispose” processes, CBMs focus on optimizing the efficient use of resources by promoting reuse, recycling, and resource recovery. In the water sector, this means reusing water, recovering valuable resources from wastewater, and ensuring that the water cycle is managed in a sustainable and circular manner.

So while the fundamental objective of a Business Model (BM) is to define how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value in a profitable way. This involves establishing strategies that allow offering products or services that meet customer needs while ensuring the financial viability and growth of the organization, the objective of a CBM expands these principles by including sustainability and resource efficiency as a central part of the strategy. In addition to seeking profitability, a CBM focuses on:

1. **Closing resource loops:** Extending the life cycle of products and materials through reuse, recycling, and recovery, reducing waste and the consumption of natural resources.
2. **Generating sustainable value:** Creating value propositions that are not only economically viable but also contribute positively to the environment and society, aligning with the principles of the circular economy.
3. **Adapting to regulated environments:** Operating within the constraints and opportunities of regulatory environments, taking advantage of incentives and policies that promote the circular economy.

In essence, while a traditional BM focuses primarily on profitability and growth, a CBM has the additional objective of integrating sustainable and efficient resource use practices, seeking a balance between economic, environmental, and social value creation, thus ensuring its long-term viability.

CBMs in the water sector go beyond simple resource management; they involve the implementation of innovative solutions that transform wastewater into valuable resources, reduce pollution, and decrease the dependency on natural water sources. By adopting circular approaches, organizations can drive both environmental conservation and economic profitability through the adoption of sustainable technologies.

The main objectives of the CBMs in this context are:

1. **Optimize water use efficiency:** Promote the implementation of solutions that enable water reuse and recycling. An example mentioned in the document is the use of treated wastewater for irrigation, which involves adjusting existing processes to achieve efficient reuse.
2. **Promote resource recovery and valorization:** CBMs aim to close resource loops by recovering and valorizing materials such as nutrients and biogas from wastewater treatment. For instance, processes that increase biogas production or the treatment of industrial effluents for reuse are highlighted in the document.
3. **Develop attractive value propositions:** During the initial stages, it is crucial to define clear and attractive value propositions for end-users and to conduct preliminary feasibility studies to identify potential scenarios of non-feasibility. This includes considering the incentives, roles, and responsibilities of the stakeholders involved.
4. **Adapt to the regulatory environment:** Given the highly regulated nature of the water sector, CBMs also aim to promote changes in regulatory policies, facilitating the adoption of circular solutions. In this regard, the development of CBMs is influenced by the need to comply with existing regulations, thus fostering the creation of favorable contexts for their implementation.

This definition and these objectives provide the framework to understand how CBMs are integrated into the LLs and how they guide the methodologies proposed in the document.

2.2 What is Business Model Innovation (BMI) and why is it important for the CBMs we are going to develop?

As we have seen, BM can be defined as simplified representations of the value proposition, value creation and delivery, and value capture elements and the interactions between these elements within an organisational unit (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). The elements defining value are generally described as follows:

- the value proposition: the product or service offering and the target customer – what value is offered to whom.
- the value creation and delivery: the product or service's specific features and the distribution channels – how is the value provided?
- the value capture: cost structure and revenue streams – how does the company generate value?

Figure 1 Business Model representation of value proposition, creation, delivery, and capture (from: Business Models in a Circular Economy by EEA and ETC/WMGE illustration by CSCP)

BMs that apply linear economy processes can be referred to as linear business models (LBM) when they apply a value logic of take-make-waste, where resources are extracted to make products that eventually end up as waste and are disposed of (e.g., landfills). It is a polluting system that degrades natural systems and is the driver of global challenges, including climate change and biodiversity loss (EMF, 2015).

Conversely, a sustainable business models (SBM) can be defined as BM that incorporate pro-active multi-stakeholder management, the creation of monetary and non-monetary value for a broad range of stakeholders and hold a long-term perspective (Geissdoerfer et al. 2018) and apply sustainability principles to their value chain.

A CBM is sometimes referred in the literature as a subtype of SBM which incorporates principles of circular economy (CE) into the value logic of its processes, by using different circular strategies: closing, narrowing, extending, and intensifying resource loops, and dematerializing (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020). However, it is often emphasized that there is an imperfect overlap between SBM and CBM (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). CBMs can lead for example to adverse effects on employee working conditions, thus causing social impact, or they may entail greater material and energy usage compared to their linear counterparts, triggering environmental impact (De Keyser & Mathijs, 2023). There are numerous reasons why CBM adoption might not promote sustainability (Whalen, 2019), including the potential for rebound effects (Zink and Geyer, 2017). For this reason, the conceptualization of CBMs will be expanded by introducing Sustainable Circular Business Models (SCBMs) and the definition of innovation pathways (De Keyser & Mathijs, 2023). Also referred as archetypes, SCBMs, are conceived and used in this document as a supporting classification to develop CBMs. For practical reasons, CBMs in this document may sometimes be referred as sustainable CBM, to avoid using the concept

SCBMs interchangeably, leaving the latter as a complementary concept and used for its intended application in the document, rather than as a replacement of the most traditionally used term of CBM.

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. depicts the relationship between a BM, SBM, and CBM.

Figure 2 Relationship between BM, SBM and CBM (from Circular business models: A review by Geissdoerfer et al. 2020).

The process of transforming or creating new CBMs is referred to as CBMI and is a strategic process that specifically focuses on conceptualizing and implementing CBMs (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020). Business Model Innovation (BMI) is an iterative journey that includes experimentation, piloting, gaining experience, and ultimately scaling up solutions (Bocken et al., 2019).

Applying an iterative methodology is very important for several reasons. Firstly, they allow for rapid adaptation to changing needs. By using iterations, teams can constantly test, experiment, and adjust their developments, which gives them the flexibility to evolve and even adapt objectives if necessary. In addition, this process fosters continuous innovation. By iterating, new opportunities, improvements and circular solutions can be discovered that might not have been identified initially. This constant improvement mentality is key, in the context of LLLs, to CBMI before scaling-up circular solutions and ensuring sustainability.

Another crucial aspect of iterative processes is risk reduction. By iterating, errors or potential problems can be identified and corrected at an early stage, before investing large resources or launching products and/or services. This minimises financial and reputational risks, as it allows to pivot and adjust without significantly compromising the operation.

Thus, as it can be seen, iterative processes are necessary to avoid failure of implementation of circular solutions due to rigid approaches to action.

2.3 Importance of CBMs in the Water Sector

Implementing CBMs in the water sector is crucial for addressing current challenges related to water scarcity, pollution, and the inefficient use of natural water sources. CBMs offer a way to optimize water usage, reduce waste, and promote the recovery of resources, thereby contributing to the overall sustainability of water management.

Adopting CBMs allows organizations to reduce their dependence on stressed natural water sources, minimize waste generation, and decrease pollution. This paradigm shift not only benefits the environment by conserving and protecting water resources but also stimulates innovation and economic profitability. By transforming wastewater into valuable resources, such as recycled water or energy, the water sector can create new business opportunities and drive the adoption of more sustainable technologies.

In addition to environmental and economic benefits, CBMs foster a collaborative approach to water management. By treating water as a shared resource, CBMs encourage the involvement of multiple stakeholders, including public authorities, water companies, and consumers, in creating a water-smart environment.

2.4 Challenges and Implementation of CBMs in the Water Sector

The successful implementation of CBMs in the water sector is inherently complex, as it often occurs within a highly regulated environment. Regulatory policies and legislation play a critical role in shaping the transition toward a circular economy. Effective regulations provide the framework necessary for promoting circular practices while discouraging environmentally harmful ones. In this context, Circular Business Models face significant barriers, including high production costs, regulatory constraints, and market limitations. For example, water reuse and resource recovery initiatives often encounter higher costs compared to conventional alternatives such as freshwater or traditional fertilizers. Furthermore, high infrastructure investment costs typically result in low returns on investment, which can deter public and private stakeholders from pursuing circular solutions without sufficient external incentives or policy interventions.

Given these challenges, it is crucial to consider both market and non-market solutions for CBMs. Non-market solutions are particularly relevant in scenarios where water companies offer products or services to municipalities, where the environment is so regulated that pricing is not applicable, or where the final product or service is designed for self-consumption. Therefore, the analysis of CBMs must go beyond traditional classifications (such as product-as-a-service, circular inputs, resource recovery, product extension, or sharing platforms) to incorporate social, environmental, and enabling aspects in their evaluation. This holistic approach allows for the definition of sustainable circular business models (SCBMs) that consider the broader context in which these solutions are developed, as well as the driving factors for innovation, following a triple bottom line approach.

2.5 Role of Living Labs (LLs) in CBM Development

Living Labs (LLs) are instrumental in the development and implementation of CBMs, providing a space to adapt and enable the context for circular solutions. In the framework of the BWS project, LLs undertake various activities aimed at fostering a water-smart environment, including the development of digital support technologies, innovation in governance models, policy reviews, stakeholder

engagement, and awareness-raising initiatives. These activities are directly related to the development of new CBMs and operate across different scales, from local to regional/national.

In LLs, both the process of enabling the context and developing new CBMs occur in parallel, highlighting the importance of applying a holistic CBM innovation process. However, the multidisciplinary nature of LLs means that defining CBMs for circular solutions is not straightforward, especially when their implementation is heavily influenced by regulatory contexts. Therefore, a CBM innovation process that considers macro, meso, and micro-level aspects is necessary to align circular solutions with the broader environment in which they will operate.

2.6 Towards a Holistic Evaluation of CBMs

Emphasizing the assessment of social, environmental, and enabling impacts (i.e., the intangible aspects of CBMs) is essential for developing value propositions that can offset potential financial challenges during implementation. CBMs focus on long-term sustainability; thus, their current lack of economic viability does not preclude future success. Environmental and social impact assessments, economic predictions, and scenario analyses are crucial tools for providing real information, managing expectations, and guiding the adaptation of policies and actions.

The analysis of quantitative and qualitative data using circular indicators is vital for evaluating and prioritizing circular solutions and developing sustainable CBMs in LLs. Preliminary feasibility studies and clearly defined value propositions for end-users are essential steps in this process. Additionally, clarifying the incentives, roles, and responsibilities of all stakeholders involved will ensure the development of CBMs aligned with the vision and objectives of the LLs.

Given the non-market or highly regulated market context in which most of the solutions are framed, the process of generating an economic feasibility analysis should start with a cost estimate. This estimate, being ex-ante, should not be exhaustive, but it will delimit a feasibility boundary and will open the analysis to the minimum return needs of the project in terms of possible revenues, possible savings, need for subsidies, need for financial support, etc., that the solutions must achieve or the regulatory change that must be implemented by the regulators if the projects are to be viable.

2.7 Preliminary Considerations for the Analysis

As we have seen, the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data to measure the impacts of circular solutions through circular indicators is essential. In deliverable D4.3, an analysis of the circular indicators of some of the circular solutions in the LLs has been carried out with the aim of measuring economic, environmental, and social impacts. However, given the parallel elaboration of this document, and its delivery in the same month of the project development, the results collected in D4.3 have not been included.

During the execution of task T4.3 and the elaboration of this document, the absence of preliminary feasibility studies of the selected circular solutions in LLs has been observed. For the improvement of BM (or CBM) to CBM (or more circular) in LLs, it is essential that during the initial planning phases, and more specifically in the selection process of the circular solutions, clear and attractive value propositions for the end-users are defined in advance, and that preliminary feasibility studies are developed to detect at least possible non-feasibility scenarios of the projects. In addition, it is of great importance that the incentives, roles, and responsibilities of the stakeholders involved are clarified. In

this way, it will be possible to develop CBMs that are aligned with the vision and objectives of the LLs, as well as to ensure their sustainability.

It should be noted that the CBMs that have been developed are framed within, as will be seen in the guidelines, an initial phase of its development (concept phase), and are therefore preliminary, which should be reviewed and improved by the LLs as further detailed analyses are carried out.

For all these reasons, this document proposes the development of best practice guidelines that can lead LLs in the BMI towards sustainable CBMs in regulated environments, such as the water sector. These guidelines are intended to be applicable within LLs, facilitating the development of CBMs based on circular solutions, and serving as assistance in identifying relevant contextual aspects, existing barriers, and actions required for their successful implementation.

3 Guidelines to improve new business models in LLs

The guidelines have been designed, drawing inspiration from sources within the literature on BMI and other frameworks used for implementing CE principles in organizations (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017; BS 8001 2017). Moreover, the guidelines have been drawn up considering their complementarity use with the circular business model canvas (CBMC) as a support tool to use for CBMI.

The guidelines are presented following a four key stages structure:

Stage 1) Framing and Scoping

Stage 2) Ideation

Stage 3) Detail design

Stage 4) Implementation

At each of these stages, concepts and classifications, the application of good practices and other tools will be presented for a better process in the development of CBM.

Furthermore, a **Checklist** is provided at the end of this chapter (section 2.7) to serve as the user of this guide to review all the activities and actions that should have been carried out during each of the Stages and Phases of the CBM development process.

Some of the content provided in the guidelines is based on a literature review on CBMs. The practitioner can refer to **Annex A** for further information on the concepts and classifications outlined in this document.

3.1 Initial delimitation of concepts

In line with good practices of CBMI in LLs, the design process of CBMs can be defined in two main moments: a preparation moment (planning) and an execution moment (action-oriented). The preparation moment encompasses the initial stages (ex-ante, in this case before BWS project started) when the LL is conformed, and the solutions that want to be studied are defined. At this stage, a selection of solutions is carried out among a variety of ideas, according to the challenges affecting the context of the LL, the objectives set out, and the viability of these solutions. On the other hand, the execution moment involves a more active ideation phase which involves: a more detailed ideation stage of the predefined circular solutions, preliminary assessments, and the development of the CBM concept based on the most prominent ideas; followed by the experimentation, detailed analysis, piloting, and final implementation stage of the CBMs.

- Preparation moment:
 - Framing & Scoping Stage
- Execution moment:
 - Ideation Stage (Idea Generation phase, Preliminary assessment phase and Concept phase)
 - Detail Design Stage (Experimentation phase, Prioritization phase, Detail design phase and Pilot phase)
 - Implementation Stage.

To avoid confusion, it should be considered that the stages referred in the guidelines as the Framing of the LL and Scoping of the circular solutions under study in the LLs of the BWS, have been partially elaborated during an initial study stage prior to the start of the project, while some of this work is being elaborated in parallel with the development of this document. Therefore, it is necessary to consider that, in the guides presented, the Framing and Scoping stages are shown as an exercise of organisation and compilation of information that should be available prior to the start of the innovation of the CBMs of the circular solutions.

The CBM innovation process presented here, is based on the development of the BWS project, in which circular solutions were defined prior to the start of the project. As will be seen below, the development of this initial stage of ex ante studies has a determining effect on the innovation process of the CBMs that may be adopted, affecting from the Ideation stage onwards, which in the present project begins after the definition of circular solutions and the development of their scope (this last is sometimes, for some circular solutions, carried out before the BWS and for others during the BWS). The inclusion of these stages in these guidelines for the improvement of CBMs in LLs is based on the following reasons:

1. Making the presentation of the development of CBMs coherent by presenting the information analysed and collected during the initial phases, and in other project documents, on the context at different levels in which circular solutions are developed and studied in the LL.
2. This will allow to understand and comprehend how the organisation, vision, and objectives, this is the macro context of the LL affect the type of circular solutions proposed, and the potential CBMs that can be developed to implement it.
3. Emphasise the importance of considering in the initial planning stage, relevant considerations of CBMs in the pre-selection of circular solutions. In such a way that, the selected solutions facilitate and do not limit the innovation of CBMs.
4. Lastly, to emphasise the importance of developing preliminary feasibility studies during this stage of pre-selection of circular solutions, to make this information available as an initial input to start the development of CBMs.

During the presentation of the guidelines and the various stages and phases, reference shall be made to other project documents where information has been extracted or it can be further consulted, as well as those relevant documents that are foreseen to be realised.

Next an initial overview of these stages is provided.

Framing stage:

This is the initial stage, in which the general framework or context for the LL is established. It presents the problem or challenge to be addressed delimits and establishes the perspective from which the problem is analysed, identifying its components, causes and effects. The goal of this phase is to provide a clear and complete understanding of the problem before beginning to develop solutions.

This stage will not be developed in detail as the presentation of the strategic plans of the LLs will be presented in D1.4.

Scoping stage:

Scoping involves on the one side the definition of the project's solutions to be tested (as part of the initial stage, before start of the BWS, not considered in these guidelines), both circular and non-circular, and on the other hand the scoping of the different solutions (). During this stage, the aspects of the problem that will be addressed, the resources available, the constraints and the goals of the solutions are presented. It is a crucial phase to delimit the boundaries of the solutions to be tested and prevent these from becoming too broad or diffuse. It also establishes the criteria for evaluating the success and defines the parameters that will guide the solution process.

Upon completion of this phase, and once framing and the scoping have been conducted, a "Project Initiation Document" (PID) should be in place. This document serves as the foundation for the project, outlining its purpose, objectives, and initial scope. It provides a comprehensive overview of the project's context, identifying challenges, opportunities, and key stakeholders. The PID includes an initial assessment of project feasibility, risks, available resources, and a preliminary budget. This document plays a crucial role in guiding the project's early stages, offering a clear understanding of its goals, and setting the groundwork for subsequent planning and execution phases.

Ideation stage:

During the ideation stage, ideas to implement the pre-defined circular solutions are generated to address problems. Here creativity is encouraged and the generation of a wide range of ideas without restrictions is sought. It is a time of exploration and free generation of proposals, where techniques such as brainstorming, and design thinking can be used to stimulate the innovation and the identification of innovative opportunities.

In BWS, this task has been conducted as part of task **T4.2**. The identification of circular opportunities and the description of the circularities that will be further analysed in the LLs is presented on deliverable **D4.3**.

Following a preliminary assessment of these solutions, the concept is designed using tools such as the CBMC.

Thus, the framing focuses on understanding and defining the problem. Scoping delimits and sets the boundaries of the solutions, and the Ideation focuses on the creative generation of ideas to implement the solutions and the development of the concept. Although these phases are distinct, they are interdependent: an effective framing influences proper scoping, and the quality of scoping can influence the effectiveness of the ideation phase.

Detail Design stage

It is a crucial stage in which detailed analysis, experimentation and piloting the concept are required to test the products and services defining the value propositions for the CBMs, and deeper analyses of the financial aspects, environmental and social impacts, operative processes, and necessary resources required are carried out before its implementation evaluation and implementation.

Implementation stage:

In this phase, the execution of the new CBM takes place. Designed strategies and plans are executed.

Further information on the execution of this phase will be presented as part of the work on WP1 and WP7 on documents D1.4 and D7.8.

All these phases represent a continuous cycle in the CBMI, from the conception of ideas to the actual implementation of a new business approach.

3.2 Aspects to be considered in the planning work

It is common in many projects to give little importance to the planning or preparation work, which in many cases leads to not dedicating time or resources to the correct preparation of the project. Thus, it is common to make mistakes such as skipping stages, rushing to propose circular solutions without an adequate framing and scoping, which can result in difficulties to implement proposed solutions. Below are some of the most common errors in each of these stages:

- **Framing stage:** the main problem in this stage is to develop a limited or in some cases biased framing, often by narrowing the frame of the problem too early, missing the opportunity to consider different perspectives and causes.
- **Scoping stage:** There are two very basic and common problems in this stage:
 - First, defining a scope that is either too broad or too narrow, which leads to solutions that are hard to put in practice, or to solutions that do not fully cover the problem that has been identified.
 - The second most common mistake is not considering enough preliminary assessments, thus missing timeframes, resources or budget constraints when defining the scope and the circular solutions.
- **Ideation phase:**
 - Mistakes often come from creative self-censorship, due to the tendency to prematurely discard creative ideas as unconventional or impractical, which includes the fear of failure that unconventionality implies, feelings of security in a justified failure.
 - There is also a tendency not to encourage diversity of ideas or limit the participation of different perspectives. This reduces the variety and originality of the proposals, again keeping to the commonplace provides a sense of security.
 - Finally, not evaluating and prioritising the ideas generated leads to an inadequate selection or lack of follow-up of the most promising ideas.

During the initial stage of setting up the LL, it is essential to consider aspects that are fundamental for guaranteeing the viability of the CBMs that can be developed in these environments. The aspects that directly condition the development of sustainable CBMs are the selection of circular solutions that solve the problems identified at the outset and that present attractive value proposals for the end users, the development of feasibility studies for their ex-ante selection, and the identification and communication, from the outset, of the incentives and value captured by the stakeholders involved in the solutions.

Mistakes in the initial phases can be determinant in the subsequent development or implementation of CBMs for the circular solutions proposed by the LLs. This underscores the importance of working thoroughly in these initial phases, since a strong foundation is a key prerequisite for the successful implementation of CBMs.

3.3 Framing and Scoping of circular solutions in the Living Lab

The Framing stage aims at providing a macro level analysis of the context in which the LL operates, and the Scoping stage aims at analysis the meso and micro level context, to define solutions (circular and non-circular) addressing the problems identified, and also defining their scope. Meso and micro level context will be amalgamated for practical reasons, considering the complexity of a detailed analysis of some of the value chains for the circular solutions involving multiple actors. As it will be developed later, the macro and meso-micro perspectives or analysis have different parameters of action that make it necessary to establish distinct delimitation routes.

For the macro level, an introduction of the LL context in which the solutions are encompassed should be described based on the following aspects:

1. LL challenges
2. LL problem-owner
3. LL vision and objectives
4. LL partners
5. Key dependencies, risks, and opportunities
6. Barriers & Drivers

At the meso-micro level, the following aspects should be defined and described:

1. Defining the LL project solutions, site location and a state-of-the-art description.
2. Mapping ecosystem of stakeholders.
3. Mapping stakeholders captured value.

Given that circular solutions, and the CBMs that are developed from them, have the function of solving problems that affect different scales, from Macro to Micro aspects, in this section it is necessary to connect the different levels: providing a brief overview of the Macro context in which the circular solutions are located, as well as the meso and micro context that will define the more technical and practical aspects in the implementation of these solutions.

3.3.1 Framing LL macro level context

From a macro perspective, the main problems, needs or challenges present in the region or area of action affecting the solutions proposed in the LL, the main partners and their functions should be presented to provide the supporting rationale behind the study and potential implementation of the circular solutions. This will also provide a common ground for developing a holistic analysis that aligns the individual actions and solutions (not only circular), identify opportunities, establish meaningful collaborations, and assess the overall impact of the innovations generated within the overarching ecosystem.

These guidelines will briefly cover this phase, since this task will be outlined in the deliverable **D1.4** containing the Strategic Agendas for the LLs. However, the macro level is presented to contextualize, conceptualize the CBMs, analyse the CBMI pathways, identify barriers and drivers and guide the design phases. As indicated before it is a conditioning factor for the successful development of the CBM.

LL Challenges

The identification of problems and challenges is crucial for developing the value proposition around which the proposals of the new business models will revolve, as these challenges represent the difficulties or opportunities for improvement in the macro context, serving as focal points for innovation and the development of effective solutions.

Efficient water management in the context of urban coastal environments faces several significant challenges and risks. The intricate interconnection between urban expansion, the increasing demand of water by the industry and agriculture sector, the climate change, and the management of drinking and wastewater services creates a complex set of threats for water sustainability. Some of the most important risks faced in LLs are scarcity of water resources due to climatic events (e.g. droughts) or the overexploitation of natural water sources, inefficient integrated water cycle management, environmental effects such as saline intrusions and contamination of aquifers, seasonal increases in water demand, flooding and inefficiency in the stormwater management or the management of waste from water treatment. To all of these, we must add the challenges posed by current political and regulatory constraints, inefficiencies in governance models, an emerging circular market, the development of innovative and efficient infrastructures and technologies, as well as the need for financing instruments and business models that incentivize the implementation of circular and sustainable solutions to address these issues.

All these challenges are key starting points in the definition of the problem to be dealt with, which is why it is important to describe them clearly and, as we will see later, to propose innovation pathways for the business models. Challenges must be seen as drivers of change that will facilitate the development of solutions that improve the current situation, in such a way that there is no solution if there is no prior determination of a problem to be solved, this sequence transforms the problem into an opportunity, and this is where the purpose of the LL.

These challenges jeopardise municipal authorities and water companies from fulfilling their essential services of ensuring water security and their social and environmental commitment to meet the water demands of all communities and sectors.

Each of the LL has its own set of problems which condition its dependencies, risks, and opportunities, which require to prioritise one or another solution, therefore directly affecting the CBMI related to these.

LL problem-owners

Although it may seem obvious, it is important to clearly identify and characterise the problem owners in the LLs for each of the solutions, as this is essential to establish responsibility and direction for the development of the solutions. This owner acts as the main responsible for the problem or challenge to be addressed, providing the vision, and leading the efforts to find innovative solutions. It is generally the case, that the problem-owner will also be the LL owner, which will lead the directions of the whole project from a macro perspective.

In the Project, there are two types of problem-owners, water companies and municipalities, which mark the orientation of the proposed solutions in the LL. Therefore, this initial delimitation has an impact on the scope definition of the solutions, being broader in the case of municipalities (integrated management of water resources in the environment), while water companies are likely to focus on more specific solutions. This will also affect the participation of actors and collaborations, the focus on management or technology development and the temporality of the LL and their actions.

LL Vision and objectives

Circular solutions and the corresponding CBMs developed must respond to a shared vision and objectives developed in the project by the partners and stakeholders involved in the solutions. In the BWS project, the vision and strategic objectives of the LLs will be presented in deliverable **D1.4**.

LL Partners

At this point, a description of the strategic partners and key collaborators should be included. These partners can come from various areas, such as business, R&I institutions, governmental organisations or civil society, and their involvement brings resources, knowledge, and experience to address the challenges at hand.

The LLs, within the framework of B-Water Smart, are organised as follows:

- LL problem-owner: water companies or public authorities.
- LL mentor: solution providers (e.g. research institutes).
- Partners: technology providers, water companies, research institutes, solution providers etc.

As indicated before, two types of LLs can be distinguished: LLs oriented by water companies and LLs oriented by municipal authorities. In general, the differences between the objectives of a water utility and a municipal public authority in water management lie in their specific approaches and distinct roles. The water utilities focus generally on operational and financial efficiency, quality of customer service, investments and continuous improvement, expansion of coverage and regulatory compliance. On the other hand, the municipal authority seeks the general welfare of the community, sustainable development, efficient urban planning, community participation, harmonisation with municipal policies and response to crises and emergencies. The two entities work in collaboration, but their objectives reflect the different perspectives and responsibilities they have in the context of integrated water management.

Identification of key dependencies, risks, and opportunities

Assessing key dependencies, potential risks and opportunities allows anticipating possible obstacles and external factors that could influence the achievement of objectives. By identifying these variables, it is possible to design strategies to mitigate risks and take advantage of opportunities.

A summary is proposed below, according to the LL problem-owners approach (water utility or municipality) as a self-assessment guide to be able to detect possible dependencies, risks, and opportunities in each LL's environment. Note that these entities are interconnected and therefore dependencies, risks and opportunities can influence each other, especially if there is a direct relationship between the two.

Water companies' dependencies, risks, and opportunities:

- Specific dependencies: The water utility may depend on factors such as availability of water resources, infrastructure, and technology available, government regulations, sustainable financing instruments, market demand, among others.
- Own risks: Lack of financing instruments, technologies not economically viable, failures in water management services, regulatory changes, market competition, among others.

- Particular opportunities: Development of innovative technologies, expansion of the water treatment market, promoting changes in water regulation and governance through collaborative networks and innovation projects, among others.

Interconnection with the municipality:

- Indirect dependencies: The water treatment company might be indirectly dependent on municipal policies and decisions, such as urban planning, local water management, environmental regulations, among others.
- Risks and opportunities influenced: Changes in municipal policies may affect the demand for water supply and treatment services, opportunities to expand in certain areas, risks associated with water supply from municipal sources, among others.

In summary, although the water company has its own unique dependencies, risks and opportunities, the relationship and interdependence with the municipality means that there are also external factors that can significantly impact its operation and development at the local level.

The dependencies, risks, and opportunities for a municipality in the context of water management may differ from those of a water company, although as discussed, they may also have important interconnections:

Municipalities' dependencies, risks, and opportunities:

- Specific dependencies: May include financial resources allocated to integrated water management, existing infrastructure, regulation and governance, community support, among others.
- Own risks: Crisis due to lack of water supply services to certain communities or sectors, obsolete or non-existent infrastructure (e.g. distribution network for reclaimed water service), financial challenges, climatic changes affecting the availability of the resource (e.g. droughts or contamination problems of water sources), resistance to circular change of the community, among others.
- Particular opportunities: Development of innovative policies to promote reclaimed water service, recovery and reuse of resources derived from wastewater treatment; encourage active community participation in circular projects, promote environmental education and citizen awareness, conservation programmes; funding for improved infrastructure, implementation of more efficient technologies, among others.

Interconnection with water companies:

- Indirect dependencies: The municipality may depend on the capacity of water companies to ensure adequate supply, water quality and on the supply of potable and alternative water sources (fit-for-purpose water).
- Risks and opportunities influenced: Changes in the water company's services may affect the quality of the municipal supply service, the response to water-related emergencies, the cost of services to the community, among others.

In short, the municipality has its own set of dependencies, risks, and opportunities in relation to water supply and treatment, but it is also interconnected with the water companies, which means that changes or challenges in one can influence the other and vice versa.

Barriers and Drivers (Macro level)

The actual barriers affecting the achievement of the LLs vision to overcome the challenges affecting them, and the drivers supporting the vision should be described in this section.

In the BWS, this information has been analysed and is presented (in deliverables **D5.3**, **D5.5**) and will be further developed in other documents of the project by WP1 and WP5.

Here presented is a group of common barriers and drivers differentiated between internal and external based on the compilation work of Alwazeer & Carlsson (2023), to environmental settings that are useful for the self-assessment of the LLs:

Internal drivers:

- Organisational benefits
- Financial benefits
- People benefits

External drivers:

- Regulatory compliance
- Required by customers
- Stakeholder pressure
- Positive public image
- Environmental benefits

Internal Barriers:

- Lack of resources
- Lack of expertise, awareness, and knowledge
- Lack of training
- Lack of communication
- Lack of financial resources
- High investment cost for tools and unclear ROI
- Lack of support and poor management

External Barriers

- Lack of sharing information/collaboration between partners
- Lack of commitment from suppliers and partners
- Lack of efficient environmental measurement tools/ complexity of current tools
- Lack of government support/ guidelines and unclear regulation

For the detection and classification of Drivers and Barriers a sequence can be carried out in which:

- First of all, the information is processed internally, so that a PESTEL analysis can identify the political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors that may have an influence.
- Secondly, work should be carried out to understand the real interests, incentives and expectations that drive stakeholders, as these can be both drivers and barriers.

- Thirdly, empathy mapping should be used to understand the experiences, motivations, frustrations and needs of end-users.
- It is also useful to use tools such as Ishikaw diagrams to identify and visualise the possible causes of barriers and drivers, which helps to understand the interrelationships.
- Finally, an impact-probability matrix is proposed, which would classify barriers and drivers according to their potential impact on LL and the likelihood of their occurrence, thus helping to prioritise the most significant challenges and develop mitigation strategies.

Development of a high-level strategy.

It is important to generate a document containing the LL master plan based on what has been studied above, so this information can be provided as input of the macro level context affecting the future CBMs. This information is not covered, under the application of the guidelines to the LLs solutions in BWS, since the development of the strategic agendas for each of the LLs won't be published until the end of the project in **D1.4**.

3.3.2 Scoping LL circular solutions (Meso and Micro level)

During the initial stages of development of the LL (ex-ante in BWS) solutions planned to be tested are predefined.

In this section a scoping of these pre-defined solutions is carried out to define the system to be analysed, setting the boundaries, and defining the extension of the affected value chain.

The focus of these guidelines is on circular solutions, however also non-circular solutions should be considered when their development act as enablers for the development of the first. A brief description of the relationship between the circular and non-circular solutions should be provided, when required for providing a comprehensive understanding of the LLs actions.

In this context, the following actions are recommended during this phase:

Scoping the project solutions, site location, state of the art description.

A description of the circular solutions predefined and planned to be tested in the LL should be carried out, by referring to the affected segments of the value chain and associated BMs.

Circular solutions can modify or extend existing value chains, or they can create new value chains (when there is non-existing). Changes on these may involve the development of in new CBM in the environment defined by the LL. For this reason, it is necessary to analyse existing business models.

For example, a water utility with a core business model based on drinking water services, its value chain is segmented into collection, treatment, distribution and storage, and sanitation and purification. To implement business model innovation (BMI), it would be necessary to modify the processes of creation, distribution or capture of value in one or more of the segments of its value chain. Adaptations that modify the value chain's own activities, and transform it, affect the core business model, creating new business models. If, for example, during the wastewater treatment phase, before returning the water to the environment, a process of the treatment is transformed into a circular one by implementing circular strategies such as a reclaimed water treatment to enable reuse of water for other purposes (e.g., irrigation of green areas, industrial, agricultural; as opposed to returning it to the environment), the original value chain would be extended (i.e. an additional service would be added that changes

the way in which value is created, distributed and captured) through an increased recirculation process of water. The process of introducing a new service (i.e. reclaimed water), and the consequent need to adapt or transform the business model, is referred to CBMI and would result in the creation of a new CBM (associated with the core business model of drinking water service).

It is important to differentiate here between process innovation and BMI, as not all circular solutions lead to changes in the value chain as such, and therefore do not transform existing business models into CBM. For example, a process is implemented in a water utility which only aims at improving energy efficiency, without creating a new product or service, or causing a change in the logic of value creation in the value chain, should not be considered as a CBMI. Instead, this should be considered as a process innovation.

An analysis at the micro level examines the internal processes that are carried out by a particular organisation to ensure the operability of a segment of the value chain (e.g. in the case explained before, the analysis of the reused water production phase, and particular water treatment processes). The meso level analyses the value chain from a perspective that transcends the central organisation and includes the various actors of the value chain and their interrelationships.

In order to describe the system, a material flow analysis should be carried out to describe qualitatively and quantitatively the baseline scenario of the existent value chain and the level of circularity of their processes. In BWS, the analysis of the Baseline Scenarios of the value chains affected by the circular solutions has been carried out as part of the work in task **T4.2** in WP4. The information is collected and analysed in **D4.3**.

In addition to this material flow, resources, and capacities (e.g. infrastructure, supply chain, manpower, competences...) available to the driving organisation will also be described. This will allow defining a complete state of the art of the value chain, which can later be compared with scaled-up scenarios projecting the implementation of the circular solutions, thus transforming the value chain into a circular value chain.

These exercises will also allow the identification of further opportunities of improvements to the value chain processes.

Mapping the ecosystem: classification of stakeholders and role in the value chain.

The stakeholder mapping process implemented in the frame of the project, is based on the “Manual of stakeholder mapping and engagement” developed in **D5.1**. The stakeholder mapping of the LLs used in this document, has been performed as part of **T4.2** and is described on **D4.3**.

As a best practice in this phase, it is advisable to implement system thinking principles (refer to Figure 3) for the early design phases that provide a holistic view of the environment and allow the identification of all (direct and indirect) participants in the value chain. This is particularly important to consider all impacts resulting from the introduction of circular solutions. For this purpose, there are specific tools (e.g. Value Mapping tool developed by Bocken et al (2015), see Figure 4) that can assist the process of identifying missing, captured, and destroyed values by each of the different types of stakeholders.

During this design phase, dynamics are carried out to enhance the development of the value network, integrating all stakeholders, in order to gather as much information as possible, and without missing any sectors and potential collaborators out of the innovation process. This will create the foundation

for the long-term success of the LL and the sustainable development of CBMs out of the circular solutions proposed.

This phase is integrated within the "stakeholder engagement" activities of the project which have been carried out extensively in the context of the B-Water Smart through Community of Practice (CoPs), Focus Groups, interviews, etc.

Figure 3 Applying Systems Thinking principles for early-stage (from: Sustainable business model innovation: Design guidelines for integrating systems thinking principles in tools for early-stage sustainability assessment by Schlüter et al. 2023)

Figure 4 Value mapping tool for sustainable business thinking (from: Value mapping for sustainable business thinking by Bocken et al. 2015).

3.4 Ideation

The Ideation is a creative stage, where ideas are generated, a preliminary assessment to select the most prominent is carried out, and a concept is developed. This last will be assessed in depth during the next stage (Detail Design). This stage can be divided into three phases:

1. Idea generation.
2. Preliminary assessment.
3. Concept development.

As it was described before, during the planning stage of BWS project, circular solutions were predefined for the LLs. These solutions are generally identified and assessed ex-ante, by considering the problems and challenges affecting the LLs, and the aim to provide effective solutions that resolve the challenges, problems, and their needs. For this reason, the subsequent phases may be constrained based on the scope of the solutions and the potential of further ideation they can offer.

Therefore, this stage is particularly influenced by the initial planning stage, which can greatly impact the idea generation. A more specific predefined circular solution limits the generation of ideas during this stage but allows the development of greater detail during the detailed design stage. Conversely, a less specific solution fosters greater idea generation but poses challenges for detailed analysis and implementation.

Both contexts have their limitations and advantages, however, it is not the purpose of this deliverable to go into this detail.

Stakeholder engagement

It is important at this point to re-emphasise the need to involve all relevant stakeholders from the early design stage of the solutions (ideally, before the start of the project), to identify opportunities, gather feedback, understand their needs, and to consider these into the decision-making process. Also, it sets a strong foundation for establishing clear and transparent communication among all the participant in the ecosystem networks.

Even if the project focuses on pre-defined and very specific solutions, one of the most important objectives for establishing a sustainable LL and developing sustainable CBM out of these solutions is to create strong foundations. Thus, serving not only for developing the project's solutions, but also others that might arise in the future.

As it will see exposed in the next stages, the long-term viability of many circular solutions is dependent on strong networks of actors (e.g. industrial symbioses), to promote the recovery and reuse of materials.

Common mistakes during the ideation phase

- One of the most common mistakes is the failure to define objectives from the early stage, which can result in ideation without clear direction and focus.
- Failure to include a sufficient variety of perspectives and skills can limit creativity and lead to uninventive solutions.
- Failure to establish clear and open channels of communication is another common mistake, as poor communication can lead to misunderstandings, loss of valuable ideas and conflict.
- Focusing too much on technology rather than understanding real needs can result in ineffective solutions.
- Ignoring or underestimating resistance to change is also a major mistake, as lack of acceptance can hinder the successful implementation of new ideas for business models.
- Lack of flexibility to adapt to changes in the environment or project requirements is another mistake that can lead to solutions that are obsolete or unable to address emerging challenges.
- Focusing only on short-term solutions without considering long-term sustainability is a mistake that can result in non-scalable solutions.
- Inefficient resource management, lack of continuous evaluation of progress and lack of end-user involvement in the ideation process are also common mistakes that can negatively affect the quality and success of the project.

3.4.1 Ideas generation

During this phase the objective is to generate and collect ideas to implement the circular solutions pre-defined in the previous sections, so that they can be further assessed in the next phases. Ideas should be differentiated between those that are intended to be implemented within the scope of the project and those that have the potential to be developed in the long-term. In the BWS project, this task has been conducted as part of T4.2. The circular solutions or also referred as circularities to be developed in the project, as well as other circular opportunities identified in the LLs for the long-term, are presented on deliverable D4.3. These will be referred on the next chapter, during the application of the guidelines to the LLs.

It is relevant during this phase to carry out dynamics with the different stakeholder groups directly or indirectly affected by the circular solutions. The next have been carried out during BWS: Community of Practices (CoP), Focus Group sessions, workshops or training actions, and interviews.

The usual tools and techniques used for generating ideas, based on working groups, are Brainstorming, Mind Maps, SCAMPER, 6-3-5 Technique, Inverse SCAMPER, Storytelling Technique, Role Storming, Analogies Method, among others. These are easily applicable and are suited for work in multidisciplinary teams.

3.4.2 Preliminary Assessment

The preliminary assessment is key phase in the innovation process of CBMs, since it allows for the identification and selection of ideas that appear to be the most viable, feasible and aligned with the strategic direction of the project and the LLs. To carried out this assessment specific evaluation criteria are applied which may include aspects such as technical feasibility, market potential, resources required and alignment with the strategic objectives set. Common evaluation techniques such as SWOT, preliminary market studies, cost benefit analysis, life cycle analysis, and weighted prioritisation are used for this purpose.

The following is a generic description of the aspects to be considered during this assessment:

- **Validation of the Idea:** The aim is to confirm whether the business model idea, and the products and services offered, have the potential to solve a real problem or satisfy a market need. This involves market research, surveys, interviews with potential customers and trend analysis.
- **Market analysis:** The market is examined to understand demand, competition, and opportunities. It seeks to identify the market segment targeted by the business model and how it is positioned in relation to other existing products or services.
- **Financial Feasibility:** A preliminary analysis of the costs associated with the implementation and operation of the business model is carried out. This involves estimating initial and recurrent costs, as well as projected revenues to assess short- and long-term financial viability.
- **Technical Feasibility:** Involves the analysis of technical feasibility of the technologies that will be implemented, whether the technology is available, affordable and can be implemented effectively.
- **Risks and Challenges:** Potential obstacles, risks and challenges that could arise during the implementation of the business model are identified. This may include factors such as regulatory changes, technological challenges, barriers to market entry, among others.
- **Team and Resources:** Assess whether the right team is in place to carry out the idea and whether additional resources will be needed. This involves analysing the skills and capabilities of the founding team and determining whether it is necessary to seek collaborators, partners, or investors.

The main objective is to filter and prioritise the most promising ideas, discarding or putting on hold those that, in an initial analysis, do not demonstrate technical or commercial feasibility or are not aligned with the purpose of the project.

A feasibility document should emerge from this stage to assess the most relevant aspects of the idea to implement the circular solution and develop the CBM.

This stage is critical because it allows efforts and resources to be directed towards the ideas with the greatest potential for success, avoiding the investment of valuable resources in less promising

concepts. This ensures that the selected ideas advance to further development, testing and validation stages, maximising the chances of success of the innovation project.

It is important to consider that LLs, depending on the leadership i.e. the problem owners, will put more emphasis on different aspects of evaluation. Water companies, given their competencies, will tend to implement and evaluate innovative technologies, analyse their financial viability, and collaborate with industry to find commercial opportunities. On the other hand, those led by public authorities will prioritise the evaluation of enabling aspects, such as social inclusion and perception, and compliance with policy and regulations. They assess how solutions impact the community, ensure the participation of the different stakeholders and other sectors in the process, and in some cases prioritise social and environmental aspects over economic ones. However, these differences are general, and reality may vary, suggesting that a holistic approach, combining technical and enabling aspects, can be advantageous, regardless of leadership.

It is important to note that, at this stage, the initial assessment of the project's feasibility that should have been carried out during the selection of circular solutions in the early planning phases of the LL (LL), and as already mentioned, should be documented in the "Project Initiation Document" (PID), should serve as inputs for the development of the preliminary assessment.

3.4.3 Concept

The concept development phase involves designing a preliminary CBM by turning the initial idea into a more detailed and structured plan. During this phase, the conceptualisation of the proposal is deepened, and more tangible and specific elements are created. In points 1 to 4, a process of placing the business model in the specific context is carried out, while the following points are carried out to generate a status document of the CBM.

The following steps are recommended for the conceptualisation of the CBM:

- Step 1: Definition of the circular strategies and the operating cycle.
- Step 2: Definition of the BMI strategy.
- Step 3: Definition of the innovation path and the SCBM archetype.
- Step 4: Classification of CBMs.
- Step 5: Development a preliminary circular business model canvas.
- Step 6: Development of a SWOT analysis.
- Step 7: Definition of performance and outcome metrics.
- Step 8: Development of prototypes.

3.4.3.1 Step 1: Circular strategies and cycle of operation

Strategies are approaches adopted by organisations to achieve their objectives while guiding change and transition (Morseletto, 2020). In the context of the circular economy of water (CEW), strategies represent the main pathways toward a more circular use of water and serve as categories to which various CEW solutions and applications can be attributed. Figure 5, identify circular strategies (Morseletto et al., 2022) that can be implemented through circular solutions.

CEW strategies for implementing circular solutions should be identified at this step.

Figure 5 Strategies of CEW (from Circular Economy of Water: Definition, Strategies and Challenges. Circular Economy and Sustainability, 2(4), 1463-1477, by Morseletto, P., et al., 2022).

Identifying the cycles of operation in which the circular solutions interact will also help to establish a framework for the categorization of the CBMs. Two different cycles of operations can be differentiated: a biological cycle and a technical cycle.

The *biological cycle* encompasses natural processes found in ecosystems, involving living organisms and their interactions with the environment. This cycle emphasizes the regenerative capacity of the biosphere, including the growth, decay, and renewal of organic materials. Examples include anaerobically digesting organic matter to return to nature. The *technical cycle* is a human-designed system that focuses on the controlled and efficient use of resources within industrial and technological processes. It involves the extraction, production, use, and recovery of materials, often through manufacturing, recycling, and advanced technologies (EMF).

Notice that a circular solution can interact on both cycles of operation.

3.4.3.2 Step 2: Business model innovation strategy

In this step, the business model innovation strategy that the original business model will follow is defined (Geissdoerfer et al. 2020, see Figure 6). Starting business models can be either LBM, when their value chains are based on linear economy principles; CBMs when the value chains have already adopted circular strategies; or they may be non-existent.

The proposed categories for classifying innovation strategies are as follows:

- **CBM transformation** modifies an existing business model, whether it is conventional or circular.
- **CBM diversification** involves the development of a new business models within an existing organisation, without altering the current business model. It can become an integral part of the organisation or spin off as subsidiaries (includes joint ventures).
- **CBM acquisition** involves merger and acquisition of CBMs.

- **CBM circular start-up**, the creation of new business models takes place outside of an existing company.

Figure 6 Circular Business Model Innovation strategies (from Circular business models: A review by Geissdoerfer et al. 2020).

Defining the innovation strategy will condition the chosen innovation route. Thus, in a sequential decision-making process, the pros and cons of each possible action should be evaluated. For example, there may be the option of either transforming internal processes (CBM transformation) or acquiring another company or start-up to integrate it (CBM acquisition). If we start from scratch, the same analysis could be made: what is better to begin anew (Circular start-up)? or is it preferable to acquire and integrate an already operational unit (CBM acquisition)? Each strategy will condition the development of the CBM in a very decisive way, determining the subsequent development of the work.

3.4.3.3 Step 3: Business model innovation pathways and Sustainable Circular Business Model (SCBM) archetype

In this step, an innovation pathway for the development of the business model is proposed and a sustainable circular business model (SCBM) archetype (De Keyser & Mathijs, 2023) is defined based on the purpose behind the implementation of the circular solution.

The goal is to outline a generic and hierarchical innovation pathway of the business model based on a triple bottom approach (by following a sequential order of technological, social, and organizational innovation). Delimiting a roadmap and defining a SCBM archetype can help guiding the process of designing CBMs, especially in regulated, non-market or hybrid contexts, where these solutions may be purposefully driven by environmental and social benefits, instead of profit driven, and it is important to remain in alignment with the macro level aspects.

A guide to use this classification for the development of the roadmap is presented below:

- Firstly, the planet dimension is captured through the rationale guiding the implementation of a new technology: "*Maximize material and energy efficiency*", "*Create value from waste*" or "*Substitute with renewables and natural processes*".
- Define the driving social innovation, i.e. the main social intention behind the implementation of the new business model. This can be focused on: "*Deliver functionality rather than ownership*", "*Adopt a stewardship role*" and "*Encourage sufficiency*".
- Define the organisational innovation that the business model follows. Depending on the organisation's economic objectives, a choice will be made between: "*Repurpose for society or the environment*" or "*Develop scale-up solutions*". In the first case, the environmental and social aspects are prioritised over economic aspects, its aim is to develop a subsistence model. In the second case, the aim is to scale-up sustainable solutions while guaranteeing economic viability.
- The sequence of elements selected for each innovation define the pathway of the business model (see example and Figure 7) and the SCBM archetype. For each type of technological innovation ("*Maximize material...*") six different archetypes are possible: *Purposeful Sufficiency*, *Scaled-up Sufficiency*, *Purposeful Functionality*, *Scaled-up Functionality*, *Purposeful Stewardship* and *Scaled-up Stewardship*.

For example, consider a water company that intends to diversify its business model by applying a reclamation treatment to part of the effluent it produces for its reuse in agriculture or another sector, instead of discharging it back to the sea (baseline). To achieve this, the company requires a technological innovation for the treatment of wastewater and production of reclaimed water. This would not only help the company reduce its environmental impacts but also provide a sustainable source of water for other sectors. In the regional context in which the company is located, there is a need to reduce the consumption of water from natural sources due to frequent droughts. In this situation, the technological innovation is driven by a two-fold objective: "*Create value from waste*" and "*Substitute with renewables and natural processes*", since the circular solution is driven both by the need to adopt circular processes in the value chain and to reduce the hydric stress in the region. The social innovation is driven by "*Encourage sufficiency*", since you promote the end users (agriculture or industries according to use) to reduce the consumption of freshwater. Finally, if the organisation aims to scale-up the solution, to several of its WWTPs, and apply a business model based on a stable income, the organisational innovation would be driven by "*Develop scale-up solutions*". The defined innovations and resulting innovation pathway are shown in highlighted red in Figure 7 Figure 8. The resulting SCBM archetype would be identified as: *Scaled-up Sufficiency*.

Figure 7 Sustainable business model archetypes case example (adapted from: Bocken et al. 2014).

Figure 8 Sustainable business model innovation pathway case example (adapted from: A typology of sustainable circular business models with applications in the bioeconomy by De Keyser & Mathijs 2023)

Finally, Table 1 can be used by organizations to initially identify the main features that define the archetype and guide the preliminary design of the business model by answering the following questions: How value is created? Who do we create value for? What is our source of competence? How do we competitively position ourselves? How do we make money? What is the time, scope, and size ambitions?

In Step 5 of the Concept phase, the CBM canvas is presented, to dive in more detail into these questions and to guide the practitioner in characterizing the elements of the CBM so a more comprehensive view is provided.

Table 1 SCBMs general characteristics (from: A typology of sustainable circular business models with applications in the bioeconomy by De Keyser, E. & Mathijs, E. 2023).

	Purposeful sufficiency	Scaled-up sufficiency	Purposeful functionality	Scaled-up functionality	Purposeful stewardship	Scaled-up stewardship
<i>How do we create value?</i>	Primarily products	Primarily products	Primarily services	Primarily services	Mix of products and services	Mix of products and services
<i>Who do we create value for?</i>	Relational	Relational and transactional	Relational	Relational and transactional	Relational	Relational and transactional
<i>What is our source of competence?</i>	Production	Production Selling/marketing	Intellectual capability and technology	Intellectual capability and technology Selling/marketing	Networking/ resource leveraging Supply chain management	Networking/ resource leveraging Supply chain management Selling/marketing
<i>How do we competitively position ourselves?</i>	Intimate relationship Product quality Innovation	Product quality Innovation	Intimate relationship Service quality Innovation	Low cost and efficiency Service quality Innovation	Intimate relationship Operational excellence Innovation	Low cost and efficiency Operational excellence Innovation
<i>How do we make money?</i>	Fixed revenue source High operating leverage Low volumes	Fixed revenue source High operating leverage High volumes	Fixed revenue source High operating leverage Low volumes	Fixed revenue source High operating leverage High volumes	Mixed/flexible revenue sources Low operating leverage Low Volumes	Mixed/flexible revenue sources Low operating leverage High volumes
<i>What are our time, scope and size ambitions?</i>	Subsistence or income model	Income or growth model	Subsistence or income model	Income or growth model	Subsistence or income model	Income or growth model

SCBM archetypes should be defined by the primary reason driving the BMI. However, in some cases, there may be several equally important reasons leading to its innovation, which would result in Hybrid Models with combining SCBM’s archetype features.

3.4.3.4 Step 4: Circular business model classification

There are several approaches available for classifying or conceptualizing CBMs. Visual frameworks, known as *reference models* (e.g. Canvas), illustrate the components of a CBM, including revenue mechanisms and customer segments. *Requirements* offer general descriptions of the changes needed in existing business models to align them with circular principles. *Classifications* involve sorting potential structures or arrangements, outlining how a CBM should be structured, including typologies, taxonomies, or morphological characters. Reference models are tied by the static view of CBMI, for this reason they are commonly used to structure and represent business models. Classifications on the other side, are connected to the dynamic view, and help to identify how business models should be changed with circular economy principles (Wirtz et al., 2016).

A commonly used in the literature (OECD, 2019; Accenture, 2014; Lacy et al. 2015) classification, categorizes CBMs according to typologies and sub-types (Table 2) based on circular strategies (Resource Cycles by Bocken et al. 2016).

Table 2 Accepted CBMs types and subtypes (adapted from: OECD 2019 and Lacy et al. 2020).

Business Model	Key Characteristics	Resource Efficiency Driver	Business Models Subtypes	Examples
Circular supply	Provides fully renewable, recyclable, or bio-based resource inputs, replacing traditional single-lifecycle inputs in the supply chain.	Closing resource loops	Cradle to cradle. Biomimicry	Biogas production for self-consumption Water reuse for agriculture or industrial processes Stormwater/rain water harvesting
Sharing Platforms	The utilisation rates of products and assets are optimised through shared ownership, access, and usage typically enabled by digital technologies.	Narrow resource flows	Co-ownership Co-access	Not prevalent Collaborative Resource Recovery Platform

Business Model	Key Characteristics	Resource Efficiency Driver	Business Models Subtypes	Examples
Product as a service	Offer product access and retain ownership to internalise benefits of circular resource productivity.	Narrow resource flows	Product-oriented User-oriented Result-oriented	Water Treatment as a Service (WaaS) Water recycling and reuse services
Product use extension	Extend working lifecycle of products and components through design considerations, repairs, component reconditioning, upgrades, and resale on secondary markets.	Slowing material loops	Classic long life Direct reuse Repair Refurbishment Remanufacture	Not relevant water industry.
Resource recovery	Valorisation of the materials contained in waste streams. The value of embedded materials or energy from agricultural and industrial goods is captured through collection, aggregation, and processing at the end of a product's use through recycling, upcycling or downcycling.	Narrow resource flows	Recycling Upcycling Downcycling Industrial symbiosis	Production of reclaimed water from wastewater Nutrient recovery from wastewater Biogas production for export.

The most common typologies in the water sector are: **Circular inputs**, **Resource Recovery** and **Product as a service**. Similar to the SCBM archetypes presented on the previous Step 4, CBMs can also be combined to conform **Hybrid models**.

A particularly relevant subtype in the water industry is the **Industrial symbiosis** (under Resource Recovery typology) given its relevance in the context of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Resources and materials produced and recovered by plants, have applications as inputs in other industrial sectors. Creating an industrial network that promotes the reuse of these resources favours the creation of dependencies between sectors that can boost and guarantee the long-term sustainability of CBMs.

For this subtype, a further categorization is used in the literature (Fraccascia et al. 2019) to describe industrial symbiosis systems based on the need for coordination and centralisation. It distinguishes four taxonomies: Low coordination & low centralization, low coordination & high centralization, High coordination & low centralization, and High coordination & high centralization. A definition of their characteristics is referred in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Taxonomy dimensions of IS systems (from: Fraccascia et al. 2019).

3.4.3.5 Step 5: Circular business model canvas

In this step, the concept of the new CBM, based on the ideas generated and preliminarily assessed, is visually represented using a circular business model canvas (CBMC) tool. This allows a holistic representation of the model by describing its value chain and organizing its building blocks in three segments: Value proposition, Value creation and delivery and Value Capture.

The aim here is to collect all the information that has been gathered so far from the previous steps and stages, to describe the defining elements of the business models and the relationships between them.

Below presented are some guidelines for the development of the canvas (refer to Table 3):

1. Start by detailing the general aspects of the CBM that have been collected in **Steps 1-4** in the top section of the section (refer to Figure 10).

Circularity goal and scope definition	Sustainability mission and action
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted CE principle (Select one or more principle) -P1) Create value from waste, P2) Maximize energy and material efficiency, P3) Substitute with renewables and natural processes • CE strategies (Select one or more strategies) - R1 - Rethink, R2 – Avoid, R3 – Reduce, R4-Replace, R5 - Reuse, R6- Recycle, R7 - Cascading, R8 - Store, R9 - Recover • Operating cycle (Select business operation cycle) - Technical cycle, Biological cycle • Circular business model innovation strategy (Select innovation strategy) - CBM transformation, CBM diversification, Circular start-up, CBM acquisition • Sustainable circular innovation pathways (Select one or more) - Purposeful sufficiency, Scaled-up sufficiency, Purposeful functionality, Scaled-up functionality, Purposeful stewardship, Scale-up stewardship • Circular business model type (Select one or more of the targeted circular business model type) - Circular supplies, Sharing platform, Product as a service, Product lifespan extension, Resource recovery 	<p>Targeted sustainable development goal</p> <p>Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions Goal 17: Partnership for the goals</p>

Figure 10 CBM characterization location in the CBMC.

2. The "*need, problem or challenge*" will be defined first and then the elements that characterise the value proposition of the CBM: value proposition, customer segments, targeted solutions, customer relationships, burden, and benefits.
3. Describe the elements that characterise value creation and distribution: key partners, key resources, key activities, ecosystem activities, networks and organisations and channels.
4. Finally, the elements that define the value capture: costs structure (opex and capex) and revenue streams.
5. Guiding questions to help the practitioner define the canvas units are provided in the canvas template.

The expected social and environmental impacts will be indicated under the "burden and benefits" element.

This document is recommended to be carried out in focus group sessions, workshops, or other group dynamics with key partners, and then communicated to the relevant stakeholders for feedback and clarifying certain elements before proceeding to the next stages.

Table 3 Circular business model canvas (CBMC)

Circular Business Model Canvas		Living Lab	
		Value proposition	Value creation & delivery
Key Partners	Key Activities	Key Resources	Key Partners
<p>Describe the network of suppliers and partners and the types of collaboration that support the business model execution along the value chain.</p> <p>Guiding questions: Who are the key partners through the value chain (stakeholders, key alliances...) in the LL? Which key resources and key activities do the partners provide? How might we strengthen our partnerships with organizations across the value chain to benefit from circularity (flows of materials, information and capital) in the system?</p>	<p>Main actions that should be implemented and related to the business to operate successfully, to meet the value proposition, sustain the relationship to the target audiences, create revenue streams, etc.</p> <p>Guiding questions: What key activities are required? What activities might best help to achieve the value proposition? What are the key activities based on diversification and long-term goals? What might be the positive externalities of key activities? And how might we monitor and design out any negative externalities?</p>	<p>Most important assets needed to provide the product/service to the target audience defining the quality and nature of the product/service provided.</p> <p>Guiding questions: What are the most important assets which are required to make your business work?</p>	<p>Tangible and intangible activities. The goal of this element is to address the ecosystem dimension of the business model by including activities that are performed outside by the value network stakeholders and are essential for the success.</p> <p>Guiding questions: What kind of activities do partners ecosystem perform? What kind of resources are we acquiring from partners' ecosystem?</p>
Legend:		Value proposition	Value capture
Circularity goal and scope definition		Value Proposition	Ecosystem Activities
<p>Targeted sustainable development goal Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions, Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals</p>	<p>The core component of a business model is characterized by a combination of products and services that create value for a specific type of customer. The objective is to communicate clearly and persuasively how a company's products or services address the problems or meet the specific needs of its customers in a unique and superior way compared to the competition.</p> <p>Guiding questions: What is the added value the LL provides for the target audience? For clients, for stakeholders, for community, for employees, for environment (if applicable). Which one of your target audience's problems are you helping to solve? What bundles of products and services are you offering to each customer segment? Is there anything associated with our product/service that has potential value to others?</p>	<p>The Living Lab reaches out and communicates with the target audiences.</p> <p>Guiding questions: Which channels are you using to reach the clients? Think about channels per product/service (water, energy, sludge etc) Which ones work best? Which ones are most cost-efficient? How are you integrating them with customer routines? How might you redesign your relationship with other supply chain?</p>	<p>Value capture is the process of generating revenue from the value proposition. It involves understanding what customers are looking for and tailoring the offerings.</p> <p>Guiding questions: How can products or services be customized for each segment? Adapting the offering to meet the specific needs of each customer group. What type of solutions do we want to provide by our value proposition to customers/each segment of customers?</p>
Sustainability mission and action		Customer Segments	Customer Relationships
<p>Targeted sustainable development goal Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions, Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals</p>	<p>These are all the people, organisations, associations etc. for which circularity will be creating value. This will include the final users and the paying water reuse, nutrient, energy, sludge, byproducts... users whether public or private etc.</p> <p>Guiding questions: For whom are you creating value? Define all the potential customers for water reuse, nutrients, energy, byproducts, etc. Of these, who are our most important customers? Who else might benefit from or will be affected by your material(s)/product/service?</p>	<p>This element focuses on the types of relationships a company establishes with its various customer segments.</p> <p>Guiding questions: How do you interact with the target audience? Define the typology of customer relationships you adopt. Personal Assistance, Dedicated Service, Automated Services, Peer-to-peer Communities, Co-creation with customers, Subscription Services or Transactional Relationships.</p>	<p>Describe the environmental and social positive and negative impacts.</p> <p>Guiding questions: What kind of benefits will our products/service create on customers, society and environment? What kind of burden will our products/service create on customers society and environment?</p>
Sustainability mission and action		Customer Segments	Revenue Streams
<p>Targeted sustainable development goal Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions, Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals</p>	<p>These are all the people, organisations, associations etc. for which circularity will be creating value. This will include the final users and the paying water reuse, nutrient, energy, sludge, byproducts... users whether public or private etc.</p> <p>Guiding questions: For whom are you creating value? Define all the potential customers for water reuse, nutrients, energy, byproducts, etc. Of these, who are our most important customers? Who else might benefit from or will be affected by your material(s)/product/service?</p>	<p>Represents the revenue models, and description of revenue streams, the Living Lab sets out for capturing value from the value propositions offered to the customer segments.</p> <p>Guiding questions: What value are customers really willing to pay for water reuse and associated products (energy, nutrients etc)? How much does each revenue stream contribute to overall revenues? What is your pricing mechanism? How might you diversify opportunities to increase resilience, growth, and innovation? How might the business model help create other types of value? Human, social, or natural capital? How might new services increase revenue from existing products, assets or your delivery systems?</p>	<p>Represents the revenue models, and description of revenue streams, the Living Lab sets out for capturing value from the value propositions offered to the customer segments.</p> <p>Guiding questions: What value are customers really willing to pay for water reuse and associated products (energy, nutrients etc)? How much does each revenue stream contribute to overall revenues? What is your pricing mechanism? How might you diversify opportunities to increase resilience, growth, and innovation? How might the business model help create other types of value? Human, social, or natural capital? How might new services increase revenue from existing products, assets or your delivery systems?</p>
Sustainability mission and action		Customer Segments	Revenue Streams
<p>Targeted sustainable development goal Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions, Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals</p>	<p>These are all the people, organisations, associations etc. for which circularity will be creating value. This will include the final users and the paying water reuse, nutrient, energy, sludge, byproducts... users whether public or private etc.</p> <p>Guiding questions: For whom are you creating value? Define all the potential customers for water reuse, nutrients, energy, byproducts, etc. Of these, who are our most important customers? Who else might benefit from or will be affected by your material(s)/product/service?</p>	<p>Represents the revenue models, and description of revenue streams, the Living Lab sets out for capturing value from the value propositions offered to the customer segments.</p> <p>Guiding questions: What value are customers really willing to pay for water reuse and associated products (energy, nutrients etc)? How much does each revenue stream contribute to overall revenues? What is your pricing mechanism? How might you diversify opportunities to increase resilience, growth, and innovation? How might the business model help create other types of value? Human, social, or natural capital? How might new services increase revenue from existing products, assets or your delivery systems?</p>	<p>Represents the revenue models, and description of revenue streams, the Living Lab sets out for capturing value from the value propositions offered to the customer segments.</p> <p>Guiding questions: What value are customers really willing to pay for water reuse and associated products (energy, nutrients etc)? How much does each revenue stream contribute to overall revenues? What is your pricing mechanism? How might you diversify opportunities to increase resilience, growth, and innovation? How might the business model help create other types of value? Human, social, or natural capital? How might new services increase revenue from existing products, assets or your delivery systems?</p>

3.4.3.6 Step 6: SWOT analysis

Conduct a SWOT analysis of the CBM (refer to Figure 11). Unlike analysis that might be performed in the Framing and Scoping stages, to identify strengths and weaknesses at a macro level for the LLs, this analysis should aim to be more specific to the CBMs under study, therefore considering a narrower scope. The weaknesses and threats identification should be mitigated, either by iterating the innovation process (back to previous sections) or during the next detailed design stage.

SWOT ANALYSIS	
INTERNAL FACTORS	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
Characteristics of the business or project that give it an advantage over others Examples: Developed technology, lower environmental impact, usable byproduct, etc.	Characteristics that place the business or project at a disadvantage relative to others Examples: High investment, unprofitable without feed-in tariffs, lack of knowledge and experience, high maintenance costs, etc.
EXTERNAL FACTORS	
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
Elements in the environment that the business or project could exploit to its advantage (new markets, solutions...) Examples: possibility of use of existing infrastructure, broad range of applications, raising environmental awareness, environmental legislation of EU, etc.	External factors that are potential threats for your Living Lab Examples: Legal restrictions, price volatility, etc

Figure 11 SWOT Analysis for circular business model.

3.4.3.7 Step 7: Define performance and outcome metrics.

To evaluate the potential outcomes derived from the implementation of a proposed new CBM, it is necessary to define performance and outcome metrics, which quantify the economic, social, and environmental impacts of the circular solution under study. These will be used to guide the design of the experimentation, as well as to develop detailed analyses (e.g. comparative analysis between different solution scenarios) that allow to evaluate the concept developed in this phase, and subsequently proceed to the detailed design stage.

In **WP6** in deliverable **D6.3** a water-smartness assessment framework is presented to assist the selection of metrics.

As for the specific metrics to be used for the circular solutions, these should be selected based on the consideration of all the relevant stakeholders and decision-makers at the LLs, according to their preferences and requirements.

Common mistakes during this stage:

- Exclusive focus on financial metrics.
- Lack of specific metrics for circularity.
- Ignoring stakeholder participation.
- Lack of adaptability of metrics to specific contexts.
- Failure to assess impact throughout the life cycle.

3.4.3.8 Step 8: Prototyping and Next steps

Since the integration of technology is indispensable for the innovation of CBM, it is convenient during this stage to build the hypotheses and scenarios, which are intended to be tested in the next stage

(laboratory experiments and/or pilots). One of the goals in this preparation step (before starting the experimentation phase) is to obtain feedback from potential users, the customers or end-users, and the stakeholders participating in the solution to understand their preferences, needs, and pain points, in order to consider them in the experimentation phase.

During this stage, some specific forms of prototyping are: Virtual prototyping (e.g. simulation software and process flow diagrams), modelling and prototyping regulatory compliance (e.g. permitting simulations) and data analysis and prediction (e.g. data analytics). Benchmarking studies are also desirable to compare the proposed solution with other options available in the industry.

Common mistakes at this stage:

- Failed to integrate important stakeholders into the process.
- Too much effort/prototypes become too big.

3.5 Detail Design

3.5.1 Experimentation

In contrast to the prototyping phase, the experimentation stage involves more thorough and detailed testing in controlled environments. During this phase, the main focus is on testing and validating the key concepts defining the CBM, particularly products and services, by considering critical variables in conditions closer to reality. Smaller and agile tests are conducted to assess the overall acceptance and feasibility of the model, allowing significant flexibility to make iterative adjustments based on test results and user feedback. The ultimate goal is to learn and adapt the model before committing to a larger scale implementation.

This phase is characterised by the following activities:

1. Identification of key variables.
2. Rapid design and execution of experiments.
3. Analysis of results and lessons learned.

Designing an experiment during the BMI process is essential to validate hypotheses, learn effectively and make informed decisions.

Within the design of the experiment, it is important to consider key information to analyse the CBM, as we want to prove that the value proposition, we are making is viable, considering the information defined in previous phases, such as the following:

- Clear definition of the objective: Clearly state the objectives of the experimentation, which are intended to be achieved or validated. Define the objectives in a specific, measurable, and achievable way.
- The identification of hypotheses (Step 8): These hypotheses must be aligned with the project objectives and be the foundational basis for testing.
- The customisation of the experiments to the targeted solutions, previously agreed with the end-users and already identified in the preliminary CBMC (Step 5).
- The selection of key variables and indicators: the variables and indicators predefined in the concept phase will be used to measure the success of the experiment (Step 7).

Common mistakes during this phase:

- No experiments
- Methodological issues
- Too much effort

In the BWS, the implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of the experiments is carried out in **WP2 (D2.17, D2.14 and D2.15)**.

3.5.2 Prioritization of circular business models

In a LL where various circular solutions are being tested and different concepts and CBMs are being developed, the phase of prioritising CBMs is a key strategic step. This phase helps to focus resources and efforts on the CBMs that show the greatest potential for success and sustainability. After initial experimentation, the results should be analysed to evaluate:

- Operational feasibility and environmental and social impacts.
- Analyse the costs, profitability, and sustainability of each CBM.
- Ability to scale and expand in a sustainable way, and alignment with Living Lab's objectives and values.
- External factors, such as market trends and regulatory changes, to anticipate long-term impact.

It is essential that feedback from LL partners and other key stakeholders is incorporated into the prioritisation process.

As indicated in **Step 7** of the Ideation Phase, the Assessment Framework (AF) is a tool elaborated with the objective of assisting decision-makers in the prioritisation of circular solutions according to a set of predefined objectives, criteria, and metrics.

There are several prioritisation tools, based on multi-criteria analysis, which facilitate the scoring and ranking of CBMs based on predefined criteria. One of these is the strategic planning decision framework developed by Puglieri, F. N. et al. (2022), which prioritises CBMs (refer to Figure 12) based on the following parameters: ease of implementation, economic viability, social and environmental benefits, according to the competitive strategies adopted.

Throughout the guidelines, analytical controls for the innovation process have been carried out at the different stages. Firstly, a control during the planning stage of the LL (Framing and Scoping stage) using feasibility studies is carried out for selecting the circular solutions to be studied in the project. Secondly, a control is required to select the most viable ideas (Preliminary Assessment) to implement the predefined circular solutions. In this phase another should be carried out for the prioritisation of CBMs and, lastly, during the detail design phase (next), which will be the most in-depth analysis. These are conditioned by the information available and the specific requirements at each of the stages, in such a way that the information used for the selection of ideas will not have the same quality and depth than those carried out once the experimentation phase is over.

Figure 12 Strategic planning oriented to CBMs (source: Puglieri, F. N. et al. 2022)

3.5.3 Detail Design

Using the information and learning obtained after the experimentation phase, in the case there is only one CBM under study, or after the prioritisation phase in case several CBMs are considered, a more detailed design is required to cover all operational, technological, and strategic aspects of the CBM.

In this phase, the following tasks should be carried out to develop an Implementation Strategy:

- **Cost and Profitability Analysis:** At this point, an in-depth analysis of the costs associated with the implementation and operation of the CBM should be carried out and compared with the socio-environmental and economic benefits. A profitability analysis should be also performed to show the economic risks associated to the implementation of the CBM.
- **Analysis of financial mechanisms:** Based on the evaluation of financial resources necessary for the development and implementation of the CBM, potential financial resources are identified and evaluated. Then, various funding sources are explored, including equity, grants loans, among others. Each option is carefully analysed for costs, repayment terms, and long-term financial impacts. The goal is to ensure both the initial launch and long-term sustainability of the CBM through realistic financial projections and efficient resource management strategies. In the BWS, this task will be carried out through **T4.4** and presented in **D4.5**.
- **Environmental and social impact analysis:** Assess the environmental and social impact of the CBM at all stages of the life cycle. Consider how the model contributes to the objectives of the LL. If the prioritisation phase has been carried out, this would not be necessary unless a specific aspect is to be studied in greater detail.

- **Designing the operational processes:** identifying process analysis, optimisation, workflow and coordination, elaboration of process documentation, resource management, staff training, among other activities.
- **Iterate the CBM:** refine, readapt (i.e. CBMC) and perform an in-depth analysis of all the elements of the CBM and the interactions between them.
- **Measuring results:** Define key metrics to measure the performance of the CBM after implementation. Establish monitoring systems to collect relevant data and evaluate success and define frequency of review of the CBM.
- **Resilience and contingency:** identify risks and develop contingency plans for the implementation of the CBM.
- **Change management:** developing strategies to manage organisational change that may arise from the implementation of the CBM.
- **Regulatory compliance:** ensuring that the CBM complies with all regulatory requirements, and that procedures for obtaining permits and licences are clearly defined.

Depending on the circular solutions and the limitations of the regulatory framework in which they are framed, it will be more or less necessary to adapt regulatory policies to encourage the development of CBMs. As seen above, depending on the type of LL, i.e. whether they are run by public bodies or by water companies, the circular solutions defined will be more or less oriented towards overcoming regulatory and social barriers, i.e. towards enabling the contexts in which CBMs operate. In environments driven by municipalities, it is very likely that the circular solutions and CBMs that are developed will have a preponderance to promote changes in regulatory and social policies, given that the implementation contexts may be more restrictive, and their competences and capacities are aligned with the resolution of these problems.

During the development of the BWS project, WP5 aims, among others, to analyse the drivers and barriers for the implementation of water-smart solutions, including the social acceptance of new water management strategies, social practices towards water consumption, and obstacles or enabling conditions related to governance arrangements, policy, and regulatory frameworks. Some of this work, such as the review of regulatory policies affecting the circular solutions proposed in the LLs and their adaptation, is being carried out in parallel with the work in this document. In the Framing phase, reference was made to document D5.5 for more information on the analysis of barriers and drivers and the development of new governance models. Other documents in WP5, will present the regulatory policies affecting circular solutions.

Common mistakes during this phase:

- Unsuitable level of detail of analysis.
- Missing information from previous steps.
- Insufficient documentation.

3.5.4 Piloting

The pilot phase involves the controlled and scaled-up implementation of a CBM after the prototyping, experimentation, and detailed design phases. During this stage, implementation is carried out in a more realistic, larger-scale environment to validate both the key concepts and the operational feasibility of the model. The results obtained in the pilot phase are used to make final adjustments and refinements before implementation. This phase serves as a crucial intermediate step between

experimentation and full implementation, allowing for a more comprehensive and controlled evaluation of the CBM prior to full deployment.

The following aspects should be considered for the effective implementation of the pilot phase:

- **Set clear objectives:** Clearly define the objectives to be achieved by the pilot and establish key performance indicators (KPIs) to evaluate the success of the pilot.
- **Selection of a representative user group:** Identify and select a group of end-users that is representative of the target audience and ensure that the pilot group provides valuable information on their perception and feasibility of the CBM.
- **Define the scope of the pilot:** Limit the scope of the pilot to keep it controlled and manageable, and clearly specify which aspects of the model will be tested during the pilot and which will not.
- **Develop protocols and procedures:** Create detailed protocols and procedures for the implementation of the pilot and specify roles and responsibilities of participants in the pilot.
- **Prepare necessary resources:** Ensure that the necessary resources are in place to carry out the pilot effectively, including personnel, technology, materials, and any other essential elements.
- **Clear communication with participants:** Establish clear communication with pilot participants, and provide information on the purpose, duration, and benefits of the pilot.
- **Gradual implementation:** Launch the pilot gradually, ensuring that all systems are functioning properly, and closely monitor implementation to address any problems in a timely manner.
- **Data collection and feedback:** Implement systems to collect relevant data during the pilot and obtain active feedback from participants to understand their experiences and perceptions.
- **Results analysis:** Analyse the results of the pilot against the established objectives and KPIs and evaluate the effectiveness of the CBM and the market response (if applicable).
- **Adjustments and improvements:** Use the results of the pilot to make final adjustments and improvements to the model, ensuring that any issues identified are addressed before full implementation. Revise the CBMC if necessary.
- **Document lessons learned:** Document lessons learned during the pilot to inform future iterations and developments, capturing positive experiences and areas requiring further attention.
- **Preparing for full implementation:** Use insights from the pilot to prepare for full implementation of the business model, establishing a clear plan for full roll-out and incorporating learnings from the pilot.

While the Pilot is considered a very important phase to validate and fine-tune solutions before full-scale implementation, it is understood that each LL has its own characteristics and that there are circumstances where implementation may not be necessary or feasible, and strategic decisions can be made to move directly to implementation or to look for more suitable alternatives.

If it is not necessary, the report should indicate the reasons why the pilot is not considered necessary, such as the direct scalability of the pilot, or that the experimentation has provided sufficient data, or that the risks identified are easily controllable, etc.

On the other hand, when a pilot is considered necessary, but not feasible due to financial, logistical, or other constraints, it is important to carefully evaluate each alternative and its potential impact on the validation and viability of the CBM. It could be possible to generate an extended experimentation stage, or other solutions such as virtual models or simulations, or to work in incremental phases. Again, it is

important to detail the problems that prevent the development of the pilot with a study of the impact it may have on the implementation stage. This will allow the detection of critical or sensitive points that may help minimizing the impacts, thus limiting the effect of not piloting the CBM.

Common mistakes during this phase:

- No pilots.
- Unrealistic setting.
- Too much effort.

3.5.5 Connection of the Previous Phases with the Detailed Design

The results and analysis obtained in the phases prior to the detailed design—such as Framing, Scoping, and Ideation—are essential for guiding and supporting the detailed design of Circular Business Models (CBMs). Each of these phases provides specific information that translates into key decisions during the design process.

During the Framing phase, the macro context in which the Living Labs (LLs) operate is identified, including challenges such as water resource scarcity and regulatory barriers. This information will guide the detailed design by defining the specific objectives of the CBM, such as the need to incorporate strategies to reduce dependence on natural resources and overcome regulatory obstacles. In the design phase, this understanding of the macro context will be crucial to developing a strategy that not only meets environmental and social objectives but also addresses the regulatory challenges identified during Framing.

In the Scoping phase, an in-depth analysis of the actors involved and the value chains affected by circular solutions is carried out. For example, if during this phase the stakeholders are mapped, and a lack of infrastructure for water reuse is identified, this information will be used in the detailed design to define the necessary partnerships with actors who can provide resources and capabilities. Furthermore, the analysis of material and resource flows during the Scoping phase helps identify which specific processes need to be optimized or transformed, guiding the selection of technologies and practices during the detailed design.

In the Ideation phase, ideas for implementing circular solutions are generated and evaluated, providing a foundation for the testing and experimentation needed in the detailed design. For example, if several viable ideas for resource recovery are identified during the Ideation phase, the results of this evaluation will inform which prototypes and pilots will be developed in the design phase. Additionally, the performance metrics and indicators defined during this phase will allow the detailed design to align with the previously established sustainability and efficiency objectives.

Together, these previous phases directly feed into the detailed design phase by providing critical information for decision-making. The detailed design will be based on the challenges identified in the Framing, the characterization of stakeholders and resources from Scoping, and the strategies and metrics defined during Ideation. This ensures that the detailed design is a logical and well-founded extension of the entire previous process, making certain that the proposed solutions are not only innovative but also practical and aligned with the operating environment of the LLs

3.6 Implementation

The implementation phase in the development of a CBM is characterised by the practical execution of all strategies and plans designed during the previous phase. This stage involves putting all elements of the model into action to carry out the business operations in a comprehensive manner. During implementation, the strategies and tactics outlined during the design and the planning for implementation phases (Detail Design stage) are executed, mobilising all necessary resources including personnel, technology, infrastructure, and capital. The designed operational processes are implemented, personnel are managed (hiring, training, roles, and responsibilities), internal organisation is established, business relationships are developed (establishment and/or strengthening of relationships between suppliers, partners and customers, negotiation of contract agreements and collaborations) and products or services are officially launched. The phase also involves continuous monitoring, proactive adjustments, regulatory compliance, risk management and a continuous improvement mindset based on constant feedback from customers and stakeholders. It is a critical stage that requires careful management and a flexible approach to adapt to market dynamics and ensure the long-term success of the business model.

Common mistakes during this phase:

- Insufficient information on errors
- Lack of funding mechanisms
- Inadequate timeframe/expectations
- Communication problems

Further information on the execution of this phase will be presented as part of the work on **WP1** and **WP7** on documents **D1.4** and **D7.8**.

3.7 Checklist

1. Framing and Scoping Stage:

a. Framing LL (Macro level):

- Defined LL challenges
- Identified LL problem-owner.
- Identified LL partners, roles, and competences.
- Identified key dependencies, risks, and opportunities.
- Identified macro level Barriers & Drivers.
- Document/Report: [Living Lab Macro Context](#)

b. Scoping LL's circular solutions (Meso and Micro level):

- Identified predefined solutions to be tested in LL (Ex ante)
- Briefly described the relationship between selected circular and non-circular solutions.
- Scoping the circular solutions and described site locations.
- Identified affected value chains and analysed the state of the art of the system.
- Mapped the ecosystem: identified and engaged with key stakeholders.
- Evaluated stakeholders' captured value.
- Considered additional necessary elements.
- Evaluation of Planning Phase: [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#).
- Document/Report: [Framing and Scoping](#).

2. Ideation Stage:

a. Idea generation:

- Gathered a list of ideas by brainstorming or using other tools to implement circular solutions.
- Engaged stakeholders in the ideation process.
- Selected and prioritized ideas to develop the circular solutions.
- Evaluation of Idea Phase: [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#).
- Document/Report: [Ideas generated and stakeholder engagement activities](#).

b. Preliminary Assessment:

- Gathered initial feasibility studies used for defining circular solutions (Ex ante, 1a).
- Conducted a comprehensive preliminary assessment of the prioritized ideas from 2a.
- Evaluation of Preliminary Assessment Phase: [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#).
- [Document/Report: Preliminary assessment findings and viability Analysis.](#)

c. Concept:

- Described the CBM strategies, cycles, innovation strategy, pathway and SCBM archetype.
- Classified CBMs in type and subtype.
- Completed the CBM Canvas for the circular solutions.
- Conducted a SWOT analysis of the CBM.
- Defined CBM performance and outcome metrics.
- Developed prototypes, data analysis and benchmarking studies to test the CBM concept.
- Evaluation of Concept Phase: [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#).
- [Document/Report: Circular Business Model Concept and SWOT Analysis](#)

3. Detail Design Stage:**a. Experimentation:**

- Designed the experimentation phase.
- Ran experiments.
- Evaluation of Experimentation Phase: [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#).
- [Meeting Minutes/Reports: Experimentation results.](#)

b. Prioritization CBM:

- Prioritized CBMs following a comprehensive analysis.
- Evaluation of Prioritization Phase: [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#).
- [Reports/Documentation: Priorization Documentation](#)

c. Detail Design:

- Completed a cost and profitability analysis.

- Completed environmental and social impact analysis.
- Designed the operational processes.
- Completed a detailed design of all the CBM elements and their relationship.
- Revised the CBMC.
- Defined metrics to measure performance after implementation; developed a risk and contingency plans; and developed strategies to change management.
- Ensured regulatory compliance of CBM and defined procedures for obtaining permits and licenses.
- Evaluation of Detail Design Phase: [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#).
- [Reports/Documentation: Detailed Design Documentation](#)

d. Pilot:

- Designed the pilot phase.
- Conducted the pilot phase.
- Analysed the results of the pilot.
- Fine-tuned CBMC following results of the pilot phase (if required).
- Evaluation of Pilot Phase: [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#) [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#).
- [Pilot Report: Results and Lessons Learned](#)

4. Implementation:

- Implementation of the plans developed in the Detail Design (**3c**).
- Evaluation of Implementation Phase: [\[Insert Evaluation Here\]](#).
- [Implementation Documentation: Implementation Plan and Execution Report](#)

4 Guidelines application to LL's circular solutions

4.1 Methodology

In the previous section, guidelines were presented to describe the CBMI for the creation, transformation, or diversification of CBM in the context of a LL. During this section, the guidelines will be applied to analyse business models in the LLs of the BWS project and develop CBM from the circular solutions proposed.

This section is structured following the same order as presented in Section 3. The information collected in each of the LL has been obtained from the following sources:

1. Other project documents (deliverables from other WPs, project presentations, CoPs, etc.).
2. Semi-structured interviews to LL problem-owners and mentors.
3. Internal meetings and data requested to the LLs during the BWS.
4. Corporate documents and information gather from web portals of the organisations integrating the LLs.

The information contained on the following sections have been revised by the LL partners of the project.

Notice that the development of the concept of the CBMs is only preliminary. The application of these guidelines is limited to the actual progress in the innovation process of the CBMs at each of the LLs.

4.2 Alicante

4.2.1 Framing and scoping of the circular solutions in the Living Lab

Framing LL macro level context:

LL challenges:

Currently, the Alicante region faces a number of challenges related to water resources. Water scarcity continues to be a prominent problem, with recurrent periods of drought affecting the availability of water resources. In addition to this scarcity and the overexploitation of aquifers, there are problems linked to the increase in water demand due to pressure from tourism and the agricultural sector. In addition, there are problems of high-water salinity that make costly desalination processes necessary. Due to these factors, there is a pressing need to improve the efficiency processes of water infrastructures, including wastewater treatment plants, increasing wastewater reuse among others, so that the needs of the population can be met and a sustainable balance in water use can be maintained.

Another challenge related to wastewater treatment is the recovery of nutrients and materials, which can improve plant efficiency through the generation of energy or resources that have a marketable or reusable potential for the plants' own internal processes.

At the municipal and regional level, to enable the use of reclaimed water, the distribution and maintenance network must be improved to ensure a resilient infrastructure adapted to different uses.

LL problem owner:

The LL problem owner is Aguas Municipalizadas de Alicante (AMA), a water company that is in charge of the integral management of the water cycle in several municipalities in the Alicante region. It is a mixed (public-private) company, 50% owned by the Alicante City Council, owner of the service, and 50% by Hidraqua, Gestión Integral de Aguas de Levante S. A.

Figure 13 Services managed by AMA in the Alicante region.

Below are represented some significant data on the services offered by the company:

DRINKING WATER NETWORK	
Municipalities supplied	6
Total population served in management	494,171
Floating population served in management	670,574
Clients served in management	302,188
km of network	2,243

SANITATION NETWORK	
Municipalities supplied	3
Population served	371,646
km of network	806

DEPURATION	
Hm3 debugged	29.93
reused hm3	10.15
% reuse	3.4%

Figure 14 AMA significant data (from: <https://www.aguasdealicante.es>)

LL vision:

The LL Alicante vision is to become more water smart through converting wastewater treatment plants into biofactories, boosting water reuse through regenerated water and obtaining energy and resource recovery from wastewater treatment. The ambition is to impact at a regional level.

LL objectives:

The strategic objectives for the LLs were developed by the LL in Task 1.4 and with the input of the CoPs, as part of the project work carried out in WP1. A final strategic agenda will be presented on D1.4 - Final strategic agenda and implementation plan for each LL, with the agreed LL vision and objectives.

LL partners:

Aguas Municipales de Alicante (AMA)- LL problem-owners (water utility): manages the urban water cycle in the city of Alicante (Spain) and surrounding municipalities. Is a mixed capital company (municipal/private). In the project AMA offers a unique scenario to test solutions based on the coordinated management of the sewage network, the wastewater treatment plant, and the reused water supply infrastructure; it is in charge of the three activities.

CETAQUA- LL mentor (R&D Partner) is a research and technology transfer center based in Barcelona, specializing in water management and technology innovation. It was created by a collaboration between AGBAR (a leading water services company) and the Foundation Centre for Technological Research of the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (CERTEC). Cetaqua focuses on developing innovative solutions for the sustainable use and management of water resources. In the project it is the LL mentor

Turbulent - Partner (Technology provider): is a for profit company dedicated to the development of its patented micro hydropower plant. Turbulent role in the consortium is to contribute to a wastewater treatment plant case study in Alicante.

EURECAT – Partner (R&D Partner) is a technology center specialized in applied research and technology transfer, providing innovative solutions and expertise to companies in various industries. In the project they focus in complementing the activities related to ammonia recovery in Alicante study case.

Key dependencies, risks, and opportunities:

The dependencies, risks and opportunities for the Alicante LL are those typical of a water company. Considering the regional context of the Alicante LL, the creation of value around water is a fundamental pillar. In order to guarantee water to all users, the circularity of the processes has to be improved by maximising the efficiency of energy and material use in the system (*narrowing loops*), substituting fresh water with reused water (alternative sourcing) and creating value from the waste generated from the wastewater treatment (*closing loops*). Circularity in the processes is promoted through the introduction of innovative technologies, by ensuring the safeguarding of ecosystems and their service to society (i.e., waste does not go to landfill, environmental impact is reduced by reintroducing it into the life cycle) and access to water for all users (i.e., increasing water reuse).

- Freshwater resources:
 - Risks: dependency on non-local water resources (Taibilla River system and Tagus water transfer), competence between urban, agricultural, and industrial uses, groundwater overexploitation
 - Opportunities: Increase of already existing water reuse scheme for the replacement of conventional resources, application to new users (industry), boosting water efficiency
- Climate change:
 - Risks: Increase of temperature beyond the limits of well-being, especially at nights (tropical and even “equatorial” nights), impact on citizen’s health. Irregular rain patterns with reduced average but more frequent extreme events (torrential rains, floods)
 - Opportunities: Key role of urban water reuse in keeping/increasing the ratio of urban green areas in order to mitigate the *heat island* effect. Application of Nature Based Solutions (SUDs) for better urban resilience against floods (while simultaneously creating new green areas).

- Reused water:
 - Risks: decoupling of production and seasonal demand, especially in agriculture uses. High salinity/conductivity of reclaimed water.
 - Opportunities: Design and implementation of new transport and storage infrastructures (reservoirs) Identification and removal/mitigation of the causes of wastewater salinity: infiltration of saline groundwater into the sewerage, industrial discharges. Efficient desalination processes for reclaimed wastewater.
- Energy:
 - Risks: energy costs rise, affecting all the phases of the urban water cycle: groundwater abstraction from deep aquifers, drinking water and wastewater pumping, desalination. Wastewater treatment, in particular, is an energy demanding process (aeration, sludge drying...) The carbon footprint associated with energy consumption is an additional concern.
 - Opportunities: Optimization of processes (e.g. wastewater aeration) for improved energy efficiency. Use of renewable energies (e.g. solar) Generation of energy: micro and pico turbines in networks and treatment plants; digestion and co-digestion of wastewater sludge to generate biogas. Co-digestion offers the added benefit of the valorisation of solid waste.
- Regulatory framework:
 - Risks: regulatory barriers for water reuse and for the valorisation of wastewater sludge, raising requirement levels.
 - Opportunities: governance chances aimed at improved coordination between involved administrations; flexible and more agile processes for reused water concessions. Implementation of new monitoring and treatment solutions for priority and emerging contaminants in reused water and sludge.
- Treated and untreated wastewater discharges to the receiving bodies:
 - Risks: environmental impact of the discharges of treated wastewater and desalination brines in dry weather; combined sewer overflows due to heavy rains or system malfunction.
 - Opportunities: wastewater reclamation boost aimed at 100% reuse → 0% discharge. Nutrient recovery technologies in wastewater treatment reducing their discharge to the receiving bodies. Brine valorisation technologies for electrochlorination of reused water. CSO monitoring and mitigation technologies: nature-based solutions (SUDs) reducing the volume of rainwater entering the sewer network.

Barriers and Drivers (Macro level):

- Internal barriers:
 - Financial barriers:
 - Investment requirements: the budget for some of the required actions (e.g. reused water network and reservoirs, new technologies for wastewater treatment) are high.
 - Tariff scheme: the recovery of investments for wastewater reuse through the tariff could result in uncompetitive prices, hindering its use, especially for agriculture.
- External barriers:
 - Supply chain related barriers.
 - Reclaimed water: there are many actors involved in the value chain, roles and responsibilities are not well defined, so there are overlaps and sometimes lack of involvement of the parties.

- Legislative and economic barriers.
 - Monitoring and evaluation (sludge): There is a need to clearly define the minimum types of treatment that sludge must receive prior to its application in agriculture and the physical-chemical and microbiological parameters that must be met depending on the type of crop, establishing a plan for its implementation so that public and private initiatives have legal certainty and a roadmap for where to go.
 - There is a need to include co-digestion in the financing strategies of the regional policy for biogas generation. Instead of financing only new infrastructure, funding instruments should prioritize support for the adaptation of existing sludge infrastructures for co-digestion.
 - Regulatory frameworks (sludge): There is great regulatory uncertainty and heterogeneity of criteria at territorial level. This regulation must be updated so that it is homogeneous in all territories. To this end, there needs to be a consensus at European level to promote a common roadmap for sludge management.
- Internal drivers
 - Organisational drivers:
 - Management model: being a mixed capital company (private/municipal), the goals are shared by the municipality, which strongly supports the adoption of these solutions.
 - Resources availability and optimisation drivers:
 - Increasing scarcity of water resources: limitations to the water transfer from the Tagus River, groundwater overexploitation, impact of climate change on the rain patterns.
 - Product and process development
 - Reclaimed water is currently used in the Alicante region for several uses (e.g., agriculture, urban, recreational use, etc).
- External drivers
 - Policy regulation
 - New regulations related to reused water quality, treated wastewater quality and wastewater sludge application.
 - Society and environmental
 - Strong demand from the society for efficient water management (high awareness of water scarcity). Need to reduce the impact of treated wastewater on the receiving body (coastal waters) and carbon footprint.

The sources related to legislative and economic barriers have been gathered from D5.5 developed on WP5.

Scoping LL circular solutions (Meso and Micro Level):

Scoping, site location and state of the art description:

The circular solutions / projects that will be tested in the LL through BWS take place in wastewater treatment value chain carried out by AMA in the municipality of Alicante. These solutions will be tested out in the Rincón de León and Monte Orgegia WWTPs. Table 4 presents a list of the circularities and their baseline business model types associated.

Table 4 Alicante LL circularities and baseline business model (adapted from: D4.3).

Circularity ID	Circularity identified	Description	Baseline BM ¹	Innovation type ²
C1	Waste to Energy	Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion	CBM	BMI
C2	Wastewater to Reclaimed water	Increase of water reuse (overcoming barriers - technical, economical and governance)	CBM	BMI
C3	Wastewater to Raw materials	Recovery of materials / elements: NaClO production through electrochlorination	LBM	BMI
C4	Waste to Raw materials	Zero waste - Nutrient recovery: Ammonia recovery (ammonium salts production)	NBM	BMI
C5	Wastewater to Energy	Increase of energy production: microturbines	NBM	BP
C6	Wastewater to Raw materials	Hydrogen and oxygen production from reclaimed water and biogas	NBM	BMI

¹Baseline Business Model (Circular Business Model, Linear Business Model, New Business Model);² Innovation type: Business Model Innovation or Business process

Both plants, have different active lines of wastewater treatment. There is a baseline wastewater treatment that is used for discharge back to the ecosystem; and a tertiary treatment that recycles part of the effluent to produce reclaimed water for its reuse in different applications (agriculture, urban green areas, street cleaning, etc.).

Below presented is some corporate data on the water reuse (source: <https://www.aguasdealicante.es/datos-significativos>).

Wastewater Treatment:

- Purified Water: 29.93 Hm³
- Reused Water: 10.15 Hm³
- Valorization of sludge from treatment: 27.40 Tm (100%)

Reuse of Purified Water:

- Current length of the reused water network in Alicante: 79.3 km.
- 83% of green areas in Alicante are irrigated with regenerated water.
- Aguas de Alicante also utilizes non-potable groundwater for use in agriculture, irrigation of landscaped green areas, street cleaning, and other purposes that do not require high-quality water. Reused water is also applied to agricultural irrigation.

- In 2022, the total volume of reused water for various purposes, such as agriculture irrigation, park and garden irrigation, environmental uses, among others, as alternatives to potable water, resulted in a savings of 10,151,793 m³. Aguas de Alicante's commitment to the circular economy represents a significant environmental benefit, in this case, translating into substantial water savings.

The WWTP at Rincon de Leon also carries out an additional desalinization treatment processes to the wastewater.

In the line of resource recovery from the wastewater treatment, the sewage sludge undergoes an anaerobic digestion process to produce biogas which is cogenerated to produce heat and electricity for the internal operation of the equipment. The resulting digestate is sent by transport to a cement company (CEMEX) with which the company has an established partnership. This alliance allows on the one hand, the avoidance of further drying process of the digestate to the plant, and the reuse of the digestate by the cement plant as fuel to operate its processes.

As it can be seen, the WWTPs have established circular processes, and CBMs in their value chain (e.g. reuse of reclaimed water and sludge drying), but there is a potential to increase their capacity by improving the technologies and optimising treatment processes.

Mapping the ecosystem:

The mapping of stakeholders for all the solutions carried out in the LL of Alicante has been carried out in task T4.2. and is presented in deliverable D4.3.

4.2.2 Ideation

4.2.2.1 Idea generation

The circular opportunities identified have been set out in Table 4. It should be clarified that these correspond to circular opportunities identified from the beginning of the project, and that alternative circular solutions have not been explored during this phase. Although, some long-term opportunities have been identified for some of these solutions and have a potential to extend the circular value chain and generate new business models, the analysis of these extend beyond the scope of this document. For further information on the circular opportunities refer to deliverable D4.3.

Of all the circular solutions presented, co-digestion is particularly noteworthy due to the operational feasibility of its implementation and the potential impact it has on improving the plant energy efficiency. The LL has selected solution **C1: Improve and increase of energy production by codigestion** to be analysed in greater detail through these guidelines.

Their selection and prioritisation have been carried out by the LL owner and mentors to enable the assessment of circular indicators (D4.3) and the development of the associated. For the rest of the solutions, an overall classification of potential business models, when possible, will be presented on Annex B, but will not be analysed in detail.

Description of C1 value chain:

Although this solution is described in other documents, for the guidelines practical application a summary is provided together with a review of the current situation:

1. Currently, the digestion of sewage sludge is carried out for the generation of biogas which is transformed through cogeneration (CHP) to supply heat & energy for self-sufficiency to the plant.
2. Co-digestion is an improvement of digestion consisting in the combination of sewage sludge with another substrate of organic origin, which increases biogas production. The value of the product (i.e. mix) is dependent on the quality of the organic substrate input.
3. External suppliers of organic waste are required to produce substrates with higher biogas production capacity.
4. In the same way as during digestion, the resulting digestate is evacuated from the plant and sent to the CEMEX plant for drying and use as fuel. Currently, no alternative valorisation pathway of this by-product is envisaged.

The biogas generated is intended to be used to produce energy for self-consumption at the plant and there are no plans, at least in the short term, to export or valorise it for other external uses (e.g. electric batteries, car recharging, etc.). These have been identified as potential long-term opportunities as indicated before (D4.3) but have not been further assessed in the project.

The difficulty in implementing this new process is to ensure a stable supply of organic matter of sufficient quality (i.e. establishing long term relationship with suppliers, develop new partnerships etc.), managing a complex network of actors, and having the capacity and competences to experiment and develop effective mixes.

During the project, relationships have been established with two local organic waste suppliers (MercaAlicante and Helados Alacant), who are located close to the WWTP plants, and who have been involved in developing the solution. However, in order to scale up the solution and cover the capacity of the plant's infrastructure, the network of suppliers and substrates needs to be expanded.

In the solution, Cetaqua have been assisting AMA in the development of the technical solution, during the experimentation phase with the technology (pilot plant) and development of mixes; in the analysis of the results and also providing support in coordination tasks during the development of CoPs for stakeholder engagement and development of a stakeholder network.

Stakeholder engagement:

During the project, several CoPs, focus group sessions and internal meetings have been held to share and discuss the solutions with the different stakeholder groups involved.

Among the objectives of these meetings were those to obtain information on the different groups' perceptions in the solutions (all), identify barriers, and look for potential collaborations to participate in them (or in future LLs).

Other CoPs have taken a more systemic approach (Macro Level) and have been less focused on the projects being developed in the B-Water Smart, given the importance of creating a shared vision among the network and integrating the ecosystem of actors to ensure the long-term sustainability of the LL.

4.2.2.2 Preliminary Assessment

Although there is no explicit document detailing all the information that should be included in a preliminary feasibility study, this has been carried out organically throughout the project as more information has been obtained. Given the competencies of the LL's lead organisation, it should be

borne in mind that the focus of the analysis has been particularly directed towards the evaluation of technical aspects, with the aim of guaranteeing technological and economic viability to satisfy the requirements of the lead organisation.

Qualitative and quantitative information (when available) is provided below for those aspects that have been considered in this preliminary assessment:

- **Validation of the Idea:**

The solution helps to improve the energy efficiency of their processes and contributes to meeting the goal of becoming a biofactory. In isolation, the solution does not serve a market demand, as waste suppliers have already competitive waste managers. However, given the important social and environmental role of water treatment plants (i.e. guaranteeing a water service to the whole region), it opens up a unique form of collaboration with the water sector for organic waste producers, and other users (e.g. end-users of digestates). These collaborations improve the circular and sustainable practices of the organizations, as well as grants access to a circular economy network that can open up further opportunities.

- **Market Analysis:**

Although the target segment of the business model has been identified, a market study on the services offered by waste managers in the area has not yet been carried out. It cannot be overlooked that the intensive use of these wastes for energy recovery can make an important change at the local level, as it means the development of a nascent waste recovery market with all that this entails and a possible problem for those wastes that are not attractive for energy recovery (or other reuse purposes). These impacts will have to be considered during the next design phases.

- **Financial Viability:**

The investment in infrastructure is reduced since the WWTPs have digesters and co-generators, which makes the solution more attractive. However, plant repair costs have to be considered, in addition to the investment in additional equipment to scaled up the solution. In terms of revenue generation, gate-fees (waste management service by volume of waste received), sale of digestate as fertiliser and energy cost savings are envisaged. However, different scenarios have not yet been designed for evaluation. These will have to consider the availability of local suppliers, and the arrangements that can be made to ensure long-term supply of feedstocks. Operational cost estimates for different scenarios based on volumes have not yet been carried out.

Table 5 presents economic data for the costs of the experimentation and pilot tests (volumes cannot be considered representative) carried out in during the project. Table 6 presents estimated costs of infrastructure for a scaled-up scenario of co-digestion.

Table 5 Alicante LL C1 Operational costs during BWS pilot phase

COSTS				
Category	Description	Scenario	Type	Costs
Technology	Pilot equipment	Pilot	OPEX	€ 120.000,00
Service	Repair and maintenance (chiller, crusher, methane meter, wiring)	Pilot	OPEX	€ 17.000,00
Service	Consulting services/audits	Pilot	OPEX	€ 15.000,00
Service	Rents (methane portable meter)	Pilot	OPEX	€ 800,00
TOT (€)				€ 152.800,00

Table 6 Alicante LL C1 CAPEX scaled-up scenario

COSTS				
Category	Description	Scenario	Type	Costs
Technology	Co-generator (equipment and wiring)	Scale-up	CAPEX	€ 600.000,00
Equipment	Feedstock (solid waste) reception station	Scale-up	CAPEX	€ 30.000,00
Equipment	Feedstock distribution system (wiring and)	Scale-up	CAPEX	€ 15.000,00
Equipment	Feedstock shredder (tritador)	Scale-up	CAPEX	€ 15.000,00
TOT (€)				€ 660.000,00

As for revenue streams, no performance forecasts were made during the preliminary studies. However, after experimentation with tested feedstocks, a Scaled-up scenario has estimated an increase in electricity generation of 4,500 MWh compared to the baseline scenario of digestion, which supposes an equivalent to energy savings of approximately 400,000 €/y (considering an average market price in 2023 of 88 €/Mwh).

- **Technical feasibility:**

Co-digestion is a process that is successfully implemented in numerous WWTPs worldwide. As part of the development of biogas solutions, experimentation with locally sourced substrates is essential to be able to carry out feasibility analysis. These are carried out as part of the innovation process of the circular solutions in the LLs.

- **Social and environmental impacts:**

On the one hand, co-digestion through biogas generation contributes to renewable energy production, reducing greenhouse gases emissions. The recovery of organic waste also reduces landfilling and can benefit agriculture with organic fertilisers. However, it can generate gaseous emissions and unpleasant odours, requiring careful management. Socially, the project can generate local employment and encourage community participation, but it is essential to address potential conflicts of interest with waste managers and maintain trust through transparent communication. In summary, the co-digestion offers significant benefits, but its success depends on careful management of environmental and social impacts.

- **Risks and Challenges:**

At the regulatory level, the following challenges are present:

- One of the key challenges is the need for a more comprehensive harmonisation of standards for digestate quality, as lack of consistency can hinder the efficient management and reuse of this by-product. In addition, co-digestion may be subject to different interpretations and regulatory approaches. Regulatory complexity and variability in implementation can create uncertainty for operators and limit the effective expansion of practices.

- Regarding the regulatory framework and the monitoring and evaluation of sludge:

There is a need to clearly define the minimum types of treatment that sludge must receive prior to its application in agriculture and the physical-chemical and microbiological parameters that must be met depending on the type of crop, establishing a plan for its implementation so that public and private initiatives have legal certainty and a roadmap for where to go. At the level of funding, there is a need to include co-digestion in the financing strategies of the regional policy for biogas generation. Instead of financing only new infrastructure, funding instruments should prioritize support for the adaptation of existing sludge infrastructures for co-digestion.

At the operational level, a major risk is the availability of sufficient organic waste to reach the available capacity of the infrastructures, as well as the long-term permanence of supply. The information presented above have been gathered from document D5.5.
- Equipment and Resources:**

Operational equipment is in place at the plant to start co-digestion, although in a potential scale-up scenario it would be necessary to rehabilitate and reinvest in infrastructure. Future partnerships with local waste suppliers would be required to cover the volumetric capacity of the plant. In addition, to facilitate implementation, the service of a third-party company specialised in the development of these projects, with extensive technical and regulatory experience, may be used to assist in the search for waste suppliers, among other activities.

4.2.2.3 Concept

Due to the complexity of the value chain that characterises circular solutions linked to biogas production, it is necessary to analyse the business model from both an organisational and a systemic perspective, as it includes the participation of several actors in the business ecosystem. For this purpose, in addition to the traditional dimensions of value proposition, creation, distribution and capture, the system dimensions of coordination, centralisation and value network will be considered.

Step 1: Circular strategies and cycle of operation.

Circular strategies: **Refuse, Rethink, Reuse and Recovery.**

The operating cycle: **Technical and Biological cycle.**

Step 2: Business model innovation strategy.

The currently existing business model, digestion, is a **circular starting business model** as it implements the same circular strategies, and there is an existing industrial symbiosis with CEMEX and the farmers (who are supplied with digestate).

The innovation strategy followed by this CBM is: **CBM transformation.**

Step 3: BMI pathway and SCBM

The innovation pathway followed by the CBM:

Technological innovation: **Maximize material and energy efficiency & Create value from waste.**

Social innovation: the priority is the reduction of energy consumption from sources outside the plant, and the promotion of self-sufficiency through the improvement of the products (cosubstrate: sludge plus organic waste) obtained through the processes. Social innovation is

therefore predominantly directed towards **Encourage sufficiency**. However, it is also intended to innovate by encouraging the creation of a network of actors, which can drive the development of circular solutions, promote new collaborations, and encourage the exchange of resources between different sectors. This innovation is aligned with a **Adopt a stewardship role** archetype.

Organisational innovation: the LL aims to **Develop scale-up solutions** and adopt a cost recovery and energy saving model that not only produces social and environmental benefits, but also sustainable economic performance over time.

SCBM archetype: **Hybrid model: Scale-up sufficiency and Scale-up stewardship**.

For further information on the development of the innovation pathway, and the characteristics of the SCBM archetype refer to Figure 7, Figure 8 and Table 1 presented in section 3.4.3.3.

Step 4: Circular business model classification

CBM type (according to Lacy et al.): **Hybrid model (Resource recovery and Circular Inputs)**.

CBM subtype (according to Lacy et al): **Industrial Symbiosis**

From a systemic or ecosystem analysis perspective, the CBM subtype resulting from the implementation of co-digestion can be classified as an "Industrial Symbiosis" in which, with respect to the base scenario, the complexity of the value chain has been increased by the intervention of new actors (mainly feedstock suppliers but also a potential third party acting as solution provider) in the network. This perspective is also coherent with the LL's vision to become a biofactory.

According to the stage of development of the industrial symbiosis system in Alicante (incipient stage) and based on the taxonomy of these systems, it could be classified as a system with low centralisation and coordination (refer to Figure 9). This is typical of an industrial network that is not yet very mature, and in which there is no interrelation between the network members, outside of the exchanges that take place with the central organisation. Like the innovation process of other CBMs, the development of industrial symbiosis is dynamic and iterative in nature.

Refer to **Annex B**, for the classification of the remainder of CBMs linked to rest of circular solutions identified in the LL.

Step 5: Circular Business Model Canvas

A preliminary circular business model canvas for C1 is presented in Table 7.

For practical reasons, reference is made to those elements that, given the stage of development of the case study, will need to be reviewed in depth further in the detail design phase of the business model innovation process. These have been indicated with a symbol (*).

Table 7 Alicante LL C1 (Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion) CBMC.

Circular Business Model Canvas		Circularity goal and scope definition		Sustainability mission and action			
<p>Living Lab: ALICANTE</p> <p>Legend: Value proposition Value creation & delivery Value capture</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted CE principle (Select one or more principle) - P1) Create value from waste, P2) Maximize energy and material efficiency, P3) Substitute with renewables and natural processes • CE strategies (Select one or more strategies) - R1 - Rethink, R2 -- Avoid, R3 -- Reduce, R4-Replace, R5 - Reuse, R6- Recycle, R7 - Cascading, R8 - Store, R9 - Recover • Operating cycle (Select business operation cycle) • Technical cycle, Biological cycle • Circular business model innovation strategy (Select innovation strategy) • CBM transformation, CBM diversification, Circular start-up, CBM acquisition • Sustainable circular innovation pathways (Select one or more) • Purposeful sufficiency, Scaled-up sufficiency, Purposeful functionality, Scaled-up functionality, Purposeful stewardship, Scale-up stewardship • Circular business model type (Select one or more of the targeted circular business model type) • Circular supplies, Sharing platform, Product as a service, Product lifespan extension, Resource recovery 		<p>Targeted sustainable development goal</p> <p>Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions Goal 17: Partnership for the goals</p>			
Key Partners	Key Activities	Ecosystem Activities	Value Proposition		Customer Segments	Targeted solution	Benefits and burden
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >AMAEM (WWTPs: Rincón de León and Monte Orgegia) >Consultants >Technology provider (*) >Organic feedstock suppliers (Mercalicante, Helados Alacant *) >Digestate end-users >Transports company (*) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Production of biogas (waste management*, mixing, AD, dispose of digestate) >Coordination and management of supply chain >Transportation of digestate to end users >Maintenance and repair of infrastructure >Running experiments with different substrate mixes. >Monitoring efficiency and operations >Burocracy procedures (regulation compliance, permits, staying up to date etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Public authorities: policy and regulations amendments, social awareness campaigns, issuance of permits etc. >R&I: dissemination of case study >Stakeholder engagement (e.g. CoPs): maintain relationships with value network, identify opportunities, gather feedback, promote new collaborations, dissemination and promotion of circular practices... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >To WWTPs (AMAEM): Energy resilience by saving energy consumption through biogas improved treatment. Improves business resilience by a diversification strategy (i.e. waste managers). Improve brand by adopting circular practices, and social perception from the community. >To organic feedstock supplier (Mercalicante and Helados Alacant*): WWTPs offer waste management service. Improving brand image by collaborating with water industry. Access to a local ecosystem network. >To Digestate end-users (CEMEX, agriculture, others): digestate. Promoting their circular and sustainable practices >To Ayuntamiento de Alicante: Improving wastewater management system in the municipality (increased performance of services). Reducing pollution, recirculation and maximization of resources efficiency. <p>Stakeholders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >All: Moving towards achieving strategic objectives of the Living Labs. >Technology provider: building development of technology increased 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Organic waste suppliers (e.g. food Industry, hospitality) >Digestate end-users (e.g. construction and agricultural sector) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Organic waste suppliers -> Waste management services >Digestate end-user -> Valorization of digestate as fertilizer or fuel. 	<p>Benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Increased city resilience to climate change by improving of water and wastewater services. >New job opportunities. <p><i>Environment:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Reduced GHG (methane capture and CO2 reduction). >Waste management: reduced sludge volume to be managed. >Odour control: reduced foul-smelling compounds due to Anaerobic Digestion. <p>Burden:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Increased competition for "high quality" organic waste <p><i>Society:</i></p>
			Channels	Need/problem/challenge			
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Physical channels: transportation of resources in and out of the plant. >AMAEM channels: Website, participation on circular economy conventions, events and fairs, site visits etc. >Project channels (ecosystem network after project): CoP, industry events, workshops, focus groups. >Municipality channels: social awareness campaigns. 	<p>Severe droughts in the region coupled with high demand of water from agriculture and tourism sector, demands resilient water infrastructure, capable of satisfying the needs of the population.</p> <p>Challenge is to improve the processes to maximize their efficiency.</p>			
			Cost Structure		Revenue Streams		
			<p>*The operational costs structure still to be defined. Below presented available economic data:</p> <p>CAPEX: 660.000€</p> <p>Cogenerator</p> <p>Fine-tuning of available infrastructure</p> <p>Reception station and mixing equipment</p> <p>OPEX -</p> <p>Experimentation (Pilot): 150.000€</p> <p>Transportation (to be agreed depending on organizational structure)</p> <p>Coordinating and managing supply chain</p> <p>Maintenance and repair</p> <p>Labor (in-plant workers, engineer and administrator)</p>		<p>*Revenue streams are not yet detailed. Below presented available estimated revenues:</p> <p>Gate fees for waste/wastewater management services</p> <p>Energy cost-savings (400.000€)</p> <p>Selling of digestate (if applicable)</p>		

Value Proposition
<p>>AMAEM (WWTPS): Energy resilience of the company by saving energy consumption through biogas. Increasing business portfolio as waste managers to food industry and private customers (e.g. restaurants). Improve circular and sustainability practices and social perception from the community.</p> <p>>Organic feedstock supplier (Mercalicante and Helados Alacant): Waste management service (**). Improving brand image by collaborating with water industry. Access to a local ecosystem network.</p> <p>>Digestate end-users (CEMEX, agriculture, others): digestate. Promoting their circular and sustainable practices</p> <p>>Ayuntamiento de Alicante: Improving wastewater management system in the municipality (increased performance of services). Reducing pollution, recirculation and maximization of resources efficiency.</p> <p>Stakeholders:</p> <p>>All: Moving towards attaining strategic objectives of the Living Labs.</p> <p>>Technology provider: building development of technology increased knowledge biogas production projects, and efficiency of the technology processes to produce better quality biogas, and also develop new substrates recipes.</p> <p>>Consultants: improved knowledge on biogas projects, development of sludge mix recipes.</p>

Figure 15 Alicante LL C1 Value proposition from Table 7

Step 6: SWOT Analysis:

The C1 CBM SWOT analysis is presented in Figure 16 Alicante LL C1 CBM SWOT

SWOT ANALYSIS	
INTERNAL FACTORS	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<p>>Highly technical competencies in wastewater treatment processes.</p> <p>>Organization strategic plan is aligned with circular vision</p> <p>>Infrastructure available, not high investment required to operationalize solution.</p> <p>>Availability of resources (sewage sludge) and also local feedstock suppliers</p> <p>>Developing a stewardship rol at local and regional levels allows staying in front of innovation and development of new solutions.</p>	<p>>Efficiency of the product is dependent on waste input which is variable.</p> <p>>Complex value chain management requiring high operating excellence.</p> <p>>New activity requiring experience and training to prevent failures. Potentially requiring high maintenance costs.</p> <p>>Experimentation process needs to be set-up for testing new feedstocks on a regular basis and adapt to the available supplies.</p> <p>>No owned transport services.</p>
EXTERNAL FACTORS	
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<p>>Supporting public authorities to improve regulation framework around sludge.</p> <p>>Expanding the value network to improve resource recovery and distribution of other products aside of digestate.</p> <p>>Partnerships with Energy sector for alternative use of biogas, but also with the Food Industry and Waste sector (for increasing feedstock supply for biogas production).</p> <p>>Alternative valorization routes for digestate.</p>	<p>>Extensive bureaucracy procedures (e.g. permits, licenses) for the biogas solutions.</p> <p>>Restrictive regulations to reuse digestate.</p> <p>>Access to the waste market, and locking enough high quality feedstock. Competition over organic waste with waste sector.</p>

Figure 16 Alicante LL C1 CBM SWOT analysis.

Step 7: Define performance and outcome metrics.

Metrics for the evaluation of the CBM have been identified and selected by the LLs following the AF of D6.3. as part of the work to be developed in WP4, T4.2.

These have considered in further detail in D4.3 for the socio-environmental and economic assessment of the value chain according to three differentiated scenarios: baseline, circular and scaled-up.

Step 8: Development of prototypes.

During this phase, feedback has mainly been obtained from waste suppliers for the co-creation of the solution. No other prototypes or virtual simulations have been carried out.

4.2.3 Detail design

4.2.3.1 Experimentation

This section is essential for the fine tuning of the CBM, as the feasibility of using the substrates of the service providers has to be assessed before confirming that the waste can be used profitably. It is the biogas generation capacity of the substrate what determines the gate fees, i.e. the waste management service fees (one of the potential revenue streams of the CBM).

At the time of writing, the experimental phase has been completed. However, further experimentation will be necessary if other organic substrates are required for attaining the scaled-up volumes considered.

For more information about the description and results of the experiments and pilots carried out in the Living Lab, refer to D2.17.

4.2.3.2 Detail design

A detailed design of the CBM is still to be carried out. The innovation process is at this current stage.

4.2.3.3 Pilot

It is planned, outside the framework of this B-Water Smart project, to carry out a full-scale pilot (i.e. digester) at the Monte Orgegia plant, to stress the system, fine-tune the operational processes, identify faults, among other activities.

4.3 Lisbon

4.3.1 Framing and scoping of the circular solutions in the Living Lab

Framing LL macro level context:

LL challenges:

The key smart-water challenges of the Lisbon LL targeted in B-WaterSmart are (i) a growing resident population and economy, dependent on distant freshwater resources (up to 100 km), (ii) climate challenges (e.g., droughts and floods) and (iii) need to increase urban green areas.

LL problem-owner:

The LL problem-owner in Lisbon is the Camara Municipal de Lisboa. The Lisbon Municipal Chamber, also known as the Lisbon City Council, is the local government entity in charge of the administration and management of municipal affairs in the city of Lisbon. Its role is crucial in making decisions and implementing policies that directly affect the residents of Lisbon. Some of the responsibilities of the Lisbon City Council include urban planning, public transport, waste management, sanitation, culture, tourism, education, and other public services at the local level.

In 2023, the city of Lisbon has a population of 547733 inhabitants and its metropolitan area has a population of 3,000,536. (source: <https://worldpopulationreview.com>).

LL vision:

Lisbon aims at providing high quality of life for an increasing population and growing economy, whilst tackling climate change challenges (e.g., droughts and floods) based on a green-blue problem-solving infrastructure. Lisbon LL vision is to accelerate the transformation to a water-smarter economy and society. The green-blue infrastructure is a solution applied in Lisbon for tackling climate change impacts related to droughts, floods, and heat waves. As reclaimed water is a sustainable source, largely independent of climate uncertainty, it can contribute to reducing pressure on strategic freshwater resources and to allow resources' recovery, such as phosphorus.

LL objectives:

The strategic objectives for the LLs were developed by the LLs in Task 1.4 and with the input of the CoPs, as part of the project work carried out in WP1. A final strategic agenda will be presented on D1.4 - Final strategic agenda and implementation plan for each LL, with the agreed LL vision and objectives.

LL partners:

Lisbon Municipality (CML) is the Lisbon case-study problem owner; as such, CML makes the city's data and resources available as a LL in the project, promotes the Lisbon Community of Practice, participates in the B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance, tests the Lisbon LL solutions developed within the project and plays a key role in disseminating and promoting the adoption of these solutions among its extensive networking platforms. CML also develops the urban water cycle observatory, through a linked 3rd party - LEN (Lisboa E-Nova).

Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC) is the mentor and R&I partner for the Lisbon LL, responsible, among others, for the development of the knowledge, methodologies and analytics behind the tools of (health and environment) risk assessment, reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution network, WEP balance, and decision support of alternative courses of action based on performance-cost-risk indicators. LNEC also participates in the development of the water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in beverage industry for artisanal craft beer production.

Águas do Tejo Atântico (AdTA) is the water utility enabler of Lisbon LL, providing real data (on wastewater treatment and water reclamation) for several tools and is responsible for conducting the pilot tests needed to develop the water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in craft beer production.

Agência para a Energia (Adene) is a solution provider responsible for developing the knowledge and the tool for climate-readiness certification.

Baseform is a solution provider responsible for developing the software for the risk assessment, reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution network, WEP balance and decision-support tools.

Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa (ICS-UL) is a cross-cutting R&I partner integrating the social sciences and humanities and is the Lisbon CoP moderator.

Key dependencies, risks, and opportunities:

- Freshwater resources
 - Risks: dependency on distant freshwater resources which, under the existing climate change scenario, represents a risk for the growing population and economy.
 - Opportunities: integrated water management. Increase public awareness on efficient water use. Promote water reuse in non-potable uses (e.g. street cleaning, irrigation, industrial etc.). Decrease use of freshwater sources.
- Urban infrastructure (e.g. blue and green infrastructure, water distribution network)
 - Risks: Increased urban green areas results in an increased water consumption.
 - Opportunity: Implement a reclaimed water distribution network in the city.
- Technology:
 - Risks: linear economy.
 - Opportunities: innovation in new technologies that enable the recovery of materials and nutrients. Promotion of the circular economy and partnerships in the city, job creation, etc.
- Regulatory framework
 - Risk: lack of regulatory clarity on the approval and governance of reuse schemes, namely on the water distribution service.
 - Opportunities: update laws and policies to drive the adoption of circular water solutions.
- Water management governance
 - Risk: Need for planning and action at local and basin levels.
 - Opportunities: innovation in governance models.
- Social perception:
 - Risk: lack of public awareness regarding water sources' local context
 - Opportunity: inform the public on the use of water in the city, the treatment of wastewater and the use of fit-for-purpose water.

Barriers and drivers (Macro level):

Main barriers :

- Legislation - No secondary users allowed in a water reuse system (DL 119/2019), difficult to implement water reuse & rainwater harvesting in buildings (DR 23/1995).
- Infrastructure - Reclaimed water distribution network exists only in limited Lisbon areas, uncertainty as to the entity responsible for this distribution network.
- Public perception - Relatively low levels of interest about water consumption in the city, although the main freshwater resources are distant approximately 100 km.

Scoping LL circular solutions (Meso and Micro Level):

Scoping, site location and state of the art description:

The previous section described the macro vision of the LL. In the following, we will narrow down the system of analysis to the circular solutions that are being developed in the B-Water Smart.

The challenges posed by the climate change (e.g. droughts), coupled with the expansion of green areas, reflect the need to readapt the municipality's water resource management according to circularity principles. Therefore, the circular solutions tested in the LL are intended to enable water in non-potable uses (refer to Table 8).

Table 8 Lisbon LL circularities and baseline business model (adapted from: D4.3).

Circularity ID	Circularity identified	Description	Baseline BM ¹	Innovation type ²
C7	Wastewater to Reclaimed water	Urban water reuse for irrigation	LBM	BMI
C8	Wastewater to Reclaimed water	Industrial water reuse for food grade application	N/A	BMI

¹Baseline Business Model (Circular Business Model, Linear Business Model, New Business Model); ² Innovation type: Business Model Innovation or Business process

Next solution C7's value chain and the baseline scenario for the irrigation of green areas in the city of Lisbon is described.

Currently, water for the city's drinking water supply is mainly obtained from a surface water source located 100 km away from the city of Lisbon. This is treated and distributed to the city and the metropolitan area by EPAL, a water company belonging to Aguas de Portugal Group (AdP).

The wastewater treatment is managed by another water company, Águas do Tejo Atlântico (AdTA), also belonging to the AdP Group, through several WWTPs that collect urban effluents, treat them, and discharge them into the ecosystem (to the estuary of the Tagus River). As a starting point for the analysis of the baseline scenario, it is considered that is possible to further improve the quality of the treated effluent to produce reclaimed water for non-potable uses, such as irrigation.

Currently, the green areas surrounding the Beirolas WWTP are irrigated with reclaimed water. One of these green areas was used for the reception of one million people during a large religious event in the summer of 2023.

For promoting public awareness on water scarcity and the public engagement and acceptance on water reuse, a circular project of a demonstrative nature is being developed – the production of high-quality reclaimed water (food grade application) is obtained for reuse in industrial applications (i.e. beverage industry – craft beer production) (circularity C8), although this will not be analysed in this document.

Mapping the ecosystem:

The mapping of stakeholders for all the circularities carried out in the LL of Lisbon has been carried out in task T4.2. and is presented in D4.3.

4.3.2 Ideation

4.3.2.1 Idea generation:

Apart from the circular opportunities defined in the previous section, no other ideas have been generated.

From this section onwards, the analysis focuses on the C7 solution of irrigation of urban green areas with reclaimed water. Other uses such as irrigation in state-owned and private-owned gardens with public access are also considered (future scenario).

The goal of this solution is to recirculate the effluent, transforming a linear value chain (i.e. currently wastewater is treated and discharged in the environment) to a circular one, and thereby reduce the consumption of potable water in non-potable uses. The drinking water service will still continue to be used in the irrigation of some gardens and, for the water reuse selected green areas, during the construction of the reclaimed water distribution network.

The value chain will be analysed from a systemic (meso-level) perspective, given the scope, internal organisation, and involvement of multiple actors in the LL.

As the LL is constituted around a public entity as the driving organisation (CML), the objectives are of a broader nature, and the role it plays revolves around enabling, coordinating, and maintaining a network of actors. Moreover, in this context, the presence of restrictive regulatory, organizational, and social barriers necessitates, during this stage of the innovation process, the deployment of capabilities and competencies specific to public authorities (e.g., awareness campaigns, driving regulatory changes, issuing permits and licenses, etc.) to address the existing issues.

As barriers are overcome and new regulation is developed, the LL will have to adapt and transfer capacities and resources towards an effective implementation of water reuse systems, involving of solution providers and water companies.

The ultimate goal goes beyond introducing a CBM of water reuse for a specific case, but to enable the city to allow the extended use of reclaimed water to multiple users, public and private. This will be possible by addressing current policy and regulation restrictions and creating a new distribution network for reclaimed water.

The CML has a dual role in the solution: first as an enabler and manager of the reclaimed water distribution network and another as an end-user of the reclaimed water. AdTA would act as the producer of the reclaimed water.

However, the definition of roles and responsibilities can't still be defined due to the existing barriers.

Stakeholder engagement:

During the development of the project, numerous CoPs have been carried out on different themes to engage the different stakeholders affected by the solution.

4.3.2.2 Preliminary feasibility assessment:

Information on the feasibility studies available is provided below:

- Validation of the Idea:**
 The development of this circular solution is aligned with the strategic plans of the city of Lisbon to promote water reuse. Resources and competencies are allocated for its implementation.
- Market Analysis:**
 The expected customer segment is the municipality itself and other private gardens. For the time being, the demand for reclaimed water for municipal use has been estimated at 4Mm³/year to cover the irrigation of several green areas.
- Financial Viability:**
 The economic viability (cost-benefit analysis) has not been estimated yet, although most of the projected costs have been defined. Operational costs will need to be developed in more detail in order to make future projections. Cost recovery is expected by a reclaimed water tariff still to be defined.

Table 9 Lisbon LL C7 CAPEX & OPEX (€/y) scaled-up scenario.

COSTS SCALED-UP				
Category	Description	Scenario	Type	Costs
Infrastructure	Reclaim water distribution network (1)	Scale-up	CAPEX	€ 30.966.758,00
TOT (€)				€ 30.966.758,00
Labor	Workforce (2 half-time eng, 5 full-time ope)	Scale-up	OPEX	€ 118.000,00
Service	Consultancy services (Monitoring)	Scale-up	OPEX	€ 28.362,00
Service	Water reuse Licensing fee	Scale-up	OPEX	€ 2.500,00
Service	Repair and maintenance distribution network	Scale-up	OPEX	€ 480.000,00
Infrastructure	Depreciation (3)	Scale-up	OPEX	€ 619.335,00
TOT (€)				€ 1.248.197,00

Notes (numbering in brackets) from Table 9:

- Cumulative investment until 2030 in the water supply network (over 2020-2030). The investment in fixed capital reflects the costs of civil construction of pipelines, reservoirs and pumping stations, the installation of electromechanical equipment and its replacement after 20 years after the start of operation. These costs were determined based on Technical Guide No. 23 promoted by the Water and Waste Services Regulator Authority ERSAR (source <https://www.ersar.pt/pt/publicacoes/publicacoes-tecnicas/guias>).

2. It is estimated that from year 2030 the operation and maintenance costs will amount to around €480,000 per year.
 3. Depreciation was calculated based on the constant quota method, considering the average useful life of pipelines and reservoirs of 50 years ($30.966.758\text{€}/50\text{years}=619.335\text{€}/\text{year}$) based on Technical Guide No. 23 promoted by the Water and Waste Services Regulator Authority ERSAR (source <https://www.ersar.pt/pt/publicacoes/publicacoes-tecnicas/guias>).
- **Technical feasibility:**
The WWTP of Beirolas (Águas do Tejo Atlântico) has the technology to produce quality reclaimed water in accordance with current regulations.
 - **Risks and Challenges:**
The main risks and challenges are regulatory. These have been defined in the previous section. For more information on the regulatory barriers refer to D5.5.
 - **Equipment and Resources:**
It is under evaluation the construction and management of the reclamation water network in Lisbon.

4.3.2.3 Concept

Step 1: Circular strategies and cycle of operation.

Circular strategies: **Rethink, Avoid and Reuse.**

The operating cycle: **Technical and Biological cycle.**

Step 2: Business model innovation strategy.

The baseline business model is **linear**.

The innovation strategy followed by this business model is: **CBM transformation.**

Step 3: BMI pathway and SCBM

The innovation pathway that follows the business model:

Technological innovation: **Substitute with renewables and natural processes** and **Create value from waste.**

Social innovation: The main priority is to raise public awareness of the need to reduce the consumption of water from natural sources and to build climate resilience by adopting circular solutions such as the reuse of reclaimed water. On the other hand, innovation is also geared towards the creation of a new line of action based on reclaimed water, independent of the current water service management carried out in the city, which opens up the possibility of adopting a steward role and expanding the network of actors in the management of reused water in the city.

Organisational innovation: Repurpose for society or the environment. There is a priority in delivering social and environmental benefits over economic benefits.

SCBM archetype: **Purposeful Stewardship.**

Lisbon's innovation pathway indicates that the Purposeful stewardship archetype aligns with the municipality's objectives, given that it aims to **Replace natural water sources with renewable sources** through the provision of reclaimed water and its service to green areas; by coordinating the needs of the stakeholders involved: citizens, environment, water companies, and public authorities; while extending sustainability solutions by prioritising drinking water savings, through the circular solution of reclaimed water reuse, over economic returns.

For further information on the development of the innovation pathway, and the characteristics of the SCBM archetype refer to Figure 7, Figure 8 and Table 1 presented in section 3.4.3.3.

Step 4: Circular business model classification

CBM type (according to Lacy et al. 2020): **Hybrid model**. Circular inputs and resource recovery.

CBM subtype (according to Lacy et al. 2020): **Upcycling**. Since the quality of the water will be increased compared to the effluent.

Refer to **Annex B**, for the classification of the remainder of CBMs linked to rest of circular solutions identified in the LL.

Step 5: Circular Business Model Canvas

A preliminary circular business model canvas for C7 is presented in Table 10.

Table 10 Lisbon LL C7 (Urban water reuse for irrigation) CBMC

Circular Business Model Canvas		Circularity goal and scope definition		Sustainability mission and action				
Living Lab: LISBON		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Targeted CE principle (Select one or more principle) -P1) Create value from waste, P2) Maximize energy and material efficiency, P3) Substitute with renewables and natural processes CE strategies (Select one or more strategies) R1 - Rethink, R2 – Avoid, R3 – Reduce, R4-Replace, R5 - Reuse, R6- Recycle, R7 - Cascading, R8 - Store, R9 - Recover Operating cycle (Select business operation cycle) Technical cycle, Biological cycle Circular business model innovation strategy (Select innovation strategy) CBM transformation, CBM diversification, Circular start-up, CBM acquisition Sustainable circular innovation pathways (Select one or more) Purposeful sufficiency, Scaled-up sufficiency, Purposeful functionality, Scaled-up functionality, Purposeful stewardship, Scale-up stewardship Circular business model type (Select one or more of the targeted circular business model type) Circular supplies, Sharing platform, Product as a service, Product lifespan extension, Resource recovery 		Targeted sustainable development goal Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions Goal 17: Partnership for the goals				
Legend: Value proposition Value creation & delivery Value capture								
Key Partners	Key Activities	Ecosystem Activities	Value Proposition	Customer Segments	Targeted solution	Benefits and burden		
<p>Câmara Municipal de Lisboa (CML): water consumption in non-potable uses (including green areas irrigation and street cleaning), reclaimed water distribution (the solution for the construction and management of the distribution network is currently under analysis, CML is one of the potential solution providers), stakeholder engagement (promoting partnerships, raising awareness).</p> <p>Águas do Tejo Atlântico (AdTA): reclaimed water fit-for-purpose production, reclaimed water distribution (the solution for the construction and management of the distribution network is currently under analysis, AdTA is one of the potential solution providers)</p> <p>EPAL: drinking water production, drinking water distribution in Lisbon, reclaimed water distribution (the solution for the construction and management of the distribution network is currently under analysis, EPAL is one of the potential solution providers),</p>	<p>>Production of reclaimed water from treated wastewater (including additional/advanced treatment)</p> <p>>Distribution of reclaimed water from the WWTPs to the places of use (e.g. green areas)</p> <p>>Use of reclaimed water in non-potable uses (e.g., irrigation, street cleaning)</p> <p>>Monitoring reclaimed water quality at the points of production, delivery and use</p> <p>>Looking to partnerships and collaboration with relevant stakeholders to innovate and promote the use of reclaimed water</p>	<p>Public authorities (APA, ERSAR, ARS/LVT): regulation and legislation updates (when needed), issuance of permits, promoting awareness towards water reuse</p> <p>Solution & Tech providers (inc. Baseform): consulting services to urban development and water management</p> <p>R&I&D providers (inc. LNEC): provision of knowledge in the field of water quality (treatment processes) and water reuse related risk management. Dissemination of case studies</p>	<p>For customers: (CML & others public gardens owners)</p> <p>>Use of reclaimed water for irrigating green areas as an alternative to drinking water</p> <p>> Improving their sustainable and circular practices.</p> <p>For water utilities:</p> <p>>Creating value from treated wastewater.</p> <p>>Diversification their business portfolio by providing a new service and product that can satisfy customer demands, opening new collaboration opportunities for other reuse purposes.</p> <p>For environment:</p> <p>>Safeguarding the ecosystem by reducing the use of freshwater.</p> <p>For community:</p> <p>>Increasing resilience of the city to climate change.</p> <p>For employees:</p> <p>>New job opportunities associated to the management of the reclaimed water distribution network, monitoring, etc.</p>	<p>CML is the main user of reclaimed water in the case of green areas irrigation, in Lisbon.</p> <p>State-owners, local administration-owners and private-owners of gardens with public access, in Lisbon</p>	<p>Use of fit-for-purpose reclaimed water (class-A for unrestricted irrigation, class B for restricted irrigation - DL 119/2019) for both customer segments.</p>	<p>Benefits:</p> <p><i>Environment:</i></p> <p>>Reduced use of freshwater sources.</p> <p><i>Society:</i></p> <p>>Increased the sustainability in the use of water.</p> <p>>Increased water security in the city.</p> <p>>Increased the city's resilience to climate change, since it is used an rainfall-independent water source.</p> <p>>Promotion of the circular economy around water and associated resources (i.e. phosphorus).</p> <p>>Sustained increased of urban green areas which results, among other benefits, in the promotion of the population wellbeing.</p> <p>Burden:</p> <p>>Not yet determined.</p>		
	Key Resources		Channels				Need/problem/challeng	Customer
	<p>>Treated wastewater</p> <p>>Reclaimed water</p> <p>>Additional/advanced wastewater treatment infrastructure</p> <p>>Reclaimed water distribution network</p> <p>>Permits and licences</p> <p>>Water quality system</p> <p>>Digital tools (WEP balance, risk assessment, reclaimed water quality modeling, alternative selection)</p> <p>>Skillful workforce</p>		<p>>Physical: Additional/advanced wastewater treatment infrastructure, reclaimed water distribution network.</p> <p>>Project and LL channels: CoP, focus groups, workshops, dissemination in conferences, etc.</p> <p>>Public authorities: increasing society environmental awareness, improving social perception regarding water reuse</p> <p>>Water utilities: demonstration sites, activities with schools.</p>				<p>Improving resilience against climate change / distant freshwater resources / implement sustainable blue-green solutions in the city</p>	<p>>Long-term partnerships</p> <p>>Transactional relationships</p>
<p>Cost Structure</p> <p>*Production and distribution costs of reclaimed water to be defined. Below costs available at this moment: CAPEX: 30.966.758 € Reclaimed water distribution network OPEX: 1.248.197 € (*) Workforce Consultancy services Water reuse Licensing fee Repair and maintenance distribution network Depreciation</p>			<p>Revenue Streams</p> <p>*Revenue streams and pricing mechanisms of reclaimed water to be defined. Below</p> <p>Avoided cost in the purchase of drinking water for non-potables, such as irrigation of green areas (*)</p>					

Step 6: SWOT Analysis:

The C7 CBM SWOT analysis is presented in Figure 17

SWOT ANALYSIS	
INTERNAL FACTORS	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Avoided cost in the purchase of drinking water for non-potables, such as irrigation of green areas >Alignment in vision among stakeholders and across levels to promote water reuse. >Organization's competences, capacities and resources suit to overcome current challenges. Ability to promote policy and regulation changes, social awareness, sustainable projects. >Distribution network for reclaimed water is planned as part of the water reuse strategic plan for Lisbon. >Treated wastewater volume available for the use and AdTA's technical skill and willingness, supported by Portuguese legislation recent developments, to produce reclaimed water. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >The management of the reclaimed water distribution network is not yet defined. >Urban water reuse is pioneering in Portugal, so an effort in reclaimed water quality monitoring is currently asked to users. >Significant investment in the construction of the reclaimed water distribution network. >Investment needed in advanced treatment for Class-A reclaimed water production. >The use of reclaimed water only for irrigation results in an uneven water demand along the year, with no use of the treatment and distribution infrastructure in the periods without irrigation (namely, during the Winter months). It is necessary to promote other non-potable water reuses (in industry, namely).
EXTERNAL FACTORS	
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Increase resilience of the city by promoting the construction of blue and green sustainable infrastructure. >Creating a new market for reclaimed water. >Increased quality requirements for treated wastewater discharge introduced by the recast of the Urban Wastewater Directive can make water reuse easier (closer and not necessarily higher water quality requirements for reuse and lower additional/advanced treatment needed for reclamation). >Developing a stewardship role at local and regional levels, to promote circular economy. Becoming a champion in circular practices and staying in front of innovation and development of new solutions. >Updating regulation to promote adoption of circular solutions. >Exploring public-private partnerships to implement water reuse projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >The situation currently existing in the Lisbon water distribution service is, among other aspects, affecting the decision on the management of the reclaimed water distribution network. >External political and economic context not favourable for investments and impacting the goods supply chains.

Figure 17 Lisbon LL C7 CBM SWOT analysis.

Step 7: Define performance and outcome metrics

Metrics for the evaluation of the CBM have been identified and selected by the LLs following the AF of **D6.3**, as part of the work to be developed in WP4, **T4.2**.

These have considered in further detail in D4.3 (subject to data availability) for the socio-environmental and economic assessment of the value chain according to three differentiated scenarios: baseline, circular and scaled-up.

Step 8: Development of prototypes

Modelling and prototyping of regulatory compliance have been carried out tested during the pilot phase of the solution.

4.3.3 Detail design

4.3.3.1 Experimentation

Within the framework of the project, experiments have been carried out to test different technical aspects of the proposed circular solution. These have been carried out by the Lisbon LL partners. Among them, the following have been carried out:

- T2.4.3a – Use of the innovative method for demand-driven matchmaking, which involves combining different alternative water supplies (e.g., drinking water, reclaimed water,

groundwater) with various non-potable water uses (such as garden irrigation, landscape lakes, etc.) within an urban area.

- T2.4.3b_c – Use of a user-friendly approach to human health and environmental risk assessment associated with reclaimed water use for irrigating green areas.
- T2.4.3d - Development, implementation, and calibration of a full-scale model for chlorine decay in two reclaimed water distribution systems (RWDSs) of Lisbon (Frente Ribeirinha and Alcântara WWTP internal system (TRL7), Full-scale model applied to the RWDS of Parque Tejo / Parque das Nações North

For more information about the description and results of the experiments and pilots carried out in the LL, refer to D2.17.

4.3.3.2 Detail design

A detailed design of the CBM is still to be carried out. The innovation process is at this current stage.

4.3.3.3 Pilot

The Lisbon LL solutions for promoting water reuse in non-potable uses, such as the irrigation were tested in several green areas of the city. For more information about the description and results of the experiments and pilots carried out in the LL, refer to **D2.17**.

4.4 East Frisia

4.4.1 Framing and scoping

Framing LL (Macro level context):

LL regional context:

The LL East Frisia is located in the OOWV supply area in the North-West of Lower Saxony close to the North Sea and the Dutch border. The region has growing population and a successful economy dominated by the agricultural, industrial, and service sectors.

LL problem-owner:

The OOWV is a body governed by public law and the largest water provider in Lower Saxony and one of the biggest water providers and waste treatment organisations in Germany in terms of area (7.525 km²). Drinking water is delivered to around 1 Mil. people. With 44 sewage treatment plants, it treats wastewater for around 500.000 people which is around 34 Mio. m³ of sewage per year.

As a customer-oriented, efficient, and competent service supply company since 1948 the OOWV is firmly anchored in the region and ensures the responsible supply with drinking water as well as the environmentally friendly sewage disposal for fair prices and with high quality awareness. According to its statute the OOWV is working without the intention of making a profit. All surpluses are invested in the optimisation of operating, management, and technical equipment.

Groundwater is the main source for drinking water in the OOWV provision area. Thus, the OOWV is highly committed to protecting groundwater and has got decades of experience in monitoring and modelling groundwater as well as in protecting groundwater.

LL problem-owner challenges (OOWV):

- **Increasing Water Demand:** The water demand in the OOWV supply area has been rising constantly over the past years. The demand is already at a level projected for the end of the decade, requiring the OOWV to significantly expand its infrastructure, intelligently distribute water quantities, advance alternative concepts like the treatment of process water for industrial use, secure and possibly expand its water rights to accommodate further economic growth and new residential and commercial areas.
- **Investment Needs:** Since its establishment, OOWV has constantly invested in its infrastructure. However, without additional investments and necessary capital, the association cannot meet the diverse challenges of the coming years. OOWV must take numerous measures to provide the required water quantities, ensure proper disposal, and leave future generations with a sustainable supply infrastructure.
- **Competing Uses:** OOWV currently treats drinking water exclusively from groundwater, securing public water supply. However, other user groups, including households, industries, and agricultural businesses, also extract groundwater. With climate change leading to increased water demand, particularly for field irrigation, there is a need for enhanced collaboration and prioritization of essential services, requiring support from society and politics.
- **Complex Procedures:** OOWV's water rights are largely exhausted, and the increasing water demand presents a challenge. The ongoing climate change emphasizes the urgency of the situation. However, processes to increase water rights have proven to be complex and lengthy due to extensive environmental regulations at the EU, federal, and state levels.
- **Climate Change:** The impacts of climate change, such as prolonged droughts, more heat days, and floods from heavy rainfall, are evident. Prolonged droughts and increased heat days have disproportionately elevated drinking water demand. OOWV collaborates with municipalities and other stakeholders to ensure a secure supply during extreme weather conditions. Additionally, more frequent heavy rainfall events pose a challenge, requiring joint efforts by OOWV and municipalities.
- **Pollutant Entry:** OOWV aims for high groundwater quality but faces challenges, including nitrate pollution in its jurisdiction. Residues from pesticides are increasingly found in samples. OOWV has been working for years to prevent the entry of these undesired substances into water bodies and groundwater, consistently investing in measures to proactively protect groundwater in the region.

LL Vision:

Essential element of the long-term vision for East Frisia is the sustainable management of the available water resources. Water should be available to all actors in the region (population, industry, agriculture, ecosystems) in the required quantity and quality. In order to ensure this in the long term, the development of alternative resources in addition to currently used ground water resources will become increasingly important.

LL partners:

The East Frisia LL partners:

1. Oldenburgische-Ostfriesische Wasserverband (OOWV): LL-problem owner.
2. IWW Water Centre: LL-mentor.

3. DMK Deutsches Milchkontor GmbH (DMK): LL Partner.
4. Envirochemie GmbH: LL Partner.

A description of OOWV has already been carried out above. Below, a summary of the partners' organizations is presented:

IWW Water Centre is one of the leading water research institutes in Germany and a prominent member of the international research community. In its research branch, IWW is a private, not-for-profit company affiliated with the University of Duisburg-Essen. Founded in 1986, IWW presently employs more than 100 full-time employees at three locations with the headquarter in Mülheim an der Ruhr (Germany). The shareholders of IWW are mainly from the water-supply and wastewater industry.

DMK Group, Germany's largest dairy cooperative, processes 5.5 billion kilograms of milk annually, making it a key supplier to the German retail grocery trade. Renowned for its commitment to quality, diversity, and innovation, DMK's product range spans cheese, fresh dairy products, baby food, ice cream, and industrial ingredients. Recognizable brands like MILRAM, Oldenburger, and Humana enjoy success in Europe and global markets. With over 4,700 dairy farmers and 6,600 employees across 20+ sites, DMK Group achieves an impressive 5.5 billion euros in turnover. The company's vision extends to 2030, emphasizing consumer-centric, natural milk products, and a holistic sustainability strategy that addresses social issues. As a traditional cooperative, DMK fosters a strong community ethos, ensuring excellence from farm to table.

EnviroChemie, is a leading provider of sustainable system solutions for industrial water treatment and the treatment of process water, circulation water, cooling water, boiler water, and wastewater. The company, a specialist according to §62 WHG (German Water Resources Act), is known for its proactive response to client needs, delivering quality plant solutions and services through experienced and highly qualified experts. EnviroChemie focuses on innovation, employing groundbreaking technologies and regularly participating in national and international research projects to develop forward-looking solutions. The company is recognised for its commitment to quality, holding certifications for environmental management, energy management, occupational health and safety, and a certified quality management system. As part of the EnviroWater Group, the company collaborates within a network of experts dedicated to sustainable water preparation and treatment.

Key dependencies, risks, and opportunities:

- Groundwater abstraction
 - Risk: Rising demand in the supply system
 - Opportunity: Use of alternative water sources and apply reuse concepts.
- Technology
 - Risk: ineffective technology for specific uses.
 - Opportunity: efficient and adaptive technology.
- Infrastructure
 - Risk: inefficient infrastructure, not leveraging potential of resource recovery, reuse of wastewater, and optimising operations and energy consumption.
 - Opportunity: Adaptive infrastructure (decentralized waterworks, reclaimed water facilities, reclaimed water distribution networks)
- Complex bureaucracy procedures (water permits and authorisation)
 - Risk: not adapting quickly enough to the current challenges
 - Opportunity: develop more effective procedures

- Regulatory frameworks
 - Risk: barriers to the adoption of circular practices, limiting reuse applications alternative water sources and the development of new business models.
 - Opportunity: new governance models in the water management, new enabling policy and regulation that incentivizes the adoption of water solutions.

Future dependencies:

The implementation of the energy transition will pose additional challenges for water supply and wastewater disposal. Especially to produce green hydrogen, but also for battery production, the LNG industry and the resulting peripheral industries, high water requirements are expected in northern Germany. According to the Lower Saxony Hydrogen Network, for example, there is a demand for 18 TWh of hydrogen for the 2030 scenario, corresponding to 13 GW of installed electrolysis capacity in Lower Saxony. These required water quantities can probably not be provided from the central drinking water supply. Therefore, all alternative local water resources for water supply have to be considered. These include decentralised groundwater, rainwater, surface water, municipal and industrial wastewater, and seawater. As far as possible, the use of groundwater resources should be avoided in order to ensure the long-term availability of public services for the population. Seasonal availability and quality must also be considered.

Barriers and Drivers (Macro level):

Internal drivers:

- Ensuring a sustainable drinking water supply for the region.
- Save drinking water resources for future generations.

External Drivers:

- Growing water demand (sectors households, industry, agriculture).
- Environmental benefits for the customers and the region.
- Support from stakeholders and public.
- Risks of climate change.

Internal Barriers:

- Lack of resources and experience
- High costs for investment.
- New operating models need to be developed (technology and service).

External Barriers:

- Not enough experience with applying of reuse regulations.
- High costs of investment.

Scoping LL circular solutions (Meso and Micro Level)

Scoping, site location and state of the art description:

In the previous section, we detailed the system at a regional level to put current challenges into context and to address the full range of opportunities. However, it is necessary to narrow down the system to

be analysed in the LL of East Frisia in the B-Water Smart project, according to the opportunities identified (refer to Table 11).

Table 11 East Frisia LL circularities and baseline business model (adapted from: D4.3).

Circularity ID	Circularity identified	Description	Baseline BM ¹	Innovation type ²
C12	Process water to Reclaimed water	Increase water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate (cow water)	LBM	BMI
C13	Alternative water resources to Reclaimed water	Municipal/Industrial/Urban wastewater to reclaimed water	-	-

¹Baseline Business Model (Circular Business Model, Linear Business Model, New Business Model);² Innovation type: Business Model Innovation or Business process

One of the issues that has been highlighted in the region is the increasing demand for water by industries. Therefore, these industries are ideal candidates to collaborate in innovation projects in the water management. The case study (C12) focuses to increase water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate (cow water). The milk/whey permeate is already partly used within DMK for cooling processes or as pre-cleaning water. In addition, the extended internal use of milk/whey permeate holds potential. Therefore, C12 is the focus of the following assessment and C13 is not further elaborated.

Currently, OOWV supplies freshwater to DMK which is used to produce dairy products and other in-house processes (e.g. cleaning). During the production of dairy products, cow water is generated in the internal process and reused in certain activities. The current amount of cow water reused at the analysed dairy is 350.000 m³; which amounts to 43.75 % of the potential cow water that can be reused.

The proposed circular solution (C12) is to increase the water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of cow water. The expected volume of cow water to be reused has been estimated at approximately 800,000 m³/year, which means an estimated volume of 450,000 m³/year of cow water to be reused in addition to the existing circularity. It is planned to use this to expand production in the future.

The aim of the project is twofold: on the one hand, to carry out demonstrative tests of the techno-economic viability and environmental impacts; on the other hand, to be able to promote a regulatory change that enables the adoption and scaling up of this solution.

If the results are positive, replicability in other dairies or industries in the area will be assessed.

Mapping the ecosystem:

The mapping of stakeholders for all the circularities carried out in the LL of Lisbon has been carried out in task T4.2. and is presented in D4.3.

4.4.2 Ideation

4.4.2.1 Idea generation

The circular opportunity C12, which is to increase water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate (cow water), was identified before the start of the project. Therefore, an ideation phase had taken place out of the project. No further ideas have been generated in the Living Lab in the scope of the B-WaterSmart Project with regards to other solutions.

The definition of C12 is the following: increase water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate (cow water). The milk/whey permeate is already partly used within DMK for cooling processes or as pre-cleaning water. In addition, the extended internal use of milk/whey permeate holds potential. C12 was selected by the Living Lab partners to elaborate the design of the business model.

As it was indicated before, the intended use of the cow water is for in-house reuse. The redistribution of water outside of the plant, to other local industries, was also considered as a potential long-term opportunity. However, as the potential avoided freshwater consumption is planned to be used to expand production, only the use for consumption at the dairy is considered in this assessment.

It should be noted that the adoption of this solution is restricted by the current regulation, which limits the use of treated process water for certain cleaning operations and does not contemplate the use application it is intended to perform, this is the last cleaning stage prior to the dairy production of products start. A pilot plant will be installed, to demonstrate that the quality of the produced water is suitable for reuse in this process, but also to optimize and increase the efficiency of recycled process water. Given the high starting quality of the process water, there is confidence that the necessary requirements can be reached for the implementation of this treatment.

The introduction of this circularity has an impact on different value chains: the production process at the dairy, the treatment of cow water and the provision of technology. The solution transforms a process in the production phase (e.g. cleaning), but it does not modify the business model of the production process, therefore, this would apply as process innovation and not of a business model innovation. The treatment of cow water with possible partners represents a new service. Hence a new business model is needed to realize this value chain, which would follow one or another business model innovation strategy depending on the organisational structure (e.g. operator model) of the scaled-up scenario. For a technology provider, the business model would continue to operate in the traditional way.

Stakeholder engagement:

Both in the ideation phase and in the monitoring of the development of the business model, it is necessary to maintain a close relationship between the different stakeholders. To this end, from the beginning of the project, Community of Practice and Focus Groups have been carried out with the stakeholders affected by the solution, in order to communicate the objectives, intentions and progress in the development of the solution, as well as to obtain feedback, etc.

During CoP1, CoP2 and CoP3 the circularity at DMK was addressed, but in general all the CoPs consider a broader scope and the general strategic agenda for the region of East Frisia.

4.4.2.2 Preliminary assessment

Qualitative and quantitative information is provided below for those aspects that have been considered in this preliminary assessment:

- **Validation of the Idea:**

The idea solves existing problems in the region and has great potential for saving groundwater. Its validation has been confirmed with the different stakeholders involved in the solution before the project, and during its development through the stakeholder participation dynamics mentioned in the previous section.

- **Market Analysis:**

The particular use to which the treated process water will be applied is not being done in other industries, so it is innovative. If it is viable, there is a potential market in other dairy industries of the Group and others in the area that could be interested in implementing the solution.

- **Revenue Model:**

Various revenue models possible; from the point of view of public water suppliers, the costs must be covered by customers.

- **Financial Viability:**

The cost-benefit analyses are yet to be detailed. For the time being, an approximate cost estimate for a scale-up scenario with a cow water production of 500.000 m³/year is shown in Table 12. Please note that additional costs (e.g. energy, chemicals) are not considered in this estimate. In terms of funding sources, external financing might be necessary.

Table 12 East Frisia LL C12 CAPEX & OPEX (€/y) scaled-up scenario.

COSTS SCALED-UP				
Category	Description	Scenario	Type	Costs
Infrastructure	Technology for treatment of cow water	Scale-up	CAPEX	€ 5.000.000,00
TOT (€)				€ 5.000.000,00
Service	Repair and maintenance	Scale-up	OPEX	€ 100.000,00
	Labor (Operator, engineer and administratio	Scale-up	OPEX	€ 33.000,00
TOT (€)				€ 133.000,00

In terms of funding sources, external financing is necessary to develop the solution. The different financing instruments will be developed in D4.5.

- **Technical feasibility:**

The technology employed in the project follows a multi-barrier treatment approach for treating cow water. Within the framework of the project, a pilot plant has been installed at the DMK plant to optimise its processes to the needs of the plant and to test the efficiency of water recovery.

- **Risks and Challenges:**

The main risks and challenges are associated with existing regulatory barriers to the application of the proposed use. There are also operational risks that will need to be assessed through the results of the pilots.

- **Equipment and Resources:**

The resource of cow water is available, and the pilot plant is in place. In a potential scale-up scenario, it would be necessary to reinvest in the dairy's infrastructure, including restructuring the water distribution system and implementing a large-scale process water recycling system. In addition, the relationship between all stakeholders is an important resource for the

realisation of process water recycling. Ongoing stakeholder management is therefore important.

4.4.2.3 Concept

Step 1: Circular strategies and cycle of operation.

Circular strategies: **Rethink, Replace, and Recycle.**

The operating cycle: **Technical cycle.**

Step 2: Business model innovation strategy.

Innovation strategy: **CBM diversification.**

The currently existing business model is linear, as it supplies drinking water for the identified cow water application. As indicated before, business model innovation is relevant from the water supplier's business perspective. The business model innovation follows a CBM diversification strategy, as the base business model is maintained, and a new one is created.

Step 3: BMI pathway and SCBM

The innovation pathway followed for the development of the business model:

Technological innovation: **Substitute with renewables and natural processes.** The primary objective behind the technological innovation is to reduce the consumption of drinking water for internal operating processes in dairy plants.

Social innovation: The social innovation introduced is **Encourage sufficiency**, as it encourages the recirculation of cow water and the reduction of drinking water consumption for industrial processes.

Organisational innovation: **Develop scale-up solutions** since the cow water is planned to use it for the expansion of production.

SCBM archetype: **Scaled-up Sufficiency.**

The East Frisia innovation pathway indicates that the archetype of Scaled-up sufficiency aligns with the LL objectives, given that it aims to use renewable sources as an opportunity to expand production. This is achieved by using cow water in circularities at dairy plants through a service (full or partial) to the stakeholders involved, while extending sustainability solutions by prioritising drinking water savings over economic returns.

For further information on the development of the innovation pathway, and the characteristics of the SCBM archetype refer to Figure 7, Figure 8 and Table 1 presented in section 3.4.3.3.

Step 4: Circular business model classification:

CBM (according to Lacy et al.): **Hybrid business model** (Resource Recovery and Circular Inputs; further business models are depending on ownership arrangements).

Refer to **Annex B**, for the classification of the remainder of CBMs linked to rest of circular solutions identified in the LL.

Step 5: Circular business model canvas

A preliminary circular business model canvas for C12 is presented in Table 13:

Table 13 East Frisia LL C12 (increase water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate) CBMC

Circular Business Model Canvas		Circularity goal and scope definition		Sustainability mission and action				
Living Lab: EAST FRISIA		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Targeted CE principle (Select one or more principle) P1) Create value from waste, P2) Maximize energy and material efficiency, P3) Substitute with renewables and natural processes CE strategies (Select one or more strategies) R1 - Rethink, R2 - Avoid, R3 - Reduce, R4 - Replace, R5 - Reuse, R6 - Recycle, R7 - Cascading, R8 - Store, R9 - Recover Operating cycle (Select business operation cycle) Technical cycle, Biological cycle Circular business model innovation strategy (Select innovation strategy) CBM transformation, CBM diversification, Circular start-up, CBM acquisition Sustainable circular innovation pathways (Select one or more) Purposeful sufficiency, Scaled-up sufficiency, Purposeful functionality, Scaled-up functionality, Purposeful stewardship, Scale-up stewardship Circular business model type (Select one or more of the targeted circular business model type) Circular supplies, Sharing platform, Product as a service, Product lifespan extension, Resource recovery 		Targeted sustainable development goal Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being , Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation , Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure , Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production , Goal 13: Climate action , Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions Goal 17: Partnership for the goals				
Legend:		Value proposition	Value Creation & Delivery	Value capture				
Key Partners	Key Activities	Ecosystem Activities	Value Proposition		Customer Segments	Targeted solution	Benefits and burden	
Dairy: - Provides water resource from process water - Provides surface area - Depending on the operator model, additional functions may be required Water supplier: - Treats & supplies water - Depending on the operator model, additional functions may be required External service provider: If necessary for planning, delivery/installation and commissioning of equipment and other during production (*) Suppliers: - for operating resources and other items during production	>Production and supply of industrial water on the basis of vapor condensate from the dairy plant >Operational excellence Operation/Optimization/Maintenance of processes >Coordination operator and end-user.	Solution & Tech providers Consultancy services. Research institutes & Universities: Technical/Managerial expertise. Dissemination of CE projects. Promote future innovation projects and collaboration opportunities. Local and regional authorities: Promote innovation projects and collaboration between sectors. Change of regulatory frameworks and incentivizing solution with green funding. Raise social awareness through campaigns and CE promotion.	For customers (dairy plants): >Provision of treated water volumes to save fresh water and maximize recirculation of resources. >Site security/location advantage >Positive marketing effects >Access to a CE network promoting innovative collaborations which can lead to new opportunities for the organizations. For stakeholders/community: >Careful handling of groundwater resources. Security of groundwater for next generations. >The reduced volumes lead to open groundwater volumes that can be used for other industries, municipalities or as an ecosystem service. For environment: >Reduction of groundwater extraction For employees: >Job security/additional jobs		Dairy industry. Other Food industries (potentially)	Treated water with Fit-for-Purpose quality	Benefits: Society: >Helping to guarantee healthy ecosystem for next generation (water security). >Freeing natural resources for other uses. Environment: - Ecosystem safeguarding by reducing stress of groundwater system. Burden: Environmental: >Trade offs with energy resources (highly consuming treatment) >Other impacts to be assessed	
	Key Resources		Channels	Need/problem/challeng				Customer Relationships
	>Production facilities >Water resource (cow water = whey condensate) >Financing >Skilled labor >Permits		>Physical channel: recirculation of recycled water through in-house pipeline network. > Water supplier internal channels: website, current customer database, etc. >Partners channels: promote circular practices through their websites, industry events, fairs, conventions. >Project channels (ecosystem network after project): CoPs, workshops, focus group sessions.	The groundwater natural system is under stress due to increasing demand of water by industries, the agriculture and effects of the climate change. Alternative water sources are needed to reduce the pressure to the natural sources and guarantee water availability for the next generations.				Long-term relationship
	Cost Structure		Revenue Streams					
The investments and operational costs structure still to be defined. Below presented available economic data: CAPEX: - Construction of the entire infrastructure (plant construction, engineering, EMSR, power construction) for treatment, storage and distribution (cost allocation depending on operator model). - Reconstruction of the process water network at dairy. Operating costs: - Energy - Operating resources - Adjustment of operation/production. - Personnel - Consulting services		Total revenues have not yet been estimated (*). Recycled process water price in the form of cost compensation in €/m³. Water supplier as a municipal company has no profit-making intention; investments, operating costs and risks have to be reimbursed by customers. This is done by e.g.: Price per m³; construction cost subsidy; bank guarantee; hedging of the contract (minimum quantities; running times)						

- Depending on the operator model, additional functions may be required

Step 6: SWOT analysis

The C7 CBM SWOT analysis is presented in Figure 18:

SWOT ANALYSIS	
INTERNAL FACTORS	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<p>Established long-term relationship between water supplier and dairy company.</p> <p>Highly skilled competences and capacities of LL stakeholders.</p> <p>Close relationship to public authorities (public water supplier and long-standing, established production site).</p> <p>Other strenghts to be evaluated according to operating model (water supplier and dairy partnership).</p>	<p>The production of treated industrial water is currently more expensive than fresh water. In the medium term, the realization of such projects remains dependent on public or other public/private financing instruments..</p> <p>Highly technical and specific process, the technology has to be adopted to transfer to other industries. Limited market expansion, but the milk and dairy industry is one of the most important employers in germany.</p> <p>Other weaknesses to be evaluated according to operating model (water supplier and dairy partnership).</p> <p>Environmental impacts to be assessed.</p>
EXTERNAL FACTORS	
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<p>Potential to replicate solutions in other dairies in the region.</p> <p>Update existent regulations and increase reuse potential of recycled process water.</p> <p>Create positive social and environmental impacts (increase awareness in the reuse of water; and reduce groundwater pressure in the region).</p> <p>Develop innovative collaborations and partnership in other sites, with new models of governance and business models which can boost local economy (according to specific context of the sites).</p> <p>Expand the development of a CE market with an innovative new solution.</p>	<p>In the medium term, relying on public or public/private financing instruments, due to high investments and operating costs.</p> <p>Current regulations are restrictive for intended reuse application.</p>

Figure 18 East Frisia LL C12 CBM SWOT analysis

Step 7: Define performance and outcome metrics.

Metrics for the evaluation of the CBM have been identified and selected by the Living Labs following the AF of D6.3. as part of the work to be developed in WP4, T4.2.

These have been considered in further detail in D4.3 (subject to data availability) for the socio-environmental and economic assessment of the value chain according to three differentiated scenarios: baseline, circular and scaled-up.

Step 8: Development of prototypes.

A pilot plant is successfully implemented at the dairy. The cow water is not integrated into the dairy's water distribution system, as this is currently not permitted. However, the quality required quality is achieved by the pilot plant. The next steps will be coordinated with the authorities and contract partners.

4.4.3 Detail design

4.4.3.1 Experimentation

Within the framework of the project, experiments have been carried out to test different technical aspects of the proposed circular solution. These have been carried out by IWW in off-site laboratory studies.

For more information about the description and results of the experiments and pilots carried out in the Living Lab, refer to D2.17.

4.4.3.2 Detail design

This is the current phase of East Frisia LL's business model innovation process. During this phase, a more detailed design covering all operational, technological, and strategic aspects of the business model is carried out.

4.4.3.3 Pilot

A pilot plant has been used on-site to evaluate the treatment of cow water. The pilot was installed at the site in Edeweicht by project partner EnviroChemie and partners in February 2022. Since then, EnviroChemie and partners have been operating the pilot plant. To improve the degradation of organic material contained in cow water, several operational optimizations were implemented. In 2023 two sampling rounds were performed to evaluate the microbiological performance.

4.5 Flanders

4.5.1 Framing and scoping of the circular solutions in the Living Lab

Framing of LL (Macro level context):

LL Challenges:

Flanders faces water challenges due to a combination of high drinking water demand because of the dense population, high irrigation water demand for agriculture, groundwater overexploitation, water quality deterioration, and water scarcity due to droughts and climate change. Transforming the regional water system from linear to fully circular, by integrating the urban and natural water cycles, is critical for securing a freshwater supply for all sectors. Especially after the droughts of the last several years (e.g., 2017-2020), there is strong interest in exploring alternative water sources and working towards a more robust, water-smart system. With climate change expected to lead to increased drought periods but also more frequent extreme rainfall events (leading to floods), the LL Flanders strategic agenda specifically looks towards mitigating the impact on drinking water production, stormwater management, and water as a resource for agriculture.

LL vision:

LL Flanders has the long-term ambition to drive a regional-scale shift towards a smart water system. In this context, it encompasses a range of circularity opportunities related to the reuse of wastewater for various purposes, the exploration of new water sources alternative to groundwater and surface water, improving water use efficiency and the development of synergies and symbiosis among different sectors to enhance wastewater reuse through decentralized systems.

LL objectives:

The strategic agenda has been developed by the LLs and the CoPs as part of the project work on WP1. A final strategic agenda will be presented on D1.4: Final strategic agenda and implementation plan for each LL, with the agreed LL vision objectives.

LL partners:

De Watergroep: is a public (municipality owned) and the largest company of drinking water in Flanders. Specializing in water supply and management services. Serving 3.3 million people in Belgium, the company is engaged in the capture, treatment, and distribution of water from various natural sources such as rivers and reservoirs. With a focus on maintaining water quality and ensuring compliance with safety standards. In the project, De Watergroep is one of the primary problem owners. The water utility will build and operate, together with Aquafin NV, a pilot system to test the possibility to upgrade alternative water sources to sufficient quality for drinking water and participate in the regional water system analysis.

City of Mechelen: is the municipal representative of the City of Mechelen (86,600 inhabitants). In the project, it facilitates demonstrations by granting access to the stormwater basin study site, installing a water distribution system for farmers, and actively contributing to the advancement of a stormwater reuse management system. Additionally, the City of Mechelen actively engages in regional water system analyses.

KWR Water Research Institute: is an independent and applied scientific research institute dedicated to water-related issues. It collaborates with various stakeholders, including water utilities, government bodies, industries, and research institutions, to address challenges related to water quality, availability, and sustainability. The institute conducts cutting-edge research, develops innovative solutions, and provides knowledge and expertise to support the water sector. In the project, KWR is the LL Mentor, and acts as a R&I provider for the LL Flanders. KWR is also involved in the development of a number of tools and studies related to water reuse.

Aquafin NV: Experts in wastewater collection and treatment, they are responsible for the financing, operation, and expansion of the wastewater treatment infrastructure in Flanders. Established as a public-private partnership, the company focuses on developing and maintaining an extensive network of sewage treatment plants, pumping stations, and sewers to ensure the effective collection and treatment of domestic and industrial wastewater. Aquafin's commitment to environmental sustainability is reflected in its efforts to enhance water quality, protect natural ecosystems, and contribute to the overall improvement of water management practices in Belgium. In the project, they are the technology providers for the initiation and operation of the pilot installations for reuse of WWTP effluent for drinking water production in Diksmuide and reuse of stormwater for irrigation in Mechelen, and for elaborating the buffer basin in Mechelen stormwater reuse management system to allow the combinatory function of flood prevention and water collection.

Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt: is a non-profit organisation, leading knowledge and innovation centre for vegetable cultivation focussing on practical and applied research. In the project, they are one of the problem owners with regards to the reuse of stormwater for agricultural water, complimentary R&I provider, modelling agricultural water demand and installing subirrigation for stormwater reuse management system. Participate in a regional water system analysis.

Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (VITO): the Flemish Institute for Technological Research is a renowned independent research organisation based in Flanders, Belgium. VITO specializes in applied research and technology development in various domains, including energy, sustainable chemistry, materials, land use, and environmental technologies. VITO collaborates with industry, government agencies, and other research institutions to address societal challenges and contribute to the transition towards a more sustainable and circular economy. In the project, their role is as a complementary R&I provider, modelling the storm water buffer system at Mechelen and the distribution of this water to farmers for the stormwater reuse management system.

VLAKWA: is an organisation in Flanders, dedicated to water-related research, knowledge dissemination, and the promotion of sustainable water management practices.

Key dependencies, risks, and opportunities:

An important risk in Flanders is the availability of water resources, in particular for the production of drinking water. This is mainly relevant for Drinking water utilities using surface water as a raw water source, such as De Watergroep.

However, due to climate change and increasing population in Flanders, the agricultural sector is also subject to an increasing need for irrigation to meet growing demand, while the availability of freshwater sources decreases. This leads to a potential risk for continued agricultural production in Flanders.

Concerning all applications involving wastewater reuse, there is an important dependency between the reuse application under investigation and the need for water from the environment at the current

discharge point from the environment. As this last aspect is often hard to identify, relevant authorities have a difficult assignment to take case-specific decisions leading to stand-still.

Initiatives set-up by governmental organizations (e.g., the Blue deal) to promote the extrapolation of water smart solutions are a big opportunity to stimulate investments for replicating all applications that are demonstrated in this project within LL Flanders. There is a risk however that the remaining challenges prevent these large-scale extrapolations in a short timeframe and the momentum will be missed. These remaining challenges were mentioned before as risks and interdependencies and mainly concern unclear business plans, interdependencies with evolving law and with environmental protection.

Barriers and drivers (Macro level):

- **Regulatory and governance challenges:** The applications concerning use of alternative water sources requires the elaboration of existing legislation, as these may influence the financing and management of such applications. There is an important interdependency between the final format of new legislations and the potential of several solutions involving alternative water sources that also respect environmental protection. Clear governance structure for stormwater management will be essential to ensure a good understanding of responsibilities among stakeholders, set priorities and clear financing arrangements to ensure long-term sustainability of stormwater management.
- **Business plan and financial uncertainty:** As there is no clear business plan around stormwater management in Flanders, there is also no defined funding or financial structure for stormwater management. This financial uncertainty may pose a barrier to sustained and effective stormwater management practices. However, effort can be put on exploring innovative financing models or alternative revenue streams to finance the operation and maintenance of stormwater management infrastructure to potentially drive the development and implementation of sustainable stormwater management practices.
- **Data and knowledge:** The scattered landscape of organizations that all have their different role, data and knowledge together with ever evolving General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) concerns may hinder the possibility to set-up the necessary data and knowledge sharing frameworks and define appropriate tasks and responsibilities among relevant stakeholders (including industries, agriculture, and local communities).

Addressing regulatory complexities, ensuring financial stability, and optimizing governance structures are crucial for overcoming barriers. Leveraging innovative financing models, fostering collaboration, and exploring alternative revenue streams are key drivers for effective stormwater management at the macro level in Flanders.

Scoping Living Lab circular solutions (Meso and Micro Level)

Scoping, site location and state of the art description:

In order to achieve the long-term objectives, innovation, and implementation of actions at a local level. For this, in the framework of B-Water Smart, projects have been defined according to two topics: the demonstration of the quality of wastewater for use as drinking water (it is demonstrative, under experimentation, it does not develop a pilot to test its use); and on the other hand, testing a synergy of reuse of stormwater stored in a water pond for flood prevention with agriculture and groundwater resilience. A pilot will be developed for the first one in Diksmuide, and for the second one in the city of Mechelen.

Table 14 Flanders LL circularities and baseline business model (adapted from: D4.3).

Circularity ID	Circularity identified	Description	Baseline BM ¹	Innovation type ²
C14	Stormwater to Reclaimed water	Stormwater reuse for subirrigation	NBM	BMI
C15	Indirect effluent to drinking water	Process water to feed drinking water treatment plants	-	-
C16	Maximization of Drinking water	Maximization of production in drinking water treatment plant	-	-

¹Baseline Business Model (Circular Business Model, Linear Business Model, New Business Model);² Innovation type: Business Model Innovation or Business process

Given the demonstrative nature of C15 and C16, which do not aim at innovating existing business models as yet in this project, this guide will be applied to solution **C14: Stormwater reuse for irrigation.**

Figure 19 Flanders LL C14 site location buffer basin and agriculture fields.

In Mechelen, most of the sewer network consists of hybrid systems - combined sewage systems (only 10% are separated sewer systems) - that do not separate wastewater from rain and stormwater. Consequently, during episodes of heavy rainfall, contamination of stormwater (Combined Sewer Overflow CSO) is common. For new urbanized or reurbanized areas, the installation of a separated sewer system is mandatory. In a separated system, the stormwater is directed to a nearby water course, which might increase the risk for flooding at that location. To prevent flooding, a buffer reservoir might be part of the storm water infrastructure. As part of the neighbourhood's reurbanization plan at the project location, a reservoir and a separated sewer system have been constructed to allow the separation of waters without the risk of contamination or flooding. To enable a circular solution (C14: stormwater reuse), the design of the basin (originally intended for construction) has been readapted to enable collection and the reuse of stormwater (e.g., for subirrigation). The anticipated outcome is the construction of a landscaped buffer basin with a capacity of 1,400 m³, collecting runoff stormwater

from roads, pavements, and roofs covering about 3 hectares upstream to prevent flooding and in the meantime enable water reuse.

The conception of this solution arises from the droughts experienced in the region in 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2022 when farmers (located near the project) were seeking alternative water sources for the irrigation of their crops. Moreover, the groundwater system is more and more under pressure due to lack of replenishment if too much storm water and drainage water is directed to the watercourse (and therefore flowing to the ocean instead of replenishing the ground water system. Proefstation, identified a synergetic opportunity between local farmers and the municipality and proposed to the City of Mechelen to adapt the solution for the reuse of the stormwater stored in the neighbouring fields.

In the original design of the basin construction, a buffer basin without a collection opportunity was planned, where water was stored and released without regulation through an outlet gate back into the natural channel. The initial investment for its construction was already considered outside the project scope, and its adaptation for circular use is part of the B-Water Smart project scope.

Regarding the current reservoir's location, it should be noted that it is not optimal (i.e., where more rainfall water would be collected). It had to be relocated during the preparation process due to the limited availability of land in the area (the neighbourhood's urban plan was made before obtaining the land), resulting in increased excavation costs and a potentially smaller storage capacity than planned.

As indicated above, in the baseline scenario, storm or rainwater is not separated for reuse. Instead, it is collected the combined sewer network, or returns to natural channels through surface runoff. On the other hand, farmers irrigate crops with groundwater and surface water, regulated by water permits issued by the government (Flemish Environment Agency) for exploitation periods.

Regarding regulation and current existing restrictions, they are outlined in deliverable D5.5. Here, it is briefly quoted:

- There is a lack of clarity regarding the definitions and regulation of rainwater, stormwater, and corresponding reuse and infiltration methods.
- Regulation does not specify responsibility for managing risks associated with adverse climatic events or funding solutions for flood prevention or resilience against droughts.
- Streamlining of regulations is desirable for infiltration methods. Currently, using stormwater for subirrigation would be considered artificial aquifer recharge, requiring the water to meet groundwater quality standards. However, passive (natural) infiltration of stormwater through the soil does not need to meet this standard.

Mapping the ecosystem:

The mapping of stakeholders for all the circularities carried out in the LL of Flanders has been carried out in task T4.2. and is presented in D4.3.

4.5.2 Ideation

4.5.2.1 Idea generation

The idea generation phase for the LL has not been carried out within the framework of the B-WaterSmart project. They were generated and proposed before the start of the project.

As indicated above, the analysis focuses on solution C14: stormwater reuse for irrigation. The following is a description of the preconceived idea, which will be developed in the concept (later in this phase) with the information available up to date.

The storm reservoir was planned to be constructed as part of the neighbourhood redevelopment plan, with the aim of preventing flooding downstream. The utilisation of the stored water, and adaptation of the required reservoir design, is the subject of the study.

Direct use application of the stored rainwater to the crops were initially foreseen, however the storage capacity of the basin was very high and other opportunities with additional advantages were considered. For this reason, sub-irrigation was proposed as a solution to replenish the aquifer during the whole year, as long as the groundwater level allows it, maximizing the beneficial use of the available rainwater (which is of course mostly available in rainy periods, and contributing to climatic resilience by protecting the groundwater ecosystem service. This would reduce the hydric stress to the aquifers and improve the soil moisture conditions (i.e. by capillary rise) during the warm months of the year for farmers.

Therefore, the main purpose of the solution is not irrigation for agriculture as such, but the recharge of groundwater (aquifer), from which the farmers abstract groundwater for irrigation of their crops. The proposed technology is a sub-irrigation system (no drip lines), which consists of drainage pipelines, already existing in the farmers' fields, that are adapted to fulfil a recharge function (conversely to their initial use to drain water during flood events).

Thus, farmers are both end-users and enablers of the solution, by providing access to their fields for the development of an aquifer recharge solution.

Stakeholder engagement:

During the project, various stakeholder engagement dynamics were applied including CoPs, focus group sessions and internal meetings to share and debate the solutions with the different stakeholder groups involved.

These have fulfilled different objectives, one of which was the development of the LL's strategic plan. During the CoP meeting of 23 November 2023, ideas have been proposed to develop the business model and the responsibilities for the C14 stormwater solution, given the uncertainties regarding financing, revenue models and organizational models to achieve sustainability of the project. Investment costs can be covered within existing and potentially future governmental funding initiatives. However, to be sustainable, the operational costs of the solution should be covered by a stand-alone business model.

The following are some of the ideas that have been put forward, as well as discarded, for possible sources of funding and governance:

- Co-operation with industry (mobilising private funds) as core funding is the most obvious option. In fact, there are two industrial zones close to the project location (Mechelen-Zuid and Mechelen-Noord). There is interest in mobilising private resources from these industrial zones to finance the operational costs in exchange for visibility for the company in the buffer basin or for compensating their own unmet obligations concerning infiltration.
- For management, the role of a cooperative was discarded given the small scale of the case and the costs related to setting up a cooperative. already existing local organisations (possibly

in cooperation with the municipality) were considered - neighbourhood committee, rural guild, nature associations, etc. However, an integrated water company was suggested as the way forward. Such an integrated water company does not exist yet as today the landscape of water companies is scattered. This was also identified as an important barrier in the LL of Flanders.

- External groundwater balance: the polluter pays. It was initially thought that, at the domestic level, newly constructed pavements upstream would contribute to the downstream solution. However, current regulations appear to be sufficiently oriented towards reuse and infiltration of stormwater on-site. Therefore, it was proposed to examine the existing pavements. Different solutions were suggested here: taxation, compensation fund or cadastral rent adjustment (integration paving). A barrier for this financing source is that an important part of pavements consists of public roads, redirecting the costs to the municipality.
- Groundwater permit linked to groundwater recharge efforts. The principle is simple: when water is replenished in an aquifer, there is also a right to re-abstract water in the same aquifer. However, the relationship between the volume infiltrated and what can be extracted afterwards is not clear and is a complex solution.
- Involve agriculture in the revenue model. In the case of Mechelen, agriculture is seen as the solution (as noted before), as they make their plots of land available to replenish the groundwater system. Originally the principle that they should cover certain costs for the volume of infiltrated water was dismissed out of hand. It can be considered that agriculture contributes to the revenue model. However, one must be aware that the availability of water cannot always be guaranteed during hot periods. This is because the buffer basin does not act as a classic reservoir but as a temporary storage that is significantly filled during more intense rainfall and from which water can be infiltrated at that time. Therefore, the willingness to pay for water will be rather low.
- Alternative use of infrastructure or environment. Coupling to a car charging point was considered. Also, other options such as heat exchange, although it was not known whether this route was possible. Various forms of leisure were also cited, such as the development of urban gardens, the most prominent being CSA (Community Supported Agriculture).

4.5.2.2 Preliminary assessment

The following information concerning the preliminary assessment is presented below:

- **Validation of the Idea:**
The solution helps to solve the existing problem of the hydric stress of groundwater ecosystems and the use of alternative water sources. For the farmers, the solution does not directly solve their problems or needs - an alternative water source for irrigation in case of periods of drought - but indirectly benefits them by improving the conditions of the crops. However, farmers are seen more as a solution to the problem.
- **Market Analysis:**
There is no information on whether a market study has been carried out. Although given the main function of the reservoir development this might not be relevant.
- **Revenue Model:**
The ideation of revenue models has been developed ex-post and is currently undergoing.
- **Financial Feasibility:**
The available CAPEX and OPEX costs are detailed below:
CAPEX for the buffer basin. The budget price was 673.000 €. The actual contract price 982.000 €. 70 % of this price gap was caused by the increasing cost of the groundwork. 200.000 Euro are costs assigned to the adaptation of the basin to make it circular.

The subirrigation system costs amount to 5.000€/ha of field. Solution can cover up to 8ha, amounting to total costs of 40.000€

The estimated OPEX is 15,000 Euro excluding VAT/year.

- **Technical Feasibility:**

The technical feasibility of the sub-irrigation solution has been tested and demonstrated through experimentation within the framework of the project (refer to Experimentation phase). The technical feasibility of the stormwater management control system to combine the buffer function and the collection function in one basin was demonstrated within the framework of the project first in a cloud-based environment and later in a small-scale pilot environment.

All subparts of the complete solution (stormwater management control system, subirrigation system, subirrigation control system, treatment system, etc.) will be integrated in the final full-scale design and their interoperability will be demonstrated during this last part of the project.

Risks and Challenges:

The risks and challenges identified are regulatory and economic. The former are associated with stormwater quality regulation (for more information refer to D5.5.) and the latter with uncertainty about possible revenue models to make it profitable and ensure long-term sustainability.

There are also organisational risks, related to the operating model, responsibility, and roles of the solution by the LL partners beyond the B-Water Smart project.

- **Equipment and Resources:**

For this solution, the basin was preconceived as part of the redevelopment plan, so the bulk of the infrastructure was available.

The LL partners have extensive experience and expertise in the development of circular solutions in the water sector. Additionally, the LL counts with the support of the public authorities to promote the amendment of policy and regulations concerning the reuse of stormwater and also promote financing instruments. Furthermore, the organisation of the LL is such that it promotes close participation and collaboration with farmers and other relevant stakeholders in the solution.

4.5.2.3 Concept

The information available to date on the CBM associated with C14 is presented below.

Step 1: Circular strategies and cycle of operation.

Circular strategies: **Rethink, Reuse and Store.**

The operating cycle: **Technical cycle.**

Step 2: Business model innovation strategy.

There is no baseline business model. In the absence of further information on the management of the operation, responsibilities, and roles of the organisation, it will be considered as the development of a new CBM out of an existing organisation. The ideas of stakeholders are involved in business model development through the CoP in November 2023.

Innovation strategy: **CBM Circular start-up.**

Step 3: BMI pathway and SCBM

The innovation pathway followed for the development of the business model:

Technological innovation: **Maximise material and energy efficiency.**

Social innovation: Social innovation is driven towards the creation of a collaborative business model, thus aligning with the **Adopt a stewardship role-**

Organisational innovation: **Repurpose for society and the environment** since its primary task is to deliver environmental and social benefits.

SCBM archetype: **Purposeful stewardship.**

The Flanders innovation pathway indicates that the archetype of Purposeful stewardship aligns with the LL objectives, given that it aims to Maximize material and energy efficiency. This is achieved by storing stormwater that can be reused to replenish aquifers that serve as an ecosystem service (provision of groundwater), through a partnership between public authorities, water companies and the agricultural sector, while extending sustainability solutions by prioritising environmental and social gains over economic returns.

For further information on the development of the innovation pathway, and the characteristics of the SCBM archetype refer to Figure 7, Figure 8 and Table 1 presented in section 3.4.3.3.

Step 4: Circular business model classification

CBM (according to Lacy et al.): **Circular inputs.**

The sub-typology can be defined as **Biomimicry**, as by means of methods that replicate nature, it is possible to generate a circular input by filling the water reservoirs from which farmers draw water for irrigation.

Step 5: Circular Business Model Canvas

A preliminary circular business model canvas for C14 is presented in Table 15:

Table 15 Flanders LL C14 (Stormwater reuse for irrigation) CBMC

Circular Business Model Canvas		Circularity goal and scope definition		Sustainability mission and action		
<p>Living Lab: FLANDERS case reuse stormwater</p> <p>Legend: Value proposition Value Creation & Delivery Value capture</p>		<p>Targeted CE principle (Select one or more principle)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> P1) Create value from waste, P2) Maximize energy and material efficiency, P3) Substitute with renewables and natural processes <p>CE strategies (Select one or more strategies)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> R1 - Rethink, R2 - Avoid, R3 - Reduce, R4-Replace, R5 - Reuse, R6- Recycle, R7 - Cascading, R8 - Store, R9 - Recover Operating cycle (Select business operation cycle) Technical cycle, Biological cycle Circular business model innovation strategy (Select innovation strategy) CBM transformation, CBM diversification, Circular start-up, CBM acquisition Sustainable circular innovation pathways (Select one or more) Purposeful sufficiency, Scaled-up sufficiency, Purposeful functionality, Scaled-up functionality, Purposeful stewardship, Scale-up stewardship Circular business model type (Select one or more of the targeted circular business model type) Circular inputs, Sharing platform, Product as a service, Product lifespan extension, Resource recovery 		<p>Targeted sustainable development goal</p> <p>Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions Goal 17: Partnership for the goals</p>		
Key Partners	Key Activities	Ecosystem Activities	Value Proposition	Customer Segments	Targeted solution	Benefits and burden
<p>>City of Mechelen: Responsible of sewerage and stormwater management system.</p> <p>>Water companies: Aquafin - Technology provider and operator of pilot buffer basin B-water smart Pidpa - Operates and owns buffer basin after B-water smart</p> <p>>Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt: Problem-owner manages and coordinates the relationship with the farmers. R&I provider of stormwater subirrigation systems.</p> <p>>Farmers: Collaborators in the solution by providing land for implementation of subirrigation system. Act as enablers of the solution.</p>	<p>>Coordination and management of the solution (network management: water company, farmers, communities).</p> <p>>Monitoring and operation of buffer basin</p> <p>>Monitoring and operation of the infiltration process</p> <p>>Maintenance and repair of basin and distribution systems.</p>	<p>>City of Mechelen and other public authorities: amending policy and regulations, issue of water permits to farmers and other licenses, promotes sustainable infrastructure projects and collaboration among different collectives.</p> <p>>Ecosystem services: provisioning of groundwater for irrigation.</p> <p>>R&I Institutes (KWR, VITO, Proefstation): research support in the technical solution. Also assisting in the development of CoPs to engage the stakeholder network (during B-Water smart).</p>	<p>><i>To farmers</i>: Increasing water security of farmers during dry months or drought events by recharging the groundwater system with stormwater. Installing a sub-irrigation system to perform the infiltration of water, while increasing the soil moisture of their crops by capilarity.</p> <p>><i>To stakeholders</i>: <i>All</i>: development of a collaborative circular and sustainable solution that promotes benefits for the community and the environment.</p> <p><i>City of Mechelen</i>: Improves the stormwater management system at the city. Attends the needs and demands of the agricultural sector and the community. Increases the city resilience and reputation by promoting blue infrastructure and circular solutions. Promotes awareness and educates the community, to safeguard ecosystems, make a conscious use of water resources etc.</p> <p><i>Water companies</i>: increase of expertise and knowledge in acquifer recharge projects. Opportunity to diversify their services, by testing new</p>	<p>>Farmers >Environment >Citizens (*)</p>	<p>>Farmers > installation of sub-irrigation system for stormwater infiltration and increasing soil conditions.</p> <p>>Environment > Acquifer recharge</p> <p>>Extended function of stormwater basin (* not defined yet)</p> <p>>Protection against flooding</p>	<p>Benefits:</p> <p><i>Environmental</i>: >Increased resilience to climate change by safeguarding the ecosystem. >Improving material and resources efficiency, by storing water that can be transferred to the acquifer (replenishment of groundwater) to improve ecosystem service,</p> <p><i>Society</i>: >Flood prevention by improving stormwater management system at a local level.</p> <p>>Increase awareness among the population regarding environmental protection and resource reuse..</p> <p>Burden:</p> <p>> need for Structure for cooperation after project end</p> <p>>need for financing mechanisms after projet end</p>
	Key Resources		Channels	Need/problem/challeng	Customer Relationships	
	<p>>Stormwater >Agriculture >Water infiltration on farmland >Permits and licences >Double sewage system >Buffer basin >Distribution system (Subirrigation system) >Skilled workforce >Digital tools (monitoring and operation of system)</p>		<p>>Physical- Delivery of stormwater to farmer lands by pipelines. >Proefstation established relationship with farmers. >Project channels (B-Water smart or others): Workshops, CoP, Focus Groups etc. >Public authorities channels: increasing society environmental awareness (e.g. educational campaigns)</p>	<p>Improving resilience against climate change and efficiency of water systems while protecting natural ecosystems.</p>	<p>Farmers > Long-term relationship. Co-creators of solution.</p>	
		Cost Structure		Revenue Streams		
		<p>CAPEX: soil, buffer basin construction and adaptation (980,000€), distribution system and installation of irrigation system (5,000€ per ha, 40,000€ pilot), pilot plant (60,000€).</p> <p>*OPEX still under evaluation. OPEX: monitoring, operating basin and distribution network, pumps, maintenance and repair, labor, utilities, other materials e.g. chemicals. Estimated costs: 15,000€/y</p>		<p>*The revenue streams, are not defined and are still under discussion and require further evaluation. The next have been considered up to date:</p> <p>>Public funds (related to improvement of ecosystem services). >Private funds from local industries. >Alternative uses of infrastructure (e.g. urban gardens, energy charging points).</p>		

Value Proposition
<p>> <i>To farmers:</i> Increasing water security of farmers during dry months or drought events by recharging the groundwater system with stormwater. Installing a sub-irrigation system to perform the infiltration of water, while increasing the soil moisture of their crops by capilarity.</p> <p>> <i>To stakeholders:</i> <i>All:</i> development of a collaborative circular and sustainable solution that promotes benefits for the community and the environment.</p> <p><i>City of Mechelen:</i> Improves the stormwater management system at the city. Attends the needs and demands of the agricultural sector and the community. Increases the city resilience and reputation by promoting blue infrastructure and circular solutions. Promotes awareness and educates the community, to safeguard ecosystems, make a conscious use of water resources etc.</p> <p><i>Water companies:</i> increase of expertise and knowledge in acquifer recharge projects. Opportunity to diversify their services, by testing new technologies, creating new partnerships and expanding local circular networks.</p> <p><i>R&I providers:</i> increased knowledge on acquifer recharge projects, testing new technologies, strenghtening customer relationships (e.g. Proefstation)</p> <p><i>Community:</i> Flood prevention. Increases resilience of ecosystem services. Promotes good health and wellbeing by increasing blue and green city areas.</p> <p><i>Environment:</i> Resilience against climate change by minimizing the impact on natural resources.</p>

Figure 20 Flanders LL C14 Value proposition from Table 15

Step 6: SWOT Analysis:

The C14 CBM SWOT analysis is presented in Figure 21:

SWOT ANALYSIS	
INTERNAL FACTORS	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<p>Multidisciplinary collective of stakeholders (public authorities, technology and solution providers, water utilities, communities). Promotes development of a collaborative project.</p> <p>Alignment of vision and regional objectives among stakeholders</p> <p>Reduced CAPEX (infrastructure) as part of a redevelopment plan</p> <p>Environmental benefits. Increases resilience of natural resources and promotes city blue/green infrastructure.</p>	<p>Unclear governance structure after B-Water Smart</p> <p>Revenue streams limited due to not addressing particularly customer needs (e.g. farmers).</p> <p>Difficult to quantify impacts of solution to acquifer recharge.</p> <p>Unclear scope and missing efforts in ideation phase of solution (whose needs is the solution addressing?)</p> <p>Missing preliminary assessments.</p> <p>Basin location not optimal (for max efficiency of water collection) due to limited ground availability. Also, volumes of water stored restrict application use.</p>
EXTERNAL FACTORS	
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<p>Provide alternative uses to site location to guarantee sustainable revenue streams.</p> <p>Improving regulations in the management of stormwater and rainwater, to clarify responsibilities and also environmental regulations on the reuse applications.</p> <p>Raise environmental awareness of society and promote CE solutions.</p> <p>Alternative financing instruments from local private sector looking to improve their sustainable practices in the local area.</p>	<p>Regulations, high requirements of water quality for intended use.</p> <p>No public financing instruments assigned to solutions that improve ecosystem services.</p> <p>Regulations are unclear in the assignment of responsibilities in the management of stormwater</p>

Figure 21 Flanders LL C14 CBM SWOT analysis.

Step 7: Define performance and outcome metrics.

Metrics for the evaluation of the CBM have been identified and selected by the LLs following the AF of D6.3. as part of the work to be developed in WP4, Task 4.2.

These have considered in further detail in D4.3 for the socio-environmental and economic assessment of the value chain according to three differentiated scenarios: baseline, circular and scaled-up.

4.5.3 Detail design

4.5.3.1 Experimenting

During the project, several experiments have been carried out in collaboration with farmers to test the technology and study the impact of the solution (recharge levels, crop improvement on sub-irrigated land).

For more information on the experiments conducted and results, see D2.17 which provides a synthesis of the studies carried out.

4.5.3.2 Detail design

This phase has not yet been carried out.

4.5.3.3 Pilot

The project pilot is being implemented on 2 farmers' fields.

For more information about the description and results of the experiments and pilots carried out in the LL, see deliverable D2.17.

4.6 Venice

4.6.1 Framing and scoping of the circular solutions in the Living Lab

Framing LL (Macro level context):

LL challenges

The key challenge of the Venice LL is to create the conditions for unlocking important untapped reuse potentials in the water sector, crucial for a region highly populated, with intense touristic, industrial, and agricultural activities, in a territory with wide sensitive areas. The intensification of extreme weather phenomena (heat waves, little rainfall, and droughts) made the need to address this challenge even more urgent (e.g. in 2022 the region experienced a prolonged water shortage, leading to the declaration of a state of crisis by the regional government and a subsequent state of emergency by the national government).

Beyond the identification of innovative technologies, the Venice LL recognizes the challenge of creating an enabling context for their deployment. The focus is on establishing a virtual environment where risks associated with reuse/recovery are objectively identified and solutions are mediated through discussions involving all key stakeholders in the supply chain. This strategic approach minimizes the risk of potential penalizations, safeguarding the realization of reuse goals and ensuring the long-term success of the technologies implemented.

LL problem-owner

Veritas Group is a leading multi-utility mainly operating in the Veneto Region and among the principal national players both in the Waste and the Water industry.

In terms of integrated water services, Veritas operates in 29 municipalities in the metropolitan area of Venice and 7 in the province of Treviso, serving approximately 800,000 citizens. It also manages the industrial aqueduct of Porto Marghera. The activities carried out through the service are Aqueduct (collection, supply, lifting, purification, and distribution of water for civil use), sewerage (collection and conveyance of wastewater) and water treatment (treatment of wastewater and return of purified water to the environment).

LL vision:

The long-term vision of water smartness for LL Venice in 50 years corresponds to have significantly contributed to transforming the current linear vision of production and consumption towards smart and circular patterns of resources utilisation and the bioeconomy. Pursuing the vision entails raising awareness of the strategic society actors who in turn can change the vision of society through new regulations and correct media information spreading; base to design fair policies in the field. Achieving these goals means to individuate new technologies and solutions but even and especially provide a new scientific vision to allocate them in a functioning circle while defeating misinformation, often the main leverage for building barriers.

LL objectives:

The strategic objectives for the LL were developed by the LL in Task 1.4 and with the input of the CoPs, as part of the project work carried out in WP1. A final strategic agenda will be presented on

D1.4 - Final strategic agenda and implementation plan for each LL, with the agreed LL vision and objectives.

LL partners:

Veritas (VERI) is the LL site/problem owner and will coordinate and manage the actions of the LL Venice.

Engineering is an IT company. Will be the main ICT partner supporting the Venice case study, for the development of the Water Reuse Strategic Platform and the Sludge Management Platform.

Energia Territorio Risorse Ambientali (ETRA): Public multiutility responsible for Integrated Water Services and waste management for a territory of 61 municipalities and 600.000 inhabitants. Is a problem-owner in the project and will be involved mainly in action for sludge evaluation system development and nutrient recovery goals.

Hydrotech Engineering (HYDR) is a SME technology provider that will be specifically involved in the treatment implementation for wastewater industrial reuse.

Depuracque Servizi (DEPU) is a technology provider involved in the nutrient recovery goals. SINTEF is the R&I provider and the main scientific partner supporting the case owner Veritas.

Key dependencies, risks, and opportunities:

- Freshwater resource
 - Risks: reduction of freshwater availability due to drought episodes.
 - Opportunities: Implementation of treated wastewater direct reuse for different purposes (e.g. irrigation, industrial etc.); implementation of stakeholder coordination strategies to prioritize uses; implementation of new technologies to treat sea water.
- Infrastructure
 - Risks: lack of exploitation of exiting infrastructures enabling resources reuse.
 - Opportunity: existing infrastructures completion and new infrastructure implementation to enable the exploitation of reuse potential
- Technology:
 - Risks: Reclamation treatment chains absent or not totally adequate to meet industrial and agricultural requirements for water reuse; WWTPs designed for nutrient reductions and not for their recovery
 - Opportunities: implementations of specific technologies for water industrial reuse and for N recovery from WWTPs.
- Regulatory framework
 - Risk: persistence of regulatory inconsistency and absence of incentives that encourage the investments for resource valorisation and circular solutions adoptions
 - Opportunities: new governance model (also fostered trough B-WaterSmart CoP) and Decision Support System for sharing knowledge on real risk and opportunity, can avoid precautionary approaches and promote fair and coordinated regulations that enable and foster RR-CE paths.
- Market and business model
 - Risk: low cost of freshwater; existing private companies managing industrial water supply from freshwater;

- Opportunities: co-creation (fostered also through B-WaterSmart CoP) of new CBM for water reuse; demonstration of N-recovered salt process and quality, to create business possibilities also by changing the regulation ambit (not waste but by-product)

Barriers and drivers (Macro level)

Drivers (internal/external):

- Willingness to build consistency with the principles of the circular economy and climate change policies, also for environmental benefits and positive public image.
- Shared need among stakeholders of awareness and objective knowledge on opportunities to support rational long-term planning.
- CoP willingness/availability to create a habit of competencies sharing for decision-making processes.

Barriers (internal/external):

- Complexity of the regulatory system and the variety of subjects involved which should coordinate among each other.
- Lack of transparency and access to knowledge on the actual risk associated with valorisation and reuse, especially for some resources (such as sludge).
- Long-term planning and immediate needs difficult to reconcile.
- Economical convenience (in a broad sense and for several factors, such as the low costs of conventional water use)
- Infrastructure investments possible to be defined only when national regulation for water agricultural reuse will be clear (roles, responsibility, and costs)
- Business model to be defined for each recovered product.

Scoping LL circular solutions (Meso and Micro Level)

Scoping, site location and state of the art description:

The different projects been carried out in B-Water Smart and their different scales of action are presented as follows:

- Demonstration of a compact combinatory treatment technologies for *industrial water reuse* for urban effluents (Municipal level)
- Developing two informatic tools, the *Water Reuse Strategic Platform* (#16) and the *Sludge Management Platform* (#19): comprehensive integrated evaluation support systems to assess the best reuse opportunities and valorization pathways, fostering RR-CE practices for water and sludge respectively (from local/Regional scale transferable at National/EU scale).
- Testing technologies for *N-recovery from concentrated effluents* at two WWTPs (Regional level).

As can be seen from the different scale of action of the solutions, and the objectives of the LL, enabling the environment is a priority to drive the development of the circular economy.

However, for the analysis of circular value chains and CBMs, it is necessary to narrow the scope to the circular solutions that are being tested at Micro and Meso scale in the LL (refer to Table 28). The technologies enabling these solutions are being tested in a Veritas WWTP (Fusina) and in an Etra WWTP and aim to demonstrate the technical and environmental feasibility that, together with the other

(also non-circular) solutions, will promote regulatory changes, as well as the development of a network of actors, that incentivise the adoption of these for the creation of sustainable new products (i.e. reused water and ammonia) and services. Strategic informatic tools are being developed at regional scale, by involving all key stakeholders and their expertise, to individuate critical points and mediate solutions, with the scope of ordering and standardizing the feasibility evaluations of water reuse and sludge valorization over the regional territory.

Table 16 Venice LL circularities and baseline business model (adapted from: D4.3).

Circularity ID	Circularity identified	Description	Baseline BM ¹	Innovation type ²
C9	Wastewater to reclaimed water	Increase of industrial and agricultural water reuse	LBM	BMI
C10	Wastewater to raw materials	Nutrient recovery: Ammonia recovery (ammonium salts production)	Mainly LBM, partially CBM (no direct revenue)	BMI
C11	Wastewater sludge valorization	Exploit all potential of sludge valorization	LBM-CBM	BMI

¹Baseline Business Model (Circular Business Model, Linear Business Model, New Business Model);² Innovation type: Business Model Innovation or Business process.

The following sections focus on the circularity named C9 by considering the industrial reuse: more specifically it is the increasing of industrial reuse by acting on the urban reclaimed water reuse at the Fusina WWTP (Veritas), at municipal scale; at this scale in fact, there is a synergy possibility between local industries and the utility that can facilitate its implementation.

The WWTP was upgraded by an integrated management plan (PIF - Fusina Integrated Project) to protect the Venice lagoon, by implementing a separate industrial treatment chain (out of the scope of this project) and a reclamation treatment line (such as filtrations, disinfections, wetland.) for urban WWTP effluent, to produce treated water for non-potable reuse. From its preconception this line was designed to create a symbiosis with the neighbouring industries, by treating urban wastewater to recycle it also in industrial processes.

At present the plant produces an effluent of 40 Mm³/year through Canvas Filtration and UV disinfection treatment which is mainly pumped through pipelines to 15 km away from the protected area and discharged into the sea.

In terms of equipment, the plant has an effluent treatment unit, and the industrial zone is partially enabled with a pipeline network for the distribution of reclaimed water to different industries in the area.

It should be emphasised that in addition to industrial use, as a result of the climatic crises that have beset the region in recent years and taking into account the recent revision of the regulation for agricultural use, opportunities evaluations and projects are on the table to allow the direct/indirect agricultural reuse of this and other regional WWTPs effluents, also thanks to the strategic informatic tools (specifically the tool #16) developed by the VE-LL with an active CoP collaboration. However, this will not be analysed here.

Mapping the ecosystem:

The mapping of stakeholders for all the circularities carried out in the LL of Venice has been carried out in task T4.2. and is presented in D4.3.

4.6.2 Ideation

4.6.2.1 Idea generation

The idea generation phase for the LL has not been carried out within the framework of the BWS, as these ideas were already generated and proposed before the start of the project. No further ideas, apart from those preconceived, have been generated in the LL during the project.

Circular solutions have been presented in the previous section, and of these, C9 intended for industrial reuse has been selected for the analysis. The adoption of this solution partially transforms the linear processes of treatment and discharge of effluent into the sea that are carried out at the plant, through the implementation of a combinatory treatment technology for industrial reuse consisting of two units: Ultrafiltration (UF) and Reverse Osmosis (RO). The pilot plant is provided also with a third unit consisting in Electrodeionization (EDI), but since the required quality for industrial uses is achieved with only two units, EDI was not considered in the scaled-up scenario. The main industrial application would be for cooling, among others since it implies the main industrial water consumption. The pilot's treatment chain can provide 3 types of water quality (Q1, Q2, Q3) all studied and investigated; the line chosen for scaling up stably guarantees a quality (Q2) capable to satisfy every industrial need, in case of less demanding requirements (such as for firewater) also Q1 can satisfy the need.

Stakeholder engagement:

Considering that the LL's ambition is to tackle the linearity of its processes on a regional scale, and to transform various segments of the value chain, it is particularly important to create effective stakeholder engagement dynamics that promote the development of ideas, collaborations, feedback, and communication between different stakeholders.

Furthermore, the development of this network has the potential to encourage different stakeholders to develop collaborations with each other, without having to go through the sphere of influence of the lead organisation, and to enhance the development of the circular economy.

To this end, numerous Community of Practices' meetings have been carried out during the project with the aim of bringing together the different stakeholders and making them active participants in the objectives to be achieved through the LL, involving them in the design of solutions, asking for feedback, etc.

In relation to the C9 solution, in the first CoP developed in the LL, the different industries of the Porto Marghera area were brought together to share the objectives of the project, and the proposed solutions for the reuse of resources. After a specific survey to individuate industrial water requirements (uses, quantity and quality) opportunities were defined and explored together to establish an action path to address the needs of the industries.

Industrial stakeholders confirmed their agreement with the reuse targets and showed great interest in using the reused water for their industrial processes.

The other CoPs were structured around other themes: sharing the general objectives of the LL and its vision with public authorities, industrial and agricultural sectors, research institutes etc., obtaining information for the development of the digital tools, the BWS assessment framework (CoP 4), discussing the regulation concerning the solutions and reporting on the progress of the pilots (CoP 5), meeting with the different water utilities in the area in order to collaborate and share information for the development of platforms and other collaborations (CoP6).

As the objectives of the LL are more regional (even national) in nature and are based on a long-term mentality, it was particularly important to emphasise this point in order to identify and involve the entire network of actors affected by the solutions to be promoted, not only in the context of the Fusina plant, but in the water industry as a whole in the region.

4.6.2.2 Preliminary assessment:

Information concerning the preliminary studies is presented below:

- Validation of the Idea:**
 The solution partially solves the existing problems, and the reuse of water for industrial use is in demand in the market and of interest to the local industries.
- Revenue Model:**
 The revenue model is yet to be defined, but it is expected that a water tariff model will be applied. Pricing mechanisms are not yet defined.
- Financial Viability:**

The cost benefit analysis for the analysis of a scaled-up scenario could not be performed yet, considering that it is a complex and wide industrial site, with distribution infrastructures only partially present. Data will be strictly dependent on the end-user's final scenario/puzzle.

It is only possible at this stage to focus on the treatment's costs (neglecting pumping and distribution costs) considering a treatment process of UF and RO.

The cost structure for a hypothetical production scenario of 2.6 Mm³ /y of reclaimed water, with microbiological and chemical characteristics stably suitable for each type of industrial reuse, is presented in Table 17:

Table 17 Venice LL C9 CAPEX & OPEX (€/y) scaled-up scenario.

COSTS SCALED-UP (2.6 Mm ³ /y)			
Category	Description	Type	Costs
Equipment	Ultrafiltration system and Reverse Osmosis System	CAPEX	€ 3.500.000,00
TOT (€)		CAPEX	€ 3.500.000,00
Labor	Engineers	OPEX	€ 60.000,00
Labor	Operators	OPEX	€ 52.500,00
Utilities	Energy consumption	OPEX	€ 558.450,00
Service	Repair and maintenance	OPEX	€ 105.120,00
Products	Consumables	OPEX	€ 105.120,00
Equipment	Depreciation	OPEX	€ 175.000,00
TOT (€)		OPEX	€ 1.056.190,00

Today the operational costs for the baseline treatment scenario for Canvas Filtration and UV disinfection for the discharge into the sea of 38Mm³/y are reported in following Table 18:

Table 18 Venice LL C9 OPEX of baseline treatment scenario for sea discharge

COSTS Baseline Scenario (38Mm ³ /y)			
Category	Description	Type	Costs
Labor	Operators & engineers combined	OPEX	€ 140.000,00
Utilities	Energy consumption	OPEX	€ 443.792,00
Service	Maintenance and repairs	OPEX	€ 339.320,00
TOT (€)			€ 923.112,00

However, if the treated effluent resulting from the baseline treatment scenario were to stably guarantee the microbiological quality suitable for reuse in the industry, the costs would be far superior (up to four times as much).

- **Technical feasibility:**

The technology is available and meets the technical requirements for the production of reclaimed water for industrial use. Furthermore, it is modular for the installation of future units in case of wanting to scale-up the production.

- **Risks and Challenges:**

Costs could be the main challenges to be addressed to realize this industrial reuse, since we are still in presence of low-cost alternatives (freshwater) however the tendency of the Authorities is to adapt freshwater cost.

No other significant risks to the implementation of the solution have been identified.

- **Equipment and Resources:**

The implementation of this service will require on one side the installation of a treatment plant adequately designed to produce the volumes agreed with the industries and some adaptations of the WWTP's facilities and equipment; on the other side, it will be necessary to establish tailored partnership with the industries and, if the necessary, to implement the exiting distribution infrastructures implementation.

4.6.2.3 Concept

In the following, the business model concept is presented based on the information available to date for solution C9. For the remainder of solutions (C10, C11) their classification (up to step 4) is presented in **Annex B**.

Step 1: Circular strategies and cycle of operation.

Circular strategies: **Rethink, Reduce and Reuse**.

The operating cycle: **Technical cycle**.

Step 2: Business model innovation strategy.

Innovation strategy: **CBM diversification**.

The baseline business model continues to operate, and an additional CBM is created.

Step 3: BMI pathway and SCBM

The innovation roadmap that follows the business model:

Technological innovation: **Create value from waste.**

Social innovation: **Adopting a stewardship role.**

All solutions seem to coincide with a social innovation roadmap of the business model mainly aligned with **Adopt a stewardship role**, considering the efforts that are being developed for the creation of a stakeholder network and how they are being integrated in the development of the solutions. This work is reinforced by the role of the LL lead organisation as a regional and national enabler to promote resource recovery and wastewater reuse solutions for different uses.

In the case of wastewater reuse for industries and agriculture, the business model could also be associated with a social innovation aligned with **Deliver functionality rather than ownership**, if the WWTP offers a comprehensive service to industries (fulfilling all functions from production, distribution, and treatment). However, at this stage it is not defined.

Organisational innovation: The focus is on **Develop scale-up solutions**, as the objective is replicability to similar situation present at regional level, increasing volumes to ensure economic sustainability and scaling up social and environmental impact.

SCBM archetype: **Scale-up stewardship.**

The Venice innovation pathway indicates that the Scaled-up stewardship archetype aligns with the LL's objectives of enabling the provision of reclaimed water and its service to neighbouring industrial zones, by coordinating the needs of the stakeholders involved: water companies, industries, public authorities, environment, to ensure long-term durable relationships, while scaling sustainable solutions to maximise freshwater savings and reclaimed water reuse.

For further information on the development of the innovation pathway, and the characteristics of the SCBM archetype refer to Figure 7, Figure 8 and Table 1 presented in section 3.4.3.3.

Step 4: Circular business model classification

CBM (according to Lacy et al.): **Resource recovery.**

CBM subtype (according to Lacy et al.): **Upcycling.** Since the quality of the water will be increased compared to baseline scenario.

Refer to **Annex B**, for the classification of the remainder of CBMs linked to rest of circular solutions identified in the LL.

Step 5: Circular Business Model Canvas

Table 19 presents a preliminary CBMC representing the CBM for the reclaimed water reuse solution for industrial use according to the information available to date:

Table 19 Venice LL C9 (Increase of industrial water reuse) CBMC

Circular Business Model Canvas		Circularity goal and scope definition		Sustainability mission and action			
<p>Living Lab: VENICE increase of industrial water reuse</p> <p>Legend: Value proposition Value Creation & Delivery Value capture</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted CE principle (Select one or more principle) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - P1) Create value from waste, P2) Maximize energy and material efficiency, P3) Substitute with renewables and natural processes - CE strategies (Select one or more strategies) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - R1 - Rethink, R2 – Avoid, R3 – Reduce, R4-Replace, R5 - Reuse, R6- Recycle, R7 - Cascading, R8 - Store, R9 - Recover - Operating cycle (Select business operation cycle) - Technical cycle, Biological cycle • Circular business model innovation strategy (Select innovation strategy) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CBM transformation, CBM diversification, Circular start-up, CBM acquisition - Sustainable circular innovation pathways (Select one or more) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Purposeful sufficiency, Scaled-up sufficiency, Purposeful functionality, Scaled-up functionality, Purposeful stewardship, Scale-up stewardship - Circular business model type (Select one or more of the targeted circular business model type) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Circular supplies, Sharing platform, Product as a service, Product lifespan extension, Resource recovery 		<p>Targeted sustainable development goal</p> <p>Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions Goal 17: Partnership for the goals</p>			
Key Partners	Key Activities	Ecosystem Activities	Value Proposition		Customer Segments	Targeted solution	Benefits and burden
<p>Water utility (VERITAS): Fusina WWTP produces reclaimed water.</p> <p>Water manager: distributes reclaimed water to industries (to be defined*).</p> <p>Technology provider Hydrotech: engineering company supplies and builds treatment facility. Installs pilot plant and operates during experimentation phase.</p>	<p>Coordination and management of the value chain</p> <p>Production of reclaimed water</p> <p>Distribution of reclaimed water from WWTP to the industries (*under study, still uncertain due to complexity)</p> <p>Monitoring water system and quality control at production and delivery points.</p> <p>Maintenance and repair of infrastructure (treatment units and distribution network)</p> <p><i>Main actions that should be implemented and related to the</i></p>	<p>Public authorities: adapting policy and regulations, issuance of permits, unlocking financing instruments and incentives, promoting awareness towards reuse of water.</p> <p>R&I providers: supports technical and social innovation, provides knowledge capacity for experimentation, dissemination of case studies.</p> <p>Industrial Associations: facilitate connection between industrial end-users with water companies</p>	<p>To industries: Supplying reclaimed water fit for industrial processes produced through a tertiary treatment process using an Ultrafiltration and Reverse Osmosis System.</p> <p>To stakeholders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >All: Increasing city and municipality resilience to climate change by closing resource cycles and promoting an industrial network. >Water companies: diversification of water services, expanding services to a new market segment. Also increasing their sustainable and CE practices. >Technology provider: designing, building and commissioning of scaled-up treatment plant. Increasing their knowledge and adaptation of technologies to industrial reuse projects, improving efficiency of technology processes to produce cost-effective fit-for-purpose water. <p>To environment: Substituting natural sources for reclaimed water, reducing the consumption of freshwater.</p>		<p>Local industries: chemical industries, refinery, energy production, manufacturing industries (glass, machine, alloys and metals...), industrial water required mainly for cooling system but also for other purposes (such as washing, steam production, firewater..)</p>	<p>Reclaimed water: all quality need for the several industrial requirements (from high to medium)</p>	<p>Benefits:</p> <p>Environmental:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Increased resilience to drought events, and water security at city and municipal levels. <p>Society:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Promotes sustainable and CE practices. <p>Customer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >high quality water, stably and long term assured > water availability (quantity) stably and long term assured <p>Burden:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >potentially high energy consumption that, however, could be partially compensated by the potential by-passing of an highly energy-intensive existing treatment (UV) <p><i>What kind of benefits will our products/service create on customers, society and environment?</i></p> <p><i>What kind of burden will our product/service create on customers society and environment?</i></p>
	<p>Key Resources</p> <p>Effluent</p> <p>Energy</p> <p>Water treatment technology (UF-RO) distribution network and other plant equipment.</p> <p>Permits and licenses</p> <p>Skilled workforce</p> <p>Financial resources</p>		<p>Channels</p> <p>Physical networks: delivery of reclaimed water through a distribution network.</p> <p>Dissemination of circular practices through website, events, advertisement</p> <p>Project channels (B-Water smart or others): Workshops, CoP, Focus Groups etc.</p> <p>Public authorities channels: increasing environmental</p>	<p>Need/problem/challenge</p> <p>Due to an increased frequency of droughts due to climate change, it is required to adopt alternative water sources to reduce the consumption of freshwater in the city.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <p>Industries > Long-term relationship. Industrial Associations and several industries have participated as co-creators of the solution in the project.</p>		
<p>Cost Structure</p> <p>CAPEX: Treatment plant, storage tank, adapting in-plant distribution network.</p> <p>OPEX: Monitoring, coordination between stakeholders, utilities (energy for treatment and pumping), maintenance and repair (labor, chemicals)</p> <p>Scenario for 2.6Mm³/y production of reclaimed water. Pumping and delivery of reclaimed water costs are still under discussion.</p>				<p>Revenue Streams</p> <p>*The revenue model, is not defined and is still under analysis.</p>			

Step 6: SWOT Analysis:

The C9 CBM SWOT analysis is presented in Figure 22:

SWOT ANALYSIS	
INTERNAL FACTORS	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<p>Technical expertise of partners Adaptative technology that can be expanded to increase capacity in the future. Technology capacity to produce different water quality for different purposes Qualitative and Quantitative stability of reclaimed water with respect to freshwater</p> <p>Aligned vision between stakeholders Great stakeholder engagement Reduced CAPEX (part of the distribution infrastructure already invested)</p> <p><i>Characteristics of the business or project that give it an advantage over others</i> <i>Examples: Developed technology, lower environmental impact, usable byproduct, etc.</i></p>	<p>Governance structure not clear Private-Public partnership model still to be defined; presence of a Private Organization selling industrial water produced from freshwater to the industrial pole Cost (Opex) of the technology applied to produce reclaimed water</p> <p><i>Characteristics that place the business or project at a disadvantage relative to others</i> <i>Examples: High investment, unprofitable without feed-in tariffs, lack of knowledge and experience, high maintenance costs, etc.</i></p>
EXTERNAL FACTORS	
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<p>Public authorities aligned with LL goals. Opportunity to adapt and promote policy and regulations in favor of circular solutions.</p> <p>Local industries are interested in consuming reclaimed water.</p> <p>Social awareness favorable to water conservation.</p> <p>Due to recent drought period (which confirms the tendency) increasing sensitivity to the need of freshwater saving acting as leverage versus cost of reclaimed water supply (when there is no water availability, the cost becomes the minor problem)</p> <p><i>Elements in the environment that the business or project could exploit to its advantage(new markets, solutions...)</i> <i>Examples: possibility of use of existing infrastructure, broad range of applications, raising environmental awareness, environmental legislation of EU, etc.</i></p>	<p>Risk of maintaining the gap between freshwater and reclaimed water costs</p> <p>Uncertainty in the prices of energy which can lead to increasing production and distribution costs.</p> <p>Lack of a more consistent regulatory formalization enabling reclaimed water use</p> <p><i>External factors that are potential threats for your Living Lab</i> <i>Examples: Legal restrictions, price volatility, etc</i></p>

Figure 22 Venice LL C9 CBM SWOT analysis.

Step 7: Define performance and outcome metrics:

Metrics for the evaluation of the CBM have been identified and selected by the LLs following the AF of D6.3. as part of the work to be developed in WP4, T4.2.

These have been considered in further detail in D4.3 for the socio-environmental and economic assessment of the value chain according to three differentiated scenarios: baseline, circular and scaled-up.

4.6.3 Detail design

4.6.3.1 Experimentation

The individualization of the most critical variables for the designing of a tailored phase experimentation was carried out by closely working from the beginning along with the industrial end-users, i.e. the Porto Marghera industries. Most adaptations to the experimental plan to be done through the pilot demonstration were identified through several specific meetings organized at the purpose and by using

a specific survey on industrial uses (cooling, washing, fire prevention, steam production, etc.), requirements, issues, guarantees to have and give on water uses.

The effluent from Fusina WWTP undergoes a compact combinatory/sequenced treatment pilot plant, provided by HYDROTECH, specifically designed to produce water to be reused in industrial processes. A sequence of ultrafiltration (UF), reverse osmosis (RO), and electro-deionization (EDI) is tested to obtain several qualities of pure water, suitable for the different uses in the nearby industries of Porto Marghera industrial area. A tailored monitoring plan, identified taking into account all end-user indications, allowed analysing key parameters also for each treatment of the pilot chain: first elaborations of results confirm expectations, i.e. a high quality and stability of water produced, matching the guaranteed requirements of industrial uses already at RO outlet.

For more information about the description of the experiments and pilots carried out in the LL, see deliverable D2.17.

4.6.3.2 Detail design

In this case study for this circular solution, experimentation, detail design and piloting phases have been managed together with the purpose of obtaining the answers to the specific issues (requests from the industries) that enable the circular solution. The results obtained up to now out, are already addressing some of the barriers for this reuse application (technical feasibility to guarantee high quality and stability of water produced). However, it is still remaining, the economic scenario to be adopted which will be closely dependant on the exact size and allocation of the circularity scope (not only for the scale-up of technology but also for the distribution infrastructures) and on the supplier-user edge.

Information on all the main key technical-economic variables to evaluate full-scale implementations are in fact available, and negotiation tables among different stakeholders involved (from the Utility to the industrial end users) in the reclaimed water supply chain are underway, to individuate possible investment scenario, define agreements, partnerships, and business plans.

4.6.3.3 Pilot

Given the intense work and detailed analyses carried out from the beginning with the Industrial end-users and the customized experimentation carried out, further pilot phases are not necessary.

4.7 Bodø

4.7.1 Framing and scoping of the circular solutions in the Living Lab

Framing LL (Macro level context):

LL context and challenges:

Bodø, located on the northwest coast of Norway along the shores of Saltfjorden strait, is a city and municipality with a population of around 52,000 residents. Boasting a diverse economy that includes fishing, trade, services, and tourism, Bodø is a significant economic and commercial hub in the Nordland region.

The municipality of Bodø, unlike the other Living Labs in the project, has ample availability of water resources. Surface water sources meet all the needs of the region and are not at risk of shortage due to climate change. However, one of the risks associated with climate change is the potential increase in flooding from periods of heavy rainfall. Therefore, one of the main challenges for the municipality is to improve stormwater management through nature-based solutions and the construction of resilient infrastructure.

The existing issues in this LL are related to the prevention of pollution of water resources, as well as the improvement of efficiency in water management and urban infrastructure, as a consequence of population growth and the increase in the region's economy.

In addition, the city has the opportunity to develop a new urban plan, thanks to the relocation of the civil airport, which opens the door to the development of new areas that can focus on sustainable and circular development.

LL vision:

The LL Bodø vision is to become a sustainable, low-emission society and develop the city's resilience to climate change.

Some of the ambitions of the Living lab are:

- 70 % reduction in direct GHG-emissions (cf. 2009-levels) by 2030
- 70 % recycling of materials (household and industry waste) by 2030
- Bodø as a Low Emission Society in 2050

LL objectives:

The strategic objectives for the Living Lab were developed by the Living Lab in Task 1.4 and with the input of the CoPs, as part of the project work carried out in WP1. A final strategic agenda will be presented on D1.4 - Final strategic agenda and implementation plan for each LL, with the agreed LL vision and objectives.

LL partners:

Bodø Kommune: Bodø municipality in Nordland County, Norway, is integrated in the region of Salten. In the project Bodø Kommune is a case study and LL, and a key partner in connecting the technology and researcher partners. They are problem owner and owner of the old airport area to be redeveloped. They will coordinate the local CoP and engage the local community and stakeholder network.

Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) is a technology focused university with a long tradition for close collaboration with industry in technology development. In the project is work package lead for WP2, the technology work package. They are the research contact point for Bodø case study.

Nordkontakt: is an engineering company in the area of automation and information technology. In the project. Nordkontakt will deliver the solution data collection and analysis solutions for the technology part of the Bodø LL in WP2. Their software solutions will integrate data collection and communication from the different sensors and smart meters.

TECHNI: is a privately held solution provider that perform research and innovative product development. In the project they are developer and producer of sensors, communication systems, energy systems.

SINTEF: the Foundation for Scientific and Industrial Research is a multidisciplinary non-profit research organisation with international top-level expertise in the fields of technology, natural sciences, medicine, and social sciences. In the project they are R&I providers in the case of Bodø in collaboration with NTNU.

LL activities:

The LL aims to carry out the following actions:

- Achieve improved water use efficiency by raising awareness of water usage of homeowners.
- Develop technologies that assist homeowners and municipalities in leakage detection.
- Inspire and educate stakeholders regarding the use of blue green structures in urban settings.
- Assist the development of a sludge biogas reactor for energy recovery from sludge.

Key dependencies, risks, and opportunities:

- Urban infrastructures designed for linear water and waste management systems.
 - Associated Risk: Resistance to structural changes that favour optimisation and circularity.
 - Long-term opportunities: Improvement in distribution, measurement, systems, management, and regulatory changes.
 - Circular opportunity: Redefine urban infrastructure to embrace circular models, prioritising sustainable resource management.
- Regulatory changes (EU's Urban Wastewater treatment directive, sludge handling methods) and the backlog of renewal for aging watermain network.
 - Associated Risk: Increased funding needed, deprioritization of other tasks.
 - Long-term opportunities: New funding opportunities, improved leakage detection methods, improved handling methods of sludge, improved treatment of wastewater
 - Circular opportunity: Increased efficiency in water distribution systems (reduction of leakages).
- Conventional approach to solid waste disposal.
 - Associated Risk: Limitations in sustainable waste management.
 - Long-term opportunities: Awareness raising, value chain upgrading, resource optimisation.
 - Circular Opportunity: Promote reduce, reuse, and recycle practices, incorporating circular economy principles.

- Iris (waste management company who receives and handles sludge), Public funding (through municipal fees),
 - Associated Risk: Iris being no longer able to manage municipal sludge waste due to regulatory changes, no other suppliers near, public dissatisfaction with increasing costs.
 - Long-term opportunities: Biogas production, awareness raising, value chain upgrading, resource optimisation.
 - Circular Opportunity: Promote reduce, reuse, and recycle practices, incorporating circular economy principles.

Barriers and Drivers (Macro level):

Drivers:

1. Regulatory mandates, EU UWWTD energy neutrality.
2. Internal motivations, goals, ambitions, and targets set for emission reduction.
3. Ny By Ny Flyplass Project.
4. Environmental benefits.

Barriers:

1. Lack of expertise, awareness, and knowledge.
2. High investment cost for biogas.
3. Lack of commitment to initial investment.

Scoping Living Lab circular solutions (Meso and Micro Level):

Scoping, site location and state of the art description:

The projects being developed in the Living Lab are the following:

- Installation of smart water meters for improved water management efficiency
- Feasibility study of alternative methods of handling residual byproducts of biogas reactor for energy recovery of sludge

Previously, we have presented the Living Lab's big picture and how it intends to direct its efforts towards achieving its objectives from a general perspective. In this section we narrow down the scope to the potential circular value chain enabled by the proposed solution. This is solution C17, corresponding to the production of biogas through the treatment of sewage sludge (from various municipalities) together with other sources of organic matter.

Unlike the other Living Lab, it should be noted that the design of the business model for this solution is at a very early stage of development (ideation). Within the framework of the project, no technologies will be tested through pilots, but feasibility studies will be developed to evaluate the different technological options available. This task will be carried out through T2.2.2 by the project partner SINTEF. Regarding this document, a description of the preliminary idea, a classification of the CBM, and a preliminary business model canvas will be presented.

Description of the baseline scenario:

Currently, the sewage sludge from the WWTPs is treated by a waste management plant belonging to IRIS Salten IKS, an inter-municipal company jointly owned by the municipalities in the Salten region. Given the scarcity of sludge that is generated independently at each plant, it has been proposed to study the generation of biogas through co-digestion, collecting all the sludge generated at the plants in the region.

IRIS Salten is a Group consisting of a parent company with five wholly owned subsidiaries and one majority-owned subsidiary. As far as the proposed solution is concerned, the subsidiary responsible for the treatment of municipal and regional waste is IRIS Produksjon AS. The case study plant is located in Vikan, in the municipality of Bodø.

IRIS Produksjon AS is responsible for the operation of landfill, coarse sorting, composting, iron and metal recovery and automobile facilities. The main activities carried out at the plant are reception, treatment, disposal, as well as recovery and reuse of materials.

The plant carries out composting treatment of sewage sludge prior to landfilling (there is no energy recovery or use of the post-composting waste). There is also another line of organic waste treatment through composting (no sewage sludge mixed), which are valorised post-composting as fertilisers. The origin of the organic waste is diverse in nature and comes from both domestic waste collection as well as from other private companies in the municipality.

The organic waste collection services are provided by one of the group's sister subsidiaries.

Therefore, the current value chain with regard to waste management in general is mainly linear as the calorific capacity of the organic waste and sewage sludge is not exploited.

The opportunity to recover energy from waste, together with the need to reduce the environmental (i.e. pollution reduction, ecosystem protection) and social impacts of landfill practices, presents an attractive circular opportunity to further the objectives of the Living Lab, and improve the sustainability of IRIS practices and services.

It should be added that wastewater and waste management services are provided by different organisations. Therefore, the adoption of this solution has the potential to improve the integration of both services and strengthen the collaboration between the different stakeholders in the region.

Mapping the ecosystem:

The mapping of stakeholders for all the circularities carried out in the LL of Bodø has been carried out in task T4.2. and is presented in D4.3.

4.7.2 Ideation

4.7.2.1 Idea generation

The generation of ideas for the biogas generation solution (C17) has been done through internal project meetings between the project partners SINTEF, Bodø kommune, as well as IRIS (not a project partner) and different technology providers. The different options have been communicated among the project stakeholders through consortium internal meetings. A CoP is planned to involve more stakeholders affected by the solution. As indicated above, feasibility studies to assess the different technologies will be carried out through the task T2.2.2.

As described in D4.3. All solutions have as their main objective the generation of biogas for energy production and self-consumption at the plant. The surplus will not be considered for export to the grid, due to the lack of infrastructure and the relatively low cost of selling the energy. However, other options will be considered, such as the recharging of electric batteries.

The fundamental difference between the different technological solutions to produce biogas refer to the way of processing the digestate generated after co-digestion: composting (currently done), production of biopellets or biochar. Composting would be the least efficient option in terms of circularity, as the digestate (from sludge) would have to be destined for landfill (the regulation does not foresee the use of digestate from sewage sludge for use as fertiliser).

Figure 23 Bodø LL C17 Biogas production and biosolids process diagram

Stakeholder engagement:

As a result of the project, a CoP, several focus groups, and internal meetings have been held with the different stakeholders of the LL, in which different topics have been addressed. In general, these have focused on the overarching objectives of the LL, and other technological solutions developed in the project (but not circular). Due to the fact that T2.2.2. is a feasibility study and not a pilot, as well as delays of task leadership change, the solution of biogas production has not yet been addressed in detail.

For the implementation of a biogas production system in a plant, it will be necessary to coordinate a wide network of actors.

4.7.2.2 Preliminary assessment

The preliminary feasibility analyses of the different ideas proposed is undergoing.

- **Validation of the Idea:**

The solution helps to achieve the objectives set out in the LL, as it has the potential to reduce CO₂ emissions, and promote the reuse of materials.

In terms of the market, there is currently no competition in the region.

- **Revenue Model:**

The revenue models are yet to be defined, but it is expected that gate fees (by volume and depending on the substrate) will be applied as they are applied to other municipal and private customers for the management of their waste. On the other hand, the revenue model will be based on cost savings in energy consumption and on the commercialisation of digestate (only from organic matter, not sewage sludge, see Risks and Challenges) according to the way it is processed.

- **Financial Viability:**
No cost-benefit analysis has been carried out for the time being.
- **Technical feasibility:**
The technology is available on the market, but feasibility studies of the different technological options (option appraisal) are still pending. This will be carried out as part of T2.2.2.
- **Analysis of social and environmental impacts:**
They shall be carried out in conjunction with the technical feasibility analysis.
- **Risks and Challenges:**
The main risks are those inherent to a biogas production system: lack of availability and variability of feedstock quality, strict regulation on the reuse of digestate from sewage sludge, high infrastructure costs, etc.
Regulatory barriers to the solution have been identified in D5.5.
- **Equipment and Resources:**
The company has the capacities and competences of a waste manager, which favours the implementation of this solution. However, there is no infrastructure for digestion of the substrates and an investment in a biogas plant is required.

4.7.2.3 Concept

Step 1: Circular strategies and cycle of operation.

The circular strategies: **Rethink, Reduce, Replace and Recover**.

The operating cycle: **Technical and Biological cycle**.

Step 2: Business model innovation strategy.

Innovation strategy: **CBM diversification**.

The existing Business Model at the plant would continue to operate, but a new CBM would be developed that improves the linear waste treatment processes at the plant.

Step 3: BMI pathway and SCBM

The innovation roadmap that follows the business model:

Technological innovation: “**Create value from waste**” and “**Maximize material and energy efficiency**”.

Social innovation: “**Adopt a stewardship role**” and “**Encourage sufficiency**”.

Since IRIS is inter-municipal owned, the social innovation seems to be driven towards fostering collaboration between municipalities and therefore it is aligned with "Adopting a stewardship role". However, a social innovation of "Encourage sufficiency" is also promoted, given that the reduction of external energy consumption is encouraged.

Organisational innovation: Given that the volume of waste available in the region is limited, organisational innovation will be guided by "**Repurpose for society or the environment**".

SCBM archetype: **Hybrid model: Purposeful sufficiency and Purposeful stewardship.**

For further information on the development of the innovation pathway, and the characteristics of the SCBM archetype refer to Figure 7, Figure 8 and Table 1 presented in section 3.4.3.3.

Step 4: Circular business model classification

CBM (according to Lacy et al.): **Hybrid CBM** (Circular Inputs and Resource recovery).

In the case of providing electric battery recharging services, the business model would also include the "**Product as a service**" typology.

Step 5: Circular Business Model Canvas

Table 20 presents a preliminary CBMC that captures the main elements of a potential CBM for C17: increase of energy production.

Table 20 Bodø LL C17 (Increase of energy production through biogas) CBMC

Circular Business Model Canvas		Circularity goal and scope definition		Sustainability mission and action		
Living Lab: BODO		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Targeted CE principle (Select one or more principle) P1) Create value from waste, P2) Maximize energy and material efficiency, P3) Substitute with renewables and natural processes CE strategies (Select one or more strategies) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> R1 - Rethink, R2 - Avoid, R3 - Reduce, R4-Replace, R5 - Reuse, R6- Recycle, R7 - Cascading, R8 - Store, R9 - Recover Operating cycle (Select business operation cycle) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical cycle, Biological cycle Circular business model innovation strategy (Select innovation strategy) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CBM transformation, CBM diversification, Circular start-up, CBM acquisition Sustainable circular innovation pathways (Select one or more) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Purposeful sufficiency, Scaled-up sufficiency, Purposeful functionality, Scaled-up functionality, Purposeful stewardship, Scale-up stewardship Circular business model type (Select one or more of the targeted circular business model type) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular inputs, Sharing platform, Product as a service, Product lifespan extension, Resource recovery 		Targeted sustainable development goal Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure , Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities , Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production , Goal 13: Climate action , Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions Goal 17: Partnership for the goals		
Legend: Value proposition (green), Value Creation & Delivery (blue), Value capture (orange)						
Key Partners	Key Activities	Ecosystem Activities	Value Proposition	Customer Segments	Targeted solution	Benefits and burden
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Bodo Kommune: coordinates interface between different stakeholders, acts as a bridges to the public authorities. >Technology provider (**): design and construction of biogas plant >IRIS Salten Produksjon: management and coordination of the biogas syste. >Salten's WWTPs: providers of sewage sludge. >Consultants (**): Solution providers, guidance in feedstock selection and mixes, experimentation etc. >Organic feedstock suppliers: co-creators of the product >Transports company (**): transporting of sewage sludge and organic waste. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Transportation of sewage sludge >Coordination and management of supply chain >Production of biogas (waste reception, mixing, digestion and CHP, dispose of digestate) >Transportation of digestate to end users >Maintenance and repair of infrastructure >Experimentation with different substrate mixes. >Monitoring operating efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Public authorities: adapting policy and regulations, issuance of permits, unlocking financing instruments and incentives, promoting awareness towards reuse of water. >R&I providers: supports technical and social innovation, provides knowledge capacity for experimentation, dissemination of case studies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>IRIS Salten Produksjon</i>: Improves the waste processes at the plant by maximizing resource efficiency by exploiting biogas recovery from sewage sludge and organic waste that can be transformed into electricity for the plant self-sufficiency. Improves circular and sustainability practices and brand reputation. <i>Bodo Kommune and other municipalities</i>: Improving the waste and wastewater system in the municipality and Salten's region. Reducing pollution and increasing the circular practices towards a smart city. <i>Stakeholders</i>: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >All: Moving toward attaining strategic objectives of the Living Labs. >WWTPs: <i>Improve circularity of their processes.</i> >Technology provider: designing, building and commissioning of scaled-up treatment plant. Increased knowledge biogas production projects, and fine-tuning the technology to increase efficiency of processes with different sustrates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >WWTPs/Municipalities >Private customers (e.g. restaurants, industries...) >Digestate end-users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >WWTPs/Municipalities -> Sewage sludge management service. >Private customers ->Organic waste management services >Digestate end-user -> Transformation of digestate in the form of biopellets or biochar (**) to sell as fuel. 	Benefits: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased resilience to climate change by reducing pollution and safeguarding ecosystem -Development of circular economy and a stakeholder network. Burden: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High costs for investment, operation and maintenance. - Possible increased cost for consumers - Difficulties recruiting educated staff
Cost Structure			Channels	Need/problem/challenge	Customer Relationships	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *The costs structure is not yet defined. CAPEX: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biogas treatment plant (depending on technology **) Pilot plant to run experimentation OPEX: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transportation costs (to be agreed depending on organizational structure) Coordinating and managing supply chain Utilities (mainly energy) Maintenance and repair Labor (in-plant workers, engineer and administrator) 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >IRIS Salten own channel: Website, participation on circular economy conventions, events and fairs, loyalty programs etc. >Physical channels: transportation of resources in and out of the plant. >Ecosystem network: CoP, industry events, workshops, focus groups. >Municipality channels: social awareness campaigns, surveys 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reducing pollution and increasing the efficiency of resources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WWTPs/Municipalities: partnerships Private customers: partnerships and transactional relationships. Digestate end-users: customer co-creation or partnerships. 	
Revenue Streams						
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Revenue streams are not yet defined. Some generic for biogas producers systems: Gate fees for waste/wastewater management services Cost-savings biogas self-consumption for own processes Selling of biopellets or biochar to customers (**) 			

Value Proposition
<p><i>IRIS Salten Produksjon:</i> Improves the waste processes at the plant by maximizing resource efficiency by exploiting biogas recovery from sewage sludge and organic waste that can be transformed into electricity for the plant self-sufficiency. Improves circular and sustainability practices and brand reputation.</p> <p><i>Bodo Kommune and other municipalities:</i> Improving the waste and wastewater system in the municipality and Salten's region. Reducing pollution and increasing the circular practices towards a smart city.</p> <p><i>Stakeholders:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ><i>All:</i> Moving toward attaining strategic objectives of the Living Labs. ><i>WWTPs:</i> Improve circularity of their processes. ><i>Technology provider:</i> designing, building and commissioning of scaled-up treatment plant. Increased knowledge biogas production projects, and fine-tuning the technology to increase efficiency of processes with different substrates. ><i>Consultants:</i> Increased knowledge biogas production projects, developing new substrates recipes. <p><i>Community:</i> Reduction of odors nearby waste plant.</p> <p><i>Environment:</i> Reduce GHG (methane capture).</p>

Figure 24 Bodø LL C17 Value proposition from Table 20

Step 6: SWOT Analysis:

The C17 CBM SWOT analysis is presented in Figure 25:

SWOT ANALYSIS	
INTERNAL FACTORS	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<p>IRIS Salten highly technical competencies in different sector activities, experience cross-over can be leveraged.</p> <p>Organizational structure of IRIS Salten (intermunicipal) eases collaboration with WWTPs</p> <p>Space available in the plant.</p> <p>Plant receives organic waste of various types that can be mixed with sludge to improve biogas production.</p> <p>Lower GHG emissions.</p>	<p>Transporting sewage sludge from long distances.</p> <p>Complex value chain. Requiring high operating excellence.</p> <p>High investment in infrastructure. Low returns of investments.</p> <p>Highly technical to monitor efficiency and developing experiments with new substrates. Also requiring skillfull operators.</p> <p>Complex agreements between multiple municipalities and 'Selvkost' legislation</p>
EXTERNAL FACTORS	
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<p>New market opportunity. No current competition in the region.</p> <p>Different partnerships opportunities, with different sectors, that can also expand innovation in other activities and services.</p> <p>National wide experience in biogas plant construction and also financing opportunities for biogas projects</p>	<p>Variability of feedstock, hard to predict biogas production efficiency.</p> <p>Regulatory barriers: Restrictive regulations for digestate from sewage source does not have a market (other than sell-off as fuel: pellets or biochar).</p>

Figure 25 Bodø LL C17 CBM SWOT analysis.

Step 7: Define performance and outcome metrics:

Metrics for the evaluation of the CBM have been identified and selected by the Living Lab following the AF of D6.3. as part of the work to be developed in WP4, T4.2.

These have been considered in further detail in D4.3 for the socio-environmental and economic assessment of the value chain (based on the data available at this stage) according to three differentiated scenarios: baseline, circular and scaled-up.

Step 8: Define performance and outcome metrics:

No prototypes have been realised at this stage.

4.7.2.4 Detail design

This phase has not yet started.

5 Conclusions

5.1.1 Overall conclusions

In conclusion, we will discuss the benefits that the development of this work entails and the limitations to which it is subject. We will also outline the necessary requirements identified throughout the document to achieve a successful implementation of the CE in the water sector.

Benefits of the Exercise

- **Creation of Specific Guidelines:** The development of systematic and specific guidelines for the implementation of Circular Business Models (CBMs) provides a structured framework that organizations can follow to adapt their business models in the water sector. This represents a solid methodological foundation that can be replicated and adapted to other environments and sectors.
- **Holistic Approach:** By connecting macro contexts (policies, economy, regulations) with meso-micro contexts (operations, processes, and specific actors of the Living Labs), the exercise provides a comprehensive vision that addresses the complexity of CBM implementation. This approach ensures that all relevant factors are considered for effective implementation.
- **Identification of Opportunities and Challenges:** The application of the guidelines in the six Living Labs (LLs) allows the identification of specific opportunities and unique challenges in each context. This helps organizations anticipate obstacles, such as regulatory or financial barriers, and develop strategies to overcome them, facilitating the adoption of circular practices.
- **Development of Preliminary CBMs:** Through the practical application of the guidelines, preliminary business models adapted to the needs and characteristics of each LL have been developed. This provides a valuable starting point for organizations, enabling them to direct their efforts toward circular solutions that are feasible and beneficial in their respective contexts.
- **Promotion of the Circular Economy:** The exercise reinforces the importance of adopting circular business models in the water sector, which can encourage other actors to consider the circular economy as a viable path for the sustainable management of water resources. Documenting these processes and results contributes to knowledge and awareness of best practices in this field.
- **Flexibility and Replicability:** The proposed guidelines are designed to be applied in different contexts, making them flexible and replicable in other LLs and sectors. This feature allows other projects to leverage the lessons learned and adapt them according to their specific needs and challenges.

Limitations of the Exercise

- **Preliminary State of the CBMs:** the innovation processes of the CBMs are still in a preliminary development phase, and detailed analyses are required in order to adjust and define the final CBMs..
- **Lack of Empirical Data:** The most recurrent aspects hindering the development of the CBMs at this stage are detailed financial analyses have not been carried out to define revenue models, the organisational structures of scaled solutions have not been defined or the operating models are still uncertain, financing mechanisms have not been defined, or implementation plans have still not been developed.
- **Dependence on the Regulatory Framework:** The success of many of the proposed CBMs depends on adjustments in regulatory frameworks and specific policies, which can vary significantly between regions and countries. This dependence makes the immediate replicability of the models difficult and suggests that, without adequate regulatory support, some CBMs may not be feasible.
- **Complexity of Stakeholder Collaboration:** Implementing CBMs in the water sector requires collaborative governance that involves multiple stakeholders, including regulatory bodies, public and private companies, and local communities. The coordination and alignment of interests among these actors can be complex and pose a significant barrier to the effective implementation of CBMs.
- **Limited Resources for Implementation:** Adopting circular models may require significant investments in infrastructure, technology, and training, which may not always be within the reach of all organizations, especially those with limited budgets. Additionally, the need for innovative financial models poses an additional challenge that could limit the adoption and success of the proposed CBMs.
- **Specific Application to the LLs:** Although the guidelines are designed to be flexible and adaptable, the proposed models are strongly influenced by the specific characteristics and conditions of the LLs analyzed. This means that their application in other contexts may require significant adjustments, which somewhat reduces the direct replicability of the solutions.

Requirements to achieve a successful implementation

Throughout the document, a series of requirements necessary to achieve a successful implementation of the Circular Economy in the Water Sector have been evaluated.

As highlighted throughout the document, the successful deployment of the CE in the water sector through the work in LLs requires consideration of several critical aspects. These aspects include the financial model, governance, policies and regulation, and capacity building.

1. Financial Model

- **Adapted Financial Schemes:** As discussed in the document, it is essential to emphasize the importance of having financial models that allow investment in circular technologies and processes. The adoption of CBMs in the LLs depends on sustainable financing that covers both the initial costs and long-term operations.
- **Analysis of Financial Mechanisms:** As seen in the detailed design phase of the CBMs, it is crucial during the development stages to assess financial resources and explore various sources of funding, such as grants, loans, and equity capital, to ensure long-term sustainability.

2. Governance

- **Collaboration and Stakeholder Participation:** For the implementation of CBMs, the document has highlighted the importance of maintaining a close relationship between stakeholders, especially during the ideation and monitoring phases of the business model's development. This implies the need for collaborative governance that integrates public, private, and community actors, with a particular focus on aligning the incentives of each stakeholder.
- **Governance Structure:** As emphasized, the successful application of CBMs will require a clear governance structure capable of coordinating and fostering cooperation among the various actors involved in the management of circular solutions, taking into account the specifics of a regulated environment.

3. Policies and Regulation

- **Effective Regulatory Framework:** The importance of an adapted regulatory framework is fundamental to the success of CBMs, as discussed throughout the document. A solid regulatory framework should include legislative and economic measures that promote the adoption of circular practices in the water sector.
- **Barriers and Opportunities:** It has also been observed that the implementation of CBMs faces regulatory and economic barriers, indicating that the development of these models is conditioned by the existing regulations. Addressing these barriers is crucial to facilitate the path toward a circular economy in the water sector.

4. Training and Knowledge

- **Innovation and Capabilities:** The document has also highlighted the importance of technological and organizational innovation to improve circular processes. Emphasis is placed on the need to iterate and refine the CBMs through reassessments, which involves the continuous development of specific skills within the sector.

5.1.2 Summary of results CBMs in LLs

In this section, we present the main conclusions drawn from the preliminary CBMs in the LLs.

Alicante LL:

The circularity studied is **C1: Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion**. The existing starting business model is a CBM (developed anaerobic digestion), and its innovation is developed in the context of a LL driven by a water utility. The solution increases the level of circularity of the WWTP processes by introducing an organic substrate to the digestion sludge and thus increasing biogas production. The innovation strategy implemented is a **CBM Transformation** and the innovation purposes are aligned with the development of a **Hybrid model SCBM: Scale-up sufficiency and Scale-up stewardship**. The CBM can be classified as a **Hybrid model: Circular inputs and Resource recovery** and **Industrial Symbiosis** subtype. Following the LL's specific objectives of becoming a biofactory, the development of this CBM will potentially drive the development of an Industrial Symbiosis network, which, in this case, would have a low level of centralisation and coordination, due to an early stage of maturity. At the same time, the solution is conceived from the outset for the self-consumption of the biogas generated and thus to promote the self-sufficiency of the plant. The value proposition offered, in addition to the energy resilience of the plant, is the treatment of waste for waste generators and the opportunity to enhance brand reputation and access to a local circular economy network that can generate other opportunities for the participants in the future.

In the preliminary CBM proposed through the CBMC, the following elements are yet to be defined:

- Key partners: during the project contact has been established with two organic waste suppliers, however, in order to reach the targeted feedstock volumes, agreements will have to be established with these suppliers, in addition to looking for other suppliers. Similarly, it will be necessary to define who will provide transport services for the waste from the collection point to the WWTP.
- The definition of the cost structure will have to be detailed in order to define the expected operational costs once the supplier structure is defined.
- The revenue streams that have been defined to date only by estimating economic savings from energy costs, but other revenue streams are yet to be defined (e.g. tipping fees).

Conclusions drawn from the CBM SWOT analysis:

- Strengths and opportunities: overall the solution proposed in the LL is aligned with the strategic objectives of the driving organisation. The development of the solution boosts the development of an industrial network and increases the capacities and competences to develop a stewardship role at local and regional level that will boost the development of the other circular solutions proposed (e.g. brines valorisation, nutrient recovery). In addition, the WWTP has partial infrastructure for the implementation of the solution, which reduces the necessary investment costs.
- Weaknesses and threats: the main hindrances are the entry into an organic waste market (with demand for “high quality” waste); the management of a complex value chain with multiple stakeholders (technical and organisational) which make it necessary to allocate own resources for its management; and the regulatory restrictions for the generation of income through digestates.

The current state of development of CBM is in a "Detail analysis" phase. More detailed economic and financial feasibility studies are required, as well as the development of operational processes to reduce and minimize the uncertainties and elements that have been identified. One of the measures planned by the lead organisation is to develop, outside the BWS project, a pilot to evaluate operational aspects of the solution.

Lisbon LL:

The circularity studied is **C7: Urban water reuse for irrigation**. The existing starting business model is an LBM (use of fresh water for irrigation of urban green areas). The innovation strategy followed by the BM is **CBM Transformation** and the innovation purposes are aligned with the development of a **Purposeful stewardship type SCBM**. The development of CBM is framed in the context of a LL driven by a public organisation. The main objective from a macro context for the LL that the solution aims to achieve is to enable the environment for the extended use of reclaimed water to limit the consumption of fresh water for non-potable uses in the city of Lisbon. The CBM can be classified as a **Hybrid model: Circular inputs and Resource recovery** and **Upcycling** subtype. The main value proposition is the production and distribution of reclaimed water for irrigation of publicly owned urban green areas with the municipality being the main end-user, although it is also foreseen for use in gardens owned by the state, local administrations, and some private owners with public access.

In the preliminary CBM proposed through the CBMC the following elements are still to be defined:

- Key partners: the organisational structure is preliminary but is not definitive.
- Cost structure: the costs of production and distribution of reclaimed water are unknown.
- Revenue Streams: the pricing mechanisms are not defined.

Conclusions drawn from the CBM SWOT analysis:

Strengths and opportunities: Firstly, there's a significant advantage in avoided costs through the reduced need to purchase drinking water for non-potable purposes like irrigation of green areas. Additionally, there's a remarkable alignment in vision among stakeholders and across levels, facilitating the promotion of water reuse. Moreover, the collective competences, capacities, and resources of organizations within the LL create a solid foundation for driving the necessary changes and establishing an enabling environment, which includes regulatory policy changes and heightened social awareness. Furthermore, the strategic plan for Lisbon includes the development of a distribution network for reclaimed water, while the availability of treated wastewater volume and the technical expertise of AdTA, supported by recent legislative developments, contribute to the production of reclaimed water. Lastly, the emphasis on constructing blue and green sustainable infrastructure not only enhances the city's resilience but also opens up a new market for reclaimed water, further reinforcing the potential for sustainable water management practices.

Weaknesses and threats: Urban water reuse is pioneering in Portugal, so an effort in reclaimed water quality monitoring is currently asked to users. The management of the reclaimed water distribution network is not yet defined. Additionally, significant investment in the construction of the reclaimed water distribution network and investment is needed in advanced treatment for Class-A reclaimed water production. The situation currently existing in the Lisbon water distribution service is, among other aspects, affecting the decision on the management of the reclaimed water distribution network. Moreover, external political and economic context not favourable for investments and impacting the goods supply chains.

The current state of development of CBM is in a "Detail analysis" phase. Given the context that affects the development of this CBM, conditioned especially by the existing regulation, the definition of key aspects for its development is still uncertain, requiring the overcoming of these barriers. One of the key aspects that have been identified is that the definition of the scoping of the solution must be clearer and more specific in order to facilitate the delimitation of the actions and develop analyses that are more approachable. In addition, the cost structure should be defined in more detail to be able to develop economic and financial analyses, as well as to define the organisational structures and operational procedures that will be necessary for the correct implementation of CBM.

East Frisia LL:

The circularity studied is **C12: increase water reuse in dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate (cow water)**. The circular solution is framed in the context of a LL driven by a public water company in partnership with a dairy plant, a technology supplier, and a research institute. From a macro perspective the solution helps improving the sustainable management of the available water resources and guaranteeing water availability for the next generations in East Frisia.

The existing business model, from a water supplier's perspective is linear as it supplies drinking water for the identified cow water application. The business model innovation strategy follows a **CBM diversification**, although this is subject to the final organisational structure (e.g. operator model) of the scaled-up scenario. The innovation purpose is aligned with the development of a **Scaled-up sufficiency SCBM**, since the circular solution encourages reduction of drinking water consumption for industrial processes, and the use of cow water is an opportunity to expand production.

The value proposition for dairy plants is the provision of treated water volumes to save freshwater and maximize recirculation resources, while improving site security and generating beneficial marketing effects.

The preliminary CBM proposed from the developed CBMC identifies the following elements to be defined:

- Key partners: the organizational structure for the scale-up solution is still under evaluation.
- Cost Structure: investments and operational costs are still to be defined.
- Revenue Streams: have not yet been estimated.
- Environmental impacts: to be assessed.

Conclusions drawn from the CBM SWOT analysis:

Strengths and opportunities:

There is an established long-term relationship between the water supplier and dairy company. Moreover, the LL stakeholders are highly skilled in solutions related to the reuse of water. Furthermore, there is a close relationship to the public authorities, provided the public nature of the water supplier and longstanding established production site.

The solution provides the following opportunities: replication of the solution to other dairies in the region, update existent regulation to increase reuse potential of recycled process water, promote positive social and environmental impacts, as well as develop innovative collaborations and partnerships in other sites, and lastly expand the development of a CE market.

Weaknesses and threats:

The weaknesses and threats of the solution relates to the production costs of treatment of industrial water being more expensive than freshwater, thus the dependency in the medium term to public or public/private financing instruments. Also, the process is highly technical and specific, and requires the adoption of the technology for replication to other industries. Moreover, there is limited market expansion apart from the dairy industry (still, one of the most important employers in Germany). Lastly, the current regulations are restrictive for the intended reuse application.

The current state of development of the CBM is under the "Detail design" stage. Key aspects in the development of the CBM at this stage are the determination of the production and operating costs for the envisaged scenario. This is necessary in order to correctly determine the funding requirements, whether public or public/private, to ensure the sustainability of the solution. Similarly, it is necessary to define the organizational structure, as well as to design operational processes, contingency plans, and implementation plans. Additionally, the solution is affected by regulatory constraints as the intended reuse application is restricted under current regulations. It is necessary to adapt and/or create new policies and regulations to enable its implementation. These aspects allow the CBM to be reviewed and adjusted before proceeding to implementation.

Flanders LL:

The circularity studied is **C14: Stormwater reuse for irrigation through a subirrigation system**. There was no initial business model. The innovation strategy developed for its implementation is **CBM Circular Start-up** and its objectives are aligned with the development of a **Purposeful stewardship SCBM**. The circular solution is framed in the context of an LL driven by a set of public organisations combining research institutes, water companies and public authorities. The main objective pursued through circularity is the capture of stormwater for infiltration back into the groundwater aquifer through a synergy with the farming sector. The **CBM** can be classified as **Circular inputs** of the **Biomimicry** subtype. The value proposition offered is increasing water security of farmers during dry months or drought events by recharging the groundwater system with stormwater while increasing the soil moisture of their crops by performing the infiltration of water through a subirrigation system. This improves the stormwater management of the city, improving resilience to climate change and protecting natural ecosystems.

The preliminary CBM proposed from the developed CBMC identifies the following elements to be defined:

- Value proposition: the value proposition that has been defined for the farmers, and for the community, will need to be confirmed according to the final participation they have within the circular solution.
- Key partners: the organisational structure of the solution outside the B-Water Smart project is not confirmed. The operating model to be implemented is under development.
- Cost structure: the operational costs have been estimated, but a detailed cost structure is still pending.
- Revenue streams: revenue models and financing mechanisms to cover operational costs have not been defined and are currently under evaluation with relevant stakeholder groups.
- Customer segments and Targeted solutions: depending on the value proposition, the organisational structure, and the revenue models applied, these elements will need to be reviewed.

Conclusions drawn from the CBM SWOT analysis:

- **Strengths and opportunities:** It is a project that effectively drives the collective collaboration of different stakeholders with a potential to drive the dissemination of circular practices, raises social awareness, and fosters the development of synergies between sectors. It has an environmental impact that is clearly aligned with natural resource protection and climate resilience. Infrastructure investment costs are partially covered by redevelopment plans that were planned before the BWS.
- **Weaknesses and Threats:** One of the problems identified in the project is the definition of a strong value proposition to the end-users and an absence of ex-ante feasibility studies. Given that the orientation of the solution is very much towards environmental protection of the ecosystem, and the quantification of the impact is difficult to define, the definition of revenue models to cover the application is unclear. At the same time, current regulations on the application of stormwater use in irrigation imply on the one hand high requirements on water quality, and on the other hand are not clear enough on the allocation of responsibilities for stormwater management.

The current state of development of the CBM is in the "Detail Design" phase. However, it is important to note that the stormwater reservoir, adapted for application in the planned circularity, has already been constructed. However, there are still many uncertainties in the development of a sustainable CBM. Some of the reasons identified include the absence of preliminary feasibility studies, as well as a lack of clarity and definition of value propositions in the initial (ex-ante) project planning phases. Efforts are currently being made to identify different alternatives for financing operational costs to clarify some of these uncertainties, as well as to define an organisational structure for the solution beyond the BWS. Regarding the regulatory aspects affecting the solution, work is being developed in the project that aims to overcome these barriers both by adapting policies and regulation, as well as by developing pilots to provide visibility and demonstrate the technical feasibility of the solution.

Venice LL:

The circularity studied is C9: Increase of industrial water reuse. Increase of water reuse for agriculture has not been studied. The initial business model affected by the circular solution is an LBM (discharge of effluent to the ecosystem) and the innovation strategy followed is that of CBM diversification. After analysing the innovation pathway of the business model, a Scale-up stewardship SCBM archetype has been defined. Furthermore, the CBM can be classified as a Resource Recovery model of the Upcycling subtype. The LL under which this solution is developed is driven by a water company.

The main objective pursued through the implementation of this circularity is increasing the reclaimed water reuse for industrial processes. The industries in the area currently receive both freshwater and industrial water (produced from freshwater by a private company) supplies. The value proposition offered is supplying reclaimed water fit for industrial processes produced through a tertiary treatment process using an Ultrafiltration and Reverse Osmosis System. The reclaimed water guarantees a stably high quality for industrial purposes and stable volume availability over time in comparison with the freshwater quality variation and related risk (e.g. drought events). Its implementation will allow the wwtp to, on the one hand, "Create value from waste" and thus improving the circularity of the plant's processes and, on the other hand, improve the climate resilience of the city and the municipality.

The adoption of a role as stewardship by the lead organisation must be examined through the integrative perspective that the LL has in its context of action, taking into account the set of solutions being studied, and that its objectives are aligned with the enablement and widespread use of reclaimed water (and other recovered resources) in the local and regional environment.

In the preliminary CBM proposed from the developed CBMC, following elements are still to be defined:

- Key partners: definition of the organisational structure depending on the roles and responsibilities in the distribution of reclaimed water to industries.
- Customer segments and Targeted solutions: definition of all customers, and the end-user's final scenario/puzzle.
- Cost Structure & Revenue Streams: The cost structure has not yet defined the distribution costs of reclaimed water, nor the investment in additional distribution infrastructure that would be necessary. Consequently, the revenue streams (e.g. water tariffs), which depend on the previous two points, have not been fixed.

The conclusions that can be drawn from the SWOT analysis of the CBM:

- Strengths and opportunities: Overall the competences and capacities of the driving organisation favour the implementation of the solution. The technology adopted allows the production of stable reclaimed water of different quality and application for different uses, that allows adjusting the value proposition to different uses. In addition, the infrastructure costs are partially covered. The opportunities detected are the good relationship with the authorities, which favours the possibility of adapting policies, and also that industries are interested in the consumption of reclaimed water.
- Weaknesses and Threats: The existence of a private organization that sells industrial water produced from fresh water to local industries could complicate matters. Moreover, one of the threats is the risk of not being able to cover the cost differences between industrial water (from freshwater) and reclaimed water (from WWTP effluent). Additionally, added to this is the risk of uncertain energy prices that may cause an increase in production and distribution costs. Lastly, another weakness is that the current regulation does not specifically incentivize the use of reclaimed water.

The current state of development of the CBM is in the "Detailed Design" phase. Because of the existing uncertainties and the risks presented by the CBM, it is essential during this stage to develop detailed financial analyses to define the cost structures and the costs of production and distribution of reclaimed water for different scenarios so that comparisons can be made with the freshwater tariffs that are being charged to local industries. In the case that costs of production and distribution of the alternative product would be higher than those actually paid for industrial water, it will be necessary to make an assessment to define the necessary financing mechanisms, as well as adaptations of policies and regulations, so that the use of reclaimed water can be incentivised.

Bodø LL:

The circularity studied is **C17: Increase of energy production through biogas**. The initial business model affected by the solution is an **LBM** (linear waste treatment process) and the innovation strategy followed is that of **CBM** diversification and the innovation purposes are aligned with the development of a **Hybrid SCBM: Purposeful sufficiency and Purposeful stewardship**. Furthermore, the **CBM** can be classified as a **Hybrid CBM: Circular Inputs and Resource Recovery** model of the **Industrial Symbiosis** subtype. The LL under which this solution is developed is driven by a public authority and the main partners are a waste management company and municipal water companies operating in the public sector.

The main objective pursued through the implementation of circularity is reducing pollution and increasing the efficiency of resources. The value proposition offered is improving the waste processes

at the plant by maximizing resource efficiency by exploiting biogas recovery from sewage sludge and organic waste that can be transformed into electricity for the plant self-sufficiency. The implementation of the solution will allow the waste management company to "Create value from waste" and on the to "Maximize material and energy efficiency".

Unlike the other circular solutions in the project, in Bodø's LL, preliminary feasibility studies are still underway to determine the technology that will enable the circular solution and define the value chain. Thus, information available for the development of the CBM is limited. According to the innovation process, the CBM is still at the **Ideation stage**, and a Preliminary Assessment is being developed. However, a CBMC and a preliminary SWOT analysis have also been presented. Some of the conclusions derived from the SWOT are presented below:

- **Strengths and opportunities:** The competences and capacities of the waste management sector are aligned with the competences required for the management of a biogas production system. Furthermore, the plant has volumes of organic waste from its nuclear business model that can be mixed with sewage sludge received from the wastewater treatment plants. Additionally, there are no competitors in the region, thus presenting an opportunity for market creation. Moreover, biogas generation projects are being promoted at the national level, which could lead to funding opportunities.
- **Weaknesses and Threats:** some of the weaknesses that have been identified is that the transport of sewage sludge involves long transport distances which can affect the impacts and the level of circularity of the solution. Another potential hindrance is the high cost of the infrastructure and that returns on investment are generally low in self-consumption biogas projects. Finally, another weakness is that agreements between multiple municipalities (sewage sludge comes from several municipalities) may be complex due to the existing regional legislation. Other technical threats are the variability in the quality of substrates for biogas production, and on the other hand, the existence of regulatory barriers that limit the valorisation of digestate from sewage sludge.

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Guidelines to improve new business models at Living Labs (Annex A)

1 Literature review

1.1 Circular Economy

Circular Economy concept:

A circular economy (CE) delineates an economic system rooted in business models that replace the 'end-of-life' paradigm with strategies such as reducing, alternatively reusing, recycling, and recovering material in production, distribution, and consumption processes. This approach operates at multiple levels, including the micro level (involving products, companies, and consumers), meso level (incorporating eco-industrial parks), and macro level (encompassing cities, regions, nations, and beyond). The overarching goal is to achieve sustainable development, characterised by the simultaneous creation of environmental quality, economic prosperity, and social equity, ultimately benefiting both current and future generations (Kirchherr et al., 2017).

Other authors, define CE as an economic system in which resource input and waste, emission, and energy leakages are minimised by cycling, extending, intensifying, and dematerialising material and energy loops. This can be achieved through digitalisation, servitisation, sharing solutions, long-lasting product design, maintenance, repair, reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishing, and recycling. Since a completely closed-loop system is not theoretically possible, CE can be seen from a dynamic perspective - going circular rather than a static perspective of a (impossible) fully circular system in which no leakage of materials and energy occurs (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017).

The shift towards a CE depends on the strategic initiatives undertaken by policymakers and businesses (Lewandowski, 2016). For companies to succeed in this transition, they must innovate their BMs in alignment with CE principles, aiming to dissociate value generation from resource consumption and mitigate environmental impacts (Bocken et al., 2016). The BM serves as a mechanism to prolong the product life cycle and facilitate the deceleration and closure of resource cycles (Kanda et al., 2021).

Figure 1 Circular Economy - System Level Approach (from Bio-based circular economy in European national and regional strategies by Vanhamäki, S., et al., 2019).

CE operating cycle:

In the context of an EC, the biological cycle and the technical cycle represent two distinct but interconnected approaches to resource management. The *biological cycle* encompasses natural processes found in ecosystems, involving living organisms and their interactions with the environment. This cycle emphasizes the regenerative capacity of the biosphere, including the growth, decay, and renewal of organic materials. Examples include composting organic waste to enrich soil or anaerobically digesting organic matter to return to nature. On the other hand, the technical cycle is a human-designed system that focuses on the controlled and efficient use of resources within industrial and technological processes. It involves the extraction, production, use, and recovery of materials, often through manufacturing, recycling, and advanced technologies. Key components of the technical cycle include product design for longevity, material recycling, and the responsible management of waste streams. Both cycles play crucial roles in a circular economy, with the biological cycle emphasizing harmony with natural systems, and the technical cycle highlighting the responsible and efficient use of resources within human-made systems.

Certain products exhibit a dynamic interplay between the technical and biological cycles within the circular economy. Take, for instance, cotton clothing and wooden furniture, which can undergo a series of stages in the technical cycle, including maintenance, reuse, repair, and recycling. However, their journey doesn't end there; eventually, these items can seamlessly transition back to the biological cycle. Through processes such as composting or anaerobic digestion, these products can be reintroduced to the natural environment, enriching the soil, and contributing to the growth of new cotton or wood. This dual-cycle interaction exemplifies the circular economy's holistic approach, where products navigate through both human-engineered systems and the regenerative forces of the biosphere, creating a harmonious and sustainable loop.

Figure 2 Circular economy systems diagram (from: Ellen McArthur Foundation).

Circular economy of water (CEW):

The EC has emerged as a promising framework for promoting sustainable water management. This is due to its principles, such as a closed-loop supply chain, value retention, waste minimization, and resource efficiency, which align well with the complexities of the water sector. The CE is particularly well-suited to address water supply management because, like water, it intersects with various spatial scales (from local to global), levels of governance (micro, meso, and macro), implementation stages (from design to post-use), and economic sectors. Moreover, the CE can be applied to diverse water uses and water-management flows (Morseletto et al. 2022).

Recognizing the unique characteristics of water as a resource, product, and service within the economic system, requires a specific conceptualization which has been proposed in the literature as the circular economy of water (Morseletto et al. 2022). Water serves as a resource crucial for sustaining life and is a vital input for various economic activities, including industrial processes, service delivery, and food and energy production. It can also be considered a product when sold and is embedded in products as virtual water (e.g., in all biological origin products). Additionally, water functions as a service by storing or producing energy, serving as a carrier of biogenic raw materials, and providing essential services for ecosystems, including habitats, and human activities (Tahir et al., 2018).

Strategies for CEW:

Strategies are the approaches adopted by organisations to achieve their objectives while guiding change and transition (Morseletto, 2020). In the context of the Circular Economy of Water (CEW), strategies represent the main pathways toward a more circular use of water and serve as categories to which various CEW solutions and applications can be attributed. Commonly discussed in the CE literature are the R-strategies (with varying numbers depending on the context, ranging from 6R to 10R). These include Refuse, Rethink, Reduce, Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose, Recycle, and Recover. However, it's important to note that some of these strategies relate to general resources and types of industrial production that may not align seamlessly with the water context.

One challenge with the R-strategies classification is the absence of a hierarchical structure, and another issue is associated with defining the system boundaries. In the case of the CEW, the system boundaries are determined by any natural or artificial system where water is managed for economic purposes, as the CE is fundamentally an economic model.

Given water's diverse purposes and the potential for repurposing (e.g., for cooling and then cleaning), the term Repurpose cannot be considered a distinct strategy for water. Instead, used water falls under the categories of Reuse or Recycle. Additionally, Restore (sometimes referred to as Replenish), which involves returning water used by humans to natural systems, aligns with legislation and defined parameters. While Restore is a CE principle and a vital action for natural systems, it cannot be classified as a strategy due to exceeding the defined boundaries of the CE system (Morseletto, 2020).

The CEW strategies are referred on Figure 3.

Figure 3 Strategies of CEW (from Circular Economy of Water: Definition, Strategies and Challenges. Circular Economy and Sustainability, 2(4), 1463-1477, by Morseletto, P., et al., 2022).

1.2 Business Models

The business model can be seen as the conceptual and architectural implementation of a business strategy and as the foundation for the implementation of business processes. The framework of the business model can be organised around the concept of value, identifying three major components: value proposition, value creation and delivery system and value capture (Richardson, 2008).

Following on this definition, a business model describes the rationale of how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010).

There is still not a consensus among researchers and practitioners, on the correct definition of a business model, however most of the recent definitions are founded on the value-logic proposed by Richardson. Some other recent definitions to be considered are:

- Business model as an activity system that is centred on a focal firm and spans its internal/ external boundaries to bridge value creation with value capturing (Lanzolla & Markides et al. 2021).
- Business model represents a system-level approach towards explaining how firms do business by referring to the focal firm's activity system. Business model researchers seek to explain not only the ways in which value is captured, but also how it is created (Snihur & Bocken 2022).
- Business models are defined as simplified representations of the value proposition, value creation and delivery, and value capture elements and the interactions between these elements within an organisational unit. However, since there can be several representations of the same organisational unit, perceptions of the term must be considered that assume an underlying abstract concept that is characteristic of the entity - analogue to capabilities, resources, or strategies, which can be documented in different ways without the document becoming the underlying concept. Not fully considered can be definitions with reduced scope

that assume identity of the business model with one of its elements, for example, the revenue model (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018).

1.3 Sustainable business models and circular business models

Sustainable Business Model:

The consensus among definitions in the literature is that sustainable business models (SBM) are a refinement of the conventional business model concept, with specific characteristics and goals. These definitions typically fall into two categories: 1) those that involve the inclusion of sustainability-oriented concepts, principles, or goals; or 2) those that seamlessly integrate sustainability across elements such as the value proposition, value creation and delivery activities, and/or value capture mechanisms.

Sustainable business models can be defined as business models that incorporate pro-active multi-stakeholder management, the creation of monetary and non-monetary value for a broad range of stakeholders and hold a long-term perspective (Geissdoerfer et al. 2018).

Circular Business Models:

Commonly, Circular Business Models (CBMs) are conceptualized as holistic descriptions of how organizations generate value for their stakeholders, optimize material loops, and consequently capture value (Antikainen & Valkokari, 2016; Bocken et al., 2016). In particular, the prevailing literature on CBMs outlines four discernible logics for value creation: efficient material-technical loops, effective product-service loops, social-collaborative loops, and symbiotic ecosystems (Fehrer & Wieland 2021).

Following on the previous definition for sustainable business models:

Circular business models (CBM) can be defined as SBMs that are specifically aiming at solutions for the CE (i.e. closing, narrowing, slowing, intensifying, and dematerialising resource loops) through a circular value chain and stakeholder incentive alignment (Geissdoerfer et al. 2018a).

Figure 4 delineates the distinctions between BMs, SBMs, and CBMs.

Figure 4 Relationship between BM, SBM and CBM (from Circular business models: A review by Geissdoerfer et al. 2020).

1.4 Business model innovation

Business Model Innovation (BMI) involves introducing innovative business models to the market space where a firm operates (Snihur & Zott, 2019). In practical terms, BMI is an iterative journey that includes experimentation, piloting, gaining experience, and ultimately scaling up (Bocken et al., 2019). The decision to modify or change a firm's business model, or to create a new one for a startup, can be prompted by challenges like decreasing demand or increasing competition. It can also arise from the desire to capitalize on emerging opportunities, such as shifting customer preferences, technological advancements, evolving social practices, or policy changes.

Circular Business Model Innovation (CBMI) is a strategic process that specifically focuses on conceptualizing and implementing Circular Business Models (CBMs). This can involve various approaches, including establishing circular start-ups, diversifying into CBMs, acquiring existing CBMs, or transforming a traditional business model into a circular one. CBMI has the potential to impact the entire business model, its specific elements, the relationships between these elements, and the overall value network (Geissdoerfer et al. 2020):

- **CBM Transformation:** This involves modifying an existing business model, whether it initially follows a conventional or circular approach. The resulting business model incorporates strategies aligned with the principles of the circular economy.
- **Circular Start-ups:** These are new business models created independently of an existing company. Circular start-ups operate with their own brand, employees, and resources, although they may receive support from non-independent institutions like incubators or accelerators. These models incorporate circular economy strategies such as cycling, extending, intensifying, and dematerializing resource loops.
- **CBM Diversification:** This describes the development of new business models within an existing organisation. Utilising internal resources and networks, this approach integrates circular economy strategies without altering the current business model. The new models may either become integral parts of the organisation or spin off as subsidiaries, potentially involving collaborative ventures with other organisations.
- **CBM Acquisition:** This involves merger and acquisition (M&A) activities that target business models with circular economy strategies. The process includes the identification, acquisition, and integration of new circular business models, with the degree of integration varying based on specific circumstances.

Figure 5 Circular Business Model Innovation strategies (from Circular business models: A review by Geissdoerfer et al. 2020).

It is crucial to consider circular business model innovation in conjunction with related technological and social innovations. Technological innovation is a dynamic process characterised by iterations initiated through the identification of new market or service opportunities for technology-based inventions. To qualify as innovation, it must undergo market diffusion and be adopted by end-users. The iterative nature of technological innovation involves both the initial introduction of an innovation and the subsequent reintroduction of an enhanced version (Garcia and Calantone 2002).

Social innovation can be defined as a process characterized by the emergence and adoption of novel solutions and methodologies geared towards achieving social objectives. Concurrently, it involves the restructuring of behaviors, leading to the development of new or improved capabilities and relationships, as well as the more efficient utilisation of assets and resources (Pue et al., 2016). Additionally, social innovation contributes to the establishment of new social norms specifically crafted to address needs and challenges more effectively than existing strategies. Once these emerging norms, relationships, and behaviors permeate and gain acceptance, they instigate substantial transformations in the social landscape (Howaldt, Kopp, et al., 2016).

1.5 Business model innovation pathways

Some authors emphasize that there is an imperfect overlap between SBMs and CBMs (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). For example, CBMs can induce negative consequences for the working conditions of employees (social impact), or they can involve higher material and energy usages than their linear alternatives (environmental impact). Therefore, CBMs are not necessarily sustainable. For this reason, a new conceptualization of business models was proposed by De Keyser & Mathijs (2023) - based on the commonly referred in the literature SBMs archetypes (Bocken et al. 2014, see Figure 6 below) - named sustainable circular business model.

The rest of this section outlines briefly the work developed by De Keyser & Mathijs (2023).

The process to develop this new categorization adjusts the categorization of sustainable business models by distinguishing three subsequent levels of innovation (refer to Figure 7): A technological level integrating the planet-dimension of the triple bottom line, a social level integrating the people-dimension, and an organisational level integrating the prosperity-dimension.

Figure 6 SBMs archetypes (from A literature and practice review to develop sustainable business model archetypes by Bocken et al. 2014).

The first level of innovation is technological, where circular innovations addressing sustainability can concentrate on maximising efficiency, creating value from waste, or substituting materials and energy with renewables. These technological advancements are not mutually exclusive; for instance, a biogas digester can simultaneously create value from biological waste and replace fossil fuels with renewable energy from biogas. The categorization of business models should be approached with the primary goal of the business innovation in mind.

Subsequently, a business model embracing one of these technological innovations has the potential to bring about social innovation. Social innovation, as defined by the European Commission (2013), refers to novel ideas that address social needs, establish social relationships, and foster collaborations. The social level is intricately connected to the technological level through a part-whole relationship: the technological level comprises an aggregation of different BM types on the social level.

Lastly, each business model has the opportunity for organisational innovation by repurposing its objectives towards delivering social and environmental benefits rather than solely economic profit, or by expanding sustainability solutions on a larger scale. In a scaled-up sustainable business entrepreneurs target the mass market with a profit-oriented yet environmentally conscious approach. From a financial perspective, a company repurposing its goals may prioritize the survival of the business, while a company scaling-up its technology aims for a stable income base.

Figure 7 Pathway for sustainable business model innovation (from: A typology of sustainable circular business models with applications in the bioeconomy by De Keyser, E. & Mathijs, E. 2023).

This hierarchy provides a new typology for SCBMs. Upon closer examination, it becomes apparent that there are six distinct archetypes for each technological innovation category—namely, those focused on creating value from waste, maximizing material and energy efficiency, and substituting with renewables and natural processes. These archetypes are identified as purposeful functionality, scaled-up functionality, purposeful stewardship, scaled-up stewardship, purposeful sufficiency, and scaled-up sufficiency.

- *Scaled-up sufficiency* is the reduction of demand-side consumption and hence production or the provision of high-quality durable products while scaling up sustainability solutions to maximise benefits for society and the environment.
- *Purposeful sufficiency* is the reduction of demand-side consumption and hence production or the provision of high-quality durable products while prioritising the delivery of social and environmental benefits rather than economic profit.
- *Scaled-up functionality* is the provision of services that satisfy user needs without users having to own products while scaling up sustainability solutions to maximise benefits for society and the environment.
- *Purposeful functionality* is the provision of services that satisfy user needs without users having to own products, while prioritising delivery of social and environmental benefits rather than economic profit.
- *Scaled-up stewardship* is the manufacturing and/or provision of products and/or services by considering the needs of a range of stakeholders and ensuring their long-term health and wellbeing, while scaling up sustainability solutions to maximise benefits for society and the environment.
- *Purposeful stewardship* is the manufacturing and/or provision of products and/or services by considering the needs of a range of stakeholders and ensuring their long-term health and wellbeing, while prioritising the delivery of social and environmental benefits rather than economic profit.

In Table 1 the main characteristics defining each of the distinct typologies are described.

	Purposeful sufficiency	Scaled-up sufficiency	Purposeful functionality	Scaled-up functionality	Purposeful stewardship	Scaled-up stewardship
<i>How do we create value?</i>	Primarily products	Primarily products	Primarily services	Primarily services	Mix of products and services	Mix of products and services
<i>Who do we create value for?</i>	Relational	Relational and transactional	Relational	Relational and transactional	Relational	Relational and transactional
<i>What is our source of competence?</i>	Production	Production Selling/marketing	Intellectual capability and technology	Intellectual capability and technology Selling/marketing	Networking/ resource leveraging Supply chain management	Networking/ resource leveraging Supply chain management Selling/marketing
<i>How do we competitively position ourselves?</i>	Intimate relationship Product quality Innovation	Product quality Innovation	Intimate relationship Service quality Innovation	Low cost and efficiency Service quality Innovation	Intimate relationship Operational excellence Innovation	Low cost and efficiency Operational excellence Innovation
<i>How do we make money?</i>	Fixed revenue source High operating leverage Low volumes	Fixed revenue source High operating leverage High volumes	Fixed revenue source High operating leverage Low volumes	Fixed revenue source High operating leverage High volumes	Mixed/flexible revenue sources Low operating leverage Low Volumes	Mixed/flexible revenue sources Low operating leverage High volumes
<i>What are our time, scope and size ambitions?</i>	Subsistence or income model	Income or growth model	Subsistence or income model	Income or growth model	Subsistence or income model	Income or growth model

Table 1 SCBMs general characteristics (from: A typology of sustainable circular business models with applications in the bioeconomy by De Keyser, E. & Mathijs, E. 2023).

This does not imply that, in certain instances, there are hybrid business models that equally consider multiple typologies as relevant.

This classification, allows for a distinction of pathways to sustainable business model innovation that links innovative technologies to new business models by providing a clear storyline of how technological innovations can create, deliver, and capture value in environmental, social, and economic contexts.

1.6 Circular business model classification

There are several approaches available for classifying or conceptualizing circular and sustainable business models. Visual frameworks, known as *reference models*, illustrate the components of a circular business model, including revenue mechanisms and customer segments. *Requirements* offer general descriptions of the changes needed in existing business models to align them with circular principles. *Classifications* involve sorting potential structures or arrangements, outlining how a circular business model should be structured, including typologies, taxonomies, or morphological charters. Together, these methods contribute to a thorough understanding of circular business models, facilitating their development and implementation (Geissdoerfer et al. 2020).

Reference models are tied by the static view of CBMI, for this reason they are commonly used to structure and represent business models. Classifications on the other side, are connected to the dynamic view, and help to identify how business models should be changed with circular economy principles (Wirtz et al., 2016).

Below presented is a list of commonly used classifications for circular business models:

- ReSOLVE (EMF et al., 2015).
- Resource Cycles (Bocken et al. 2016).
- Accenture (Accenture, 2014; Lacy et al., 2015, 2020).
- Adapted Accenture (OECD, 2019, Lacy et al. 2015).

A brief description of these models is presented below:

ReSOLVE:

The ReSOLVE framework, rooted in Circular Economy (CE) principles, serves as a tool for generating strategies and growth initiatives to guide governments and businesses toward a circular economy (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015c). ReSOLVE introduces six key business actions-Regenerate, Share, Optimise, Loop, Virtualise, and Exchange-each contributing uniquely to the extension of product lifecycles, increased utilisation, and the transition from finite to renewable resources (Ellen MacArthur Foundation et al., 2015).

Resource Cycles:

The goal is to develop a unified framework and terminology for strategies related to business models in closed loops and closed loop design within a Circular Economy (CE). Proposing strategies centered around the flow of resources, materials, and components through a system, the following approaches are recommended to enhance the cycling of resource loops (Bocken et al., 2016):

- *Slowing resource loops:* This entails designing products with extended lifespans and advocating for product life extension through practices such as repair and remanufacturing. Additionally, it underscores the importance of increasing product utilisation by extending its operational life or intensifying its use.
- *Closing resource loops:* This strategy concentrates on the reuse of materials through recycling, effectively closing the loop between a product's end-of-life phase and the production phase.
- *Narrowing resource loops:* Through resource efficiency, this strategy aims to utilize fewer resources per product, contributing to the narrowing of resource loops. This approach is applicable not only in a Circular Economy but also aligns with principles of resource optimization in a linear economy. Table 2 presents business model strategies based on the resource cycles.

BM Strategy	Definition	Examples
Business model strategies for slowing loops		
Functionality, not ownership / Access and performance model	Providing the capability or services to satisfy user needs without needing to own physical products.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bike and car sharing - Laundrettes - Clothing hire schemes - Document Management Systems - Leasing jeans - Leasing phones

Extending product value	Exploiting residual value of products - from manufacture, to consumers, and then back to manufacturing - or collection of products between distinct business entities	- Automotive industry - remanufacturing parts - Gazelle offering consumers cash for electronics and selling refurbished electronics (gazelle.com) - Clothing return initiatives (e.g. H&M, M&S' Shwopping)
Classic long-life model	Business models focused on delivering long-product life, supported by design for durability and repair for instance	- White goods and furniture (e.g. Miele's 20 year functional life span of appliances) - Luxury products claiming to last beyond a lifetime (e.g. luxury watches such as Rolex or Patek Philippe)
Encourage sufficiency	Solutions that actively seek to reduce end-user consumption through principles such as durability, upgradability, service, warranties and reparability and a non-consumerist approach to marketing and sales (e.g. no sales commissions)	- Premium, high service and quality brands such as Vitsoe and Patagonia - Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)
Business model strategies for closing loops		
Extending resources: collection and resource value	Exploiting the residual value of resources: collection and sourcing of otherwise "wasted" materials or resources to turn these into new forms of value	- Interface - collecting and supplying fishing nets as a raw material for carpets - RecycleBank - providing customers with reward points for recycling and other environmentally benign activities (recyclebank.com)
Industrial Symbiosis	A process- orientated solution, concerned with using residual outputs from one process as feedstock for another process, which benefits from geographical proximity of businesses	- Kalundborg Eco-Industrial Park (http://www.symbiosis.dk/en) - AB sugar and other sugar refiners - internal "waste = value" practices
Business model strategies to narrow resource loops		

Maximise material and energy efficiency	This is about doing more with fewer resources and generating less waste, emissions, and pollution (Efficiency and "zero waste" policies).	- Lean production from Toyota
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Table 2 BMs strategies based on resource cycles.

Accenture:

Accenture presents five CBMs: Circular Inputs (also known as circular supplies or circular supply chain), Sharing Platform, Product as a Service, Product Use Extension and Resource Recovery, that cover the full circular value chain (refer to Figure 8).

Fig. 2.2 Circular value loop—the five business models

Figure 8 Circular value loop-the five business models (from: Lacy et al. 2020).

Each business model has their own distinct characteristics, modifying the pattern of product and material flows through the economy in a different way. While three of the models are more focused on production (Circular Inputs, Product Use Extension, and Resource Recovery), the other two (Sharing

Platforms and Product as a Service) target consumption and the relationship between the product and the consumer (Lacy et al. 2020). These BMs are not mutually exclusive but complementary, as they can be used individually or in combination.

The OECD (2019) presented a framework adapted from Accenture's CBMs (Lacy et al. 2015). Table 3 presents the developed typologies and subtypes of CBMs:

CBM type	Key Characteristics	Resource Efficiency Driver	BM Subtypes	Main Sectors applied in
Circular supply	Provides fully renewable, recyclable, or bio-based resource inputs, replacing traditional single-lifecycle inputs in the supply chain.	Closing resource loops	Cradle to cradle Biomimicry	Consumer products/ services Energy /chemical
Sharing	The utilisation rates of products and assets are optimised through shared ownership, access, and usage typically enabled by digital technologies.	Narrow resource flows	Co-ownership Co-access	Short term lodging Transport Machinery Consumer products
Product as a service	Offer product access and retain ownership to internalise benefits of circular resource productivity.	Narrow resource flows	Product-oriented User-oriented Result-oriented	Transports Chemical Energy Fashion
Product use extension	Extend working lifecycle of products and components through design considerations, repairs, component reconditioning, upgrades, and resale on secondary markets.	Slowing material loops	Classic long life Direct reuse Repair Refurbishment Remanufacture	Automotive Heavy machinery Electronics Fashion Furniture

Resource recovery	Valorisation of the materials contained in waste streams.	Narrow resource flows	Recycling	Metals
	The value of embedded materials or energy from agricultural and industrial goods is captured through collection, aggregation, and processing at the end of a product's use through recycling, upcycling or downcycling.		Upcycling	Paper and pulps
			Downcycling	Plastics
			Industrial symbiosis	Food

Table 3 Accenture CBMs, resource efficiency and CBM subtypes (Adapted from OECD 2019 and Lacy et al. 2020).

A brief description of these models and subtypes is included below:

- Circular supply business models involve substituting traditional production inputs with bio-based, renewable, or recovered materials. By strategically selecting sources during product development, adopting firms can reduce environmental impacts from their supply chains and ensure that product materials avoid becoming waste. Essentially, the circular supply model acts as a form of resource recovery, addressing material recovery at an earlier product lifecycle stage.
- Resource recovery business models focus on producing secondary raw materials from waste streams. The process includes collection, sorting, and secondary production, typically carried out by different market actors. The business case centres on the valorization of materials in waste streams, and recycling variants include downcycling, upcycling, and industrial symbiosis.
- Product life extension models aim to prolong product life, reducing the need for new resource extraction. This involves designing durable products (Classic long life), engaging in reuse and repair activities (Direct reuse, Maintenance, and repair), and remanufacturing products to reset their lifecycle.
- Sharing models, or the sharing economy, involve intensifying the use of under-utilized consumer assets through lending or pooling. Co-ownership and co-access are sub-types of sharing models.
- Product service system (PSS) models combine physical products with a service component. Variants include product-oriented, user-oriented, and result-oriented PSS models, each emphasizing different aspects of the product and service relationship.

1.7 Circular business model ecosystems

Circular business model ecosystems:

Traditional business model literature typically focuses on individual firms when analysing circular business models (Evans et al., 2017). However, Amit and Zott (2001) and other authors, propose a broader conceptualization, situating the business model closer to the network within which a firm operates. While the single-firm perspective is valuable for a detailed analysis of circular activities, it has limitations in comprehensively addressing business endeavours aligned with circular economy principles. Circular initiatives often extend beyond organisational boundaries, covering entire value networks and crossing various sectors and markets (Kanda et al. 2021). Thus, embracing circular

economy principles requires a shift from a firm-centric focus to intensive interaction within an ecosystem of diverse actors (Pieroni et al., 2019).

Embracing this ecosystem view demands enhanced capabilities from companies to effectively manage diverse system components. They also pose challenges such as interdependence, transaction costs, power relations, and the necessity for intermediation in the system to create, deliver, and capture. However, this perspective reveals system benefits (environmental gains), often missed in traditional business model. For example, if analysing a biogas producer from a traditional perspective, the focus might be generally focused on key suppliers, and missing smaller and alternative ecosystem players like local farms (Kanda et al. 2021).

In essence, business ecosystems involve a collaborative approach to customer value creation. These ecosystems feature value networks that extend beyond specific geographical boundaries. The coordination hub is typically led by key actors like large companies, keystone organisations, and platforms, investing in the ecosystem and fostering innovation integration to spur the creation of new markets (Kanda et al. 2021).

For an analysis of an ecosystem, the industrial ecology concept can serve as a starting point since it is a core theoretical root of the CE (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020). Industrial ecology is an approach that borrows concepts from natural ecosystems to design more sustainable industrial systems. A particularly relevant domain of application of the industrial ecology, is the industrial symbiosis (IS), which involves the collaboration and mutual exchange of resources, as well as services and infrastructure, among businesses and other entities through a cooperative network to achieve competitive advantage and reduce environmental impacts (Chertow, 2000).

Industrial Symbiosis:

Industrial symbiosis (IS) diverges from CE strategies in its emphasis on intricate and diverse relationships among firms engaged in producing and utilising waste, forming what is known as the IS network. This contrasts with CE strategies, which often focus on product-service systems or collaborative consumption models where customers hold a central role. The distinctive nature of IS alters the basis for competitive advantage among firms, necessitating a different analysis of business models within IS systems. Consequently, these conceptualizations extend beyond individual firm dimensions (value proposition, creation, delivery, and capture), encompassing other dimensions such as supply chain, governance, and customer interactions within the broader system context (Albino and Fraccascia, 2015).

Companies in industrial networks use wastes to replace production inputs or use them to generate new products that can be put into the market. By adopting the IS practices, companies gain economic benefits (reducing waste discharge costs and input purchase costs) while generating benefits to the environment and society.

Coordination becomes essential among firms when the implementation of Industrial Symbiosis (IS) practices introduces interdependencies that require careful management. As the fundamental mechanism of IS involves the transformation of one firm's waste into another firm's feedstock, firms engaged in IS relationships establish resource interdependence with each other.

As firms become more involved in the network of IS relationships, the degree of interdependence increases requiring higher levels of coordination. In this regard, companies face inter-organisational

challenges, and several inter-firm activities need to be planned to carry out the IS relationship (Bansal and McNight, 2009; Herczeg et al., 2018).

Another dimension to be considered in the governance of the IS system is the *centralization of control*, this is the extent to which an actor plays a central role in the management of the entire system of relationships. A high centralization of control is characterized by a central actor who has disproportionate authority over the other companies that are part of the system, in which symbiotic interactions take place. On the other side the centralization of control is low when symbiotic relationships are managed in a decentralized approach. In this case IS relationships are regulated by contractual mechanisms negotiated by the involved companies, without a central authority (Fraccascia, L., et al. 2019).

Table 4 summarises the elements from the traditional business model adopting a firm-level perspective and elements from the industrial symbiosis and business ecosystem adopting an ecosystem perspective.

Firm-level dimensions (adopted from Richardson, 2008)	Ecosystem-level dimensions (inspired by industrial ecology, industrial symbiosis and business ecosystem literature)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value proposition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value network
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value creation and delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value capture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centralization of control

Table 4 Firm-level vs ecosystem-level dimensions in BM conceptualizations (from: circular business models to circular business ecosystems. by Kanda et al. 2021).

A taxonomy of IS systems is presented in Figure 9 (Fraccascia et al. 2019).

Figure 9 Taxonomy dimensions of IS systems (from: Business models for industrial symbiosis: A taxonomy focused on the form of governance by Fraccascia, L., et al. 2019).

Some of the benefits that can be drawn from the extension of this network in LL are:

- **At the macro level:** to promote the creation of local and regional circular economies (although the benefits of these networks are accentuated by geographical proximity), as well as to promoting regulatory changes.
- **At meso level:** ensure the long-term sustainability of the network and its actors, as it encourages the creation of long-term relationships, promotes collaboration and the development of new opportunities, increase competencies and activities to scale up economic, social, and environmental benefits (e.g. educators and drivers of change, development of new services and products etc.).
- **At the micro level:** organisations ensure the efficiency of processes, the recirculation of materials (reused by other sectors), and the improvement of their organisations' internal services and operations.

1.8 Business Model Canvas

There are different types of tools to guide business model innovation. In this document, a Circular Business Model Canvas (CBMC) based on Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) is used, with significant modifications and the inclusion of new blocks inspired by other canvases in the literature (Islam & Iyer-Raniga, 2023) to incorporate environmental and social elements as well as ecosystem considerations. The value chain dimensions (Bocken et al. 2015) have been considered by segmenting the business blocks into the three dimensions (value proposition, value creation & delivery and value capture). The CBMC is presented in Table 6 with a description of the building blocks and guiding questions.

Circular Business Model Canvas

Living Lab:

Legend:

Circularity goal and scope definition
 - Target CE principle (Select one or more principle)
 - Priority Create value from waste, P2) Maximize energy and material efficiency, P3) Substitute with renewables and natural processes
 • CE strategies (Select one or more strategies)
 - R1 - Reduce, R2 - Avoid, R3 - Reduce, R4-Repairs, R5 - Reuse, R6-Recycle, R7 - Cascading, R8 - Store, R9 - Recover
 • Operating cycle (Select business operation cycle)
 - Technical cycle, Biological cycle
 • Circular business model/innovation strategy (Select innovation strategy)
 - CBM transformation, CBM diversification, Circular start-up, CBM acquisition
 • Sustainable circular innovation pathways (Select one or more)
 - Purpose in terms of key, Scale-up strategy, Purpose in functionality, Scaled-up functionality, Pilot proof of concept, Scale-up strategy
 • Circular business model type (Select one or more of the targeted circular business model type)
 - Circular supplier, Sharing platform, Product as a service, Product lifespan extension, Resource recovery

Sustainability mission and action
 Targeted sustainable development goal
 Goal 1: No poverty, Goal 2: Zero hunger (No hunger), Goal 3: Good health and well-being, Goal 4: Quality education, Goal 5: Gender equality, Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation, Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy, Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth, Goal 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure, Goal 10: Reduced inequality, Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities, Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production, Goal 13: Climate action, Goal 14: Life below water, Goal 15: Life on land, Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions Goal 17: Partnership for the goals

Key Partners	Key Activities	Ecosystem Activities	Value Proposition	Customer Segments	Targeted solution	Benefits and burden
Describe the network of suppliers and partners and the types of collaboration that support the business model execution along the value chain. Guiding questions: <i>Who are the key partners through the value chain (stakeholders, key alliances...) in the LL?</i> <i>Which key resources and key activities do the partners provide?</i> <i>How might we strengthen our partnerships with organizations across the value chain to benefit from circularity (flows of materials, information and capital) in the system?</i>	Main actions that should be implemented and related to the business to operate successfully, to meet the value proposition, sustain the relationship to the target audiences, create revenue streams, etc. Guiding questions: <i>What key activities are required?</i> <i>What activities might best help to achieve the value proposition?</i> <i>What are the key activities based on diversification and long-term goals?</i> <i>What might be the positive externalities of key activities? And how might we monitor and design out any negative externalities?</i>	Tangible and intangible activities. The goal of this element is to address the ecosystem dimension of the business model by including activities that are performed outside by the value network stakeholders and are essential for the success Guiding questions: <i>What kind of activities do partners' ecosystem perform?</i> <i>What kind of resources are we acquiring from partners' ecosystem?</i>	The core component of a business model is characterized by a combination of products and services that create value for a specific type of customer. The objective is to communicate clearly and persuasively how a company's products or services address the problems or meet the specific needs of its customers in a unique and superior way compared to the competition. Guiding questions: <i>What is the added value the LL provides for the target audience? For clients, for stakeholders, for communities, for employees, for environment (if applicable).</i> <i>Which one of your target audience's problems are you helping to solve?</i> <i>What bundles of products and services are you offering to each customer segment?</i> <i>Is there anything associated with our product/service that has potential value to others?</i>	These are all the people, organizations, associations, etc. for which circularity will be creating value. This will include the final users and the paying water reuse, nutrient, energy, sludge, byproducts... users whether public or private, etc. Guiding questions: <i>For whom are you creating value?</i> <i>Define all the potential customers for water reuse, nutrients, energy, byproducts, etc. Of these, who are our most important customers?</i> <i>Who else might benefit from or will be affected by your material/product/service?</i> Define strategy to engage priority clients	The targeted solution, in this context, would be the specific way in which a business addresses the pain points or needs of a customer segment by its products or services. It involves understanding what customers are looking for and tailoring the offerings. Guiding questions: <i>How can products or services be customized for each segment?</i> <i>Adapting the offering to meet the specific needs of each customer group.</i> <i>What type of solutions do we want to provide by our value proposition to customer each segment of customers?</i>	Describe the environmental and social positive and negative impacts. Guiding questions: <i>What kind of benefits will our products/service create on customers, society and environment?</i> <i>What kind of burden will our product/service create on customers, society and environment?</i>
			Channels Way the Living Lab reaches out and communicates with the target audiences. Guiding questions: <i>Which channels are you using to reach the clients? Think about channels per product/service (water, energy, sludge, etc.)</i> <i>Which ones work best? Which ones are most cost-efficient?</i> <i>How are you integrating them with customer routines?</i> <i>How might you redesign your relationship with other supply chain?</i>			
Cost Structure Describe all the costs associated with the circular value chain Guiding questions: <i>Define important costs associated to the value chain of activities (CAPEX and OPEX) and how the costs are aligned to value generation per each activity phase. Which budget is needed to launch the business?</i> <i>What are the most important costs inherent in our business model?</i> <i>Which key resources and activities are most expensive?</i> <i>Which costs could be shared or lowered through other users and partners?</i> <i>Could we shift from an ownership model of underutilised assets to payment for access and usage?</i> <i>How might we reduce cost volatility and dependence on the use of finite resources?</i>			Revenue Streams Represents the revenue models, and description of revenue streams, the Living Lab sets out for capturing value from the value propositions offered to the customer segments. Guiding questions: <i>What value are customers really willing to pay for water reuse and associated products (energy, nutrients, etc)?</i> <i>How much does each revenue stream contribute to overall revenues?</i> <i>What is your pricing mechanism? How might you diversify opportunities to increase resilience, growth, and innovation?</i> <i>How might the business model help create other types of value? Human, social, or natural capital?</i> <i>How might new services increase revenue from existing products, assets or your delivery systems?</i>			

Table 5 Circular Business Model Canvas

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Guidelines to improve new business models at Living Labs (Annex B)

LL	Circularity ID*	Description	Baseline BM1	Innovation type2	BMI strategy3	Innovation pathway			SCBM4	CBM5	
						Technology	Social	Organizational		Type/Subtype	
Alicante	C1	Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion	CBM	BMI	Transformation	Max & Create	Sufficiency & Stewardship	Scaled-up	SS & SST (HM)	RR & CI	IS
Alicante	C2	Increase of water reuse	CBM	BP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Alicante	C3	Recovery of materials/elements : NaClO production	LBM	BMI	Diversification	Create	Stewardship	Scaled-up	SST	RR	RE
Alicante	C4	Nutrient recovery: Ammonia recovery and struvite production	NBM	BMI	Diversification	Create	Stewardship	Scaled-up	SST	RR	RE
Alicante	C5	Increase of energy production: microturbines	-	BP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Alicante	C6	Hydrogen and oxygen production from reclaimed water and biogas	NBM	BMI	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lisbon	C7	Urban water reuse for irrigation	LBM	BMI	Transformation	Create & Substitute	Stewardship	Repurpose	SST	RR & CI	UP
Lisbon	C8	Industrial water reuse for food grade application	LBM	BMI	-	-	-	-	-	RR & CI	UP
Venice	C9	Increase of industrial water reuse	LBM	BMI	Diversification	Create	Stewardship	Scaled-up	SST	RR	UP
Venice	C10	Nutrient recovery: Ammonia recovery (ammonium salts production)	LBM/CBM	BMI	-	-	-	-	-	RR	RE
Venice	C11	Exploit all potential of sludge valorization	LBM/CBM	BMI	-	-	-	-	-	RR & CI	RE
East Frisia	C12	Increase water reuse in dairy industry	LBM	BMI	Diversification	Substitute	Sufficiency	Scaled-up	SS	RR & CI	RE
East Frisia	C13	Municipal/Industrial/Urban wastewater to reclaimed water	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Flanders	C14	Stormwater reuse for irrigation	NBM	BMI	Circular start-up	Maximize	Stewardship	Repurpose	PST	CI	BI
Flanders	C15	Process water to feed drinking water treatment plants	NBM	N/A	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Flanders	C16	Maximization of production in drinking water treatment plant	-	BP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bodø	C17	Increase of energy production through biogas	LBM	BMI	Diversification	Create & Maximize	Sufficiency & Stewardship	Repurpose	PS & PST (HM)	RR & CI	IS

NOTES.

*Circularities identified based on D4.3

¹Baseline Business Model: Circular Business Model, Linear Business Model, New Business Model

²Innovation type: Business Model Innovation or Business process.

³Business Model Innovation strategy: CBM transformation (T), CBM diversification (D), circular start-up (CU), CBM acquisition (A).

⁴Sustainable circular business model (SCBM) by De Keyser et al.: Purposeful sufficiency (PS), functionality (PF) & stewardship (PST); Scaled-up sufficiency (SS), functionality (SF) & stewardship (SST); Hybrid Model (HM)

*CBM type: Circular inputs (CI), Sharing platform (SP), Product as a service (PSS), Product extension (PE), Resource recovery (RR)

*CBM subtype: Product as a service (PSS): Product-oriented, User-oriented & Result-oriented; Resource recovery (RR): Recycling (RE), Upcycling (UP), Downcycling (DO), Industrial Symbiosis (IS), Biomimicry (BI)

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